

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

D2.2 Report on national status in gender equality in Bulgaria, Spain, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia and Slovakia

Legislative and Policy Backgrounds to Promote Gender Equality in Research

Project Acronym: ATHENA

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List of authors

Country	Organisation/acronym	National coordinator	Authors compiling the national reports
Bulgaria	UNIVERSITY OF RUSE ANGEL KANCHEV/URAK	Prof. Dr. Diana Antonova	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Daniel Pavlov
			Assoc. Prof. Dr. Svilen Kune
Spain	UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA /ULPGC	Ángeles Mateo del Pino	Acorán Dávila Medina
			Blanca Hernández Quintana
			Gina Louise Oxbrow
			Irene Sánchez
			María del Pino Santana Quintana
Italy	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE/CNR	Patrizia Grifoni	Gara Sentís Roig
			Sveva Avveduto
			Alessia D'Andrea
			Tiziana Guzzo
			Fernando Ferri
Poland	UNIWERSYTET JANA KOCHANOWSKIEGO W KIELCACH/UJK	Ana Kaminska	Pietro De Murtas
			Małgorzata Druciarek
			Rafał Miernik
			Adrian Mitreğa
			Magdalena Molendowska
Portugal	FUNDO REGIONAL PARA A CIENCIA E TECNOLOGIA/FRCT	Maria LP Martin	Joanna Rudawska
			Kinga Stęplewska
			Lina Silveira (FRCT)
Romania	UNIVERSITATEA DIN BUCURESTI/UB	Laura Grunberg	Berta Pimentel Miúdo (Uac)
			Paulo Fontes (UÉ)
			Laura Grunberg
			Anca Dohotariu
			Corina Ilinca
Slovenia	JOZEF STEFAN INSTITUTE/JSI	Romana Jordan	Alexandra Dragomir (translation and editing support)
			Stefania Chihaiia (translation and editing support)
Slovakia	USTAV VYSKUMU SOCIALNEJ KOMUNIKACIE SLOVENSKEJ AKADEMIE VIED/UVSK SAV	Gabriel Bianchi	Maja Remškar
			Barbora Holubová (ed.)
			Miroslava Žilinská

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

CIG	Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality Portugal
EC	European Commission
EIC	European Innovation Council
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
ENIND	Estratégia Nacional para a Igualdade e a Não Discriminação - Portugal
EQI	Gender Equality Index
ERA	European research area
ERAC	European Research Area and Innovation Committee
FTE	Fulltime equivalent
GCI	Glass Ceiling Index
GE	Gender Equality
GEA	Gender Equality Audit
GEAR	Gender Equality in Academia and Research
H2020	Horizon 2020, EU funding scheme
HEI	Higher Education Institution
HG	Helsinki Group on Gender in Research and Innovation (predecessor of SWG GRI)
HR	Human resources
HRS4R	Human Resource Strategy for Researcher
NCN	National Science Centre - Poland
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
SWG GRI	Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation
WLB	Work Life Balance

Introduction

This overall report provides country-specific information on legislative and policy backgrounds, as well as measures to promote gender equality in research in countries of the Athena project partners: Bulgaria, Spain, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia and Slovakia.

The report presents the Deliverable D2.2. that was prepared within the WP2 as task *T2.2 Assessment of existing national provisions*. This task aimed to conduct an exhaustive assessment of the different national laws, policies and incentives in gender equality in research. This comprehensive report will serve during the GEP implementation period to guide relevant policies and promote gender equality in research at the organisational level. The conclusions drawn from the national reports will be parts of the complex D2.3. Gender Equality National Reports.

To compile this overall report, the following **methodology** was applied. The WP2 lead partner (UVSK SAV) outlined a national report template to guide all other partners in their assessment. Each project partner prepared national country report in accordance with the detailed template structure. In countries where two partners were represented, such as Spain, the task was assigned to one partner, to ULPGC in this case. The national reports have been prepared by utilising extensive desk research focusing mainly on the national legislation and policy documents, such as laws, regulations, strategies, action plans, monitoring and evaluation reports. The national reports have been prepared in April – June 2021 by the project partners and the overall report (D2.2) in July by UVSK SAV.

This overall report is a **compilation of the national reports** as submitted by the project partners. The UVSK SAV team used the verbatim texts from the national reports with only minor changes and sort the provided information by the structure of this report. Therefore, the main credit for the comprehensive report goes to the members of the national teams that participated in the national reports drafts (see the table of authors). The purpose of this approach was to not lose valuable information from each country that can inform all the other partners on gender equality policies and measures in research. The UVSK SAV team utilised most of the information from the national level arrangements.

Not all the aspects of gender equality in society and research are provided for all countries. In some sections, the national information is missing. The reasons for this might be twofold. Either the information was not provided in the national reports, or there is no such arrangement or measures in the country. This is clearly stated in the particular section, or simply no information is provided for the country.

The settings and measures from the organisational level have been incorporated only if of high relevance, such as the Equality Plan in place at ULPGC. Otherwise,

the organisation level information was left out from this report. Project partners are encouraged to use the information in D2.3 Gender Equality National Reports.

As the legislation and policies related to gender aspects in research and higher education institutions are set in a broader societal and political environment, the assessment encompassed broader scope than the area of research. Changes in gender equality at the level of organisation are or can be influenced by overall legislation and policies settings in the field of gender equality in society. At the same time, national policies are in many respects dependent on or at least inspired by international and Pan-European legally or politically binding commitments. For this reason, we have **expanded the scope of the analysis** to the international and European Union’s framework and selected aspects for the promotion of gender equality in society and the workplace. The extended analysis framework thus provides a broader picture of the environment in which the change at the organisational level takes place.

Figure 1 Interplay of the legislative and policies frameworks of GE at various levels

The structure of the report is following the scope of the analysis. The first chapter, prepared by Cira Mendoza and Michelle Perello for the lead partner Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation, reminds us of the international commitments and initiatives to promote gender equality. The European Union’s framework divides into directives and policies to pursue gender-balanced society and specific policy commitments to promote gender equality in the European Research Area. The second chapter is entirely devoted to overall gender equality by listing the primary legislative framework, national bodies, strategic documents, and initiatives in the partners’ countries. The assessment of the policy framework that should actively

encourage gender equality in research and innovation is captured in the third chapter. Starting from the most relevant legislation, strategies, GEP and initiatives, throughout the description of responsible actors and monitoring mechanisms, the structure follows the areas mapped by the Helsinki Group on Gender in Research and Innovation. The chapter further divides into domains of the gender dimension in graduate schools' programmes, gender-aware recruitment, gender balance working conditions and decision-making, gender equality in the research programmes, and gender-disaggregated statistics in research. The annexes contain two relevant lists, namely (a) the legislation and policy documents regarding gender equality in society and (b) national legislation and policies in terms of gender equality in research, innovation and higher education for each country.

The references in the report are formatted as footnotes with hyperlinks if possible to identify immediately the source of information provided.

1. International and European Union commitments for gender equality in society and research and innovations

1.1. International commitments

Gender equality was included in the **Universal Declaration of Human Rights² in December 1948**. Article 1 of the Universal Declaration recognised that *‘all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights’* and article 2 states that *‘everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language (...)’*. Since then, several international commitments and initiatives for equality of rights and opportunities between women and men have been adopted. The global women’s movement gained strength progressively, but most progress has been reached since the 1970s.

In 1969, the General Assembly of United Nations proclaimed the **‘Declaration on the elimination of discrimination against women’**, which set the basis for the Convention on Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination which will be adopted ten years later.

1975 was declared as the International Women’s Year. This year, the United Nations (UN) organized the **1st World Conference on Women** in Mexico City. The Conference advocated for equality between men and women, eliminating discrimination against women and improving their economic status for their effective and speedy participation in the development of their countries, among others.

In 1979, the **International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights³ (ICESCR)** entered into force, guaranteeing rights like the right to work; rights related to marriage, maternity and child protection; the right to an adequate standard of living; the right to health and education; and rights relating to culture and science. This covenant also set out the prohibition of discrimination based on sex and the equal right of men and women to the enjoyment of all rights contained in the treaty.

The same year, the UN General Assembly adopted the **Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW)⁴**, which is considered an international bill of rights for women. This international treaty, which 189 states have ratified, sets up an agenda for national action and is structured in six parts with 30 articles. Part II describes women’s economic and social rights, particularly focusing on education and employment (articles 10 and 11). Article 1 of the treaty defines discrimination against women. Articles 2 and 3

² Available at : <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>

³ Available at : <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/cescr.aspx>

⁴ Available at : <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/cedaw.aspx>

set measures that countries should carry out to eliminate discrimination. Article 5 calls for countries to eliminate all gender stereotyping, prejudices and discriminatory practices. Article 10 lays out countries' obligations and set acceptable norms, including quality of and equality in access to education or the reduction of female dropout rates.

The **4th World Conference on Women**, held in Beijing in 1995, went a step further towards consideration of women's rights as human rights. **The Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action⁵ (BDPA)** was produced as a result of the Conference and provides a clear, straightforward, and actionable blueprint for 189 governments that signed historic commitments to advance women's rights. It is considered a highly significant achievement as it includes a series of strategic objectives focused on 12 areas in which problems and opportunities were analysed from a gender perspective. The 12 areas include 'Inequalities and inadequacies in and unequal access to education and training'; 'Inequality in economic structures and policies, in all forms of productive activities and in access to resources' and 'Inequality between men and women in the sharing of power and decision-making at all levels'. The areas defined strategic objectives, among which strategic objective B addresses 'Education and training of women', and is declined as follow:

- Strategic objective B.1: Ensure equal access to education.
- Strategic objective B.2: Eradicate illiteracy among women.
- Strategic objective B.3: Improve women's access to vocational training, science and technology, and continuing education.
- Strategic objective B.4: Develop non-discriminatory education and training.
- Strategic objective B.5: Allocate sufficient resources for and monitor the implementation of educational reforms.
- Strategic objective B.6: Promote life-long education and training for girls and women.

The BDPA was the first global policy skeleton to confirm gender mainstreaming as a fundamental approach for realizing gender equality and highlighted its significance by calling on governments and other actors to apply it to all policies and programmes. The **Commission on the Status of Women⁶** was established to follow up on the implementation of the BDPA. It establishes a multi-year programme of work with priority themes to be discussed and to take action on them. Particularly, the theme for the year 2021 addresses women's full and effective participation and decision-making in public life.

Gender equality and women empowerment is also promoted by **Millennium Development Goals (MDGs)** set in 2000 by the international community. In 2015, 17 new **Sustainable Development Goals⁷ (SDGs)** with 169 targets to be achieved by 2030 replaced the MDGs. SDG 5⁸ addresses specifically gender

⁵ Available at <https://beijing20.unwomen.org/en/about>

⁶ Available at :<https://www.unwomen.org/en/csw>

⁷ Available at :<https://www.unwomen.org/en/news/in-focus/women-and-the-sdgs>

⁸ See at :<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/gender-equality/>

equality and women empowerment and seeks to achieve women rights, gender equality and women empowerment. SDG 5 sets specific objectives on legal frameworks to end discrimination, violence against women and girls; harmful practices, unpaid care and domestic work, ensure participation and leadership in public life, sexual and reproductive health and reproductive rights and economic rights. SDG 5 is mainstreamed into many of the other SDG goals, sending a strong message about the achievement of gender equality across different sectors. One of these sectors is 'Education', which is promoted through SDG 4 and calls for inclusive and equitable education of good quality. SDG 4 is being also supported through 'The Education 2020 Framework for Action', which recognizes that gender equality is key to extend the right to education. The Framework states that governments should apply gender-sensitive policies, plans and learning environments, including the elimination of gender-based discrimination and violence and providing gender-equitable instruction. Target 4.4 of SDG 4 particularly claims for the elimination of gender disparities in education.

The **UNESCO's Convention against Discrimination in Education (CADE)** is a cornerstone of the Education 2030 Agenda and is a powerful tool to achieve SDG4. It is the only international treaty specific for education, prohibiting gender discrimination and addressing access to and quality of education. Article 2 permits gender-segregated education institutions provided they provides the same quality, equivalent content and meet the same standards as gender-integrated institutions.

The latest relevant international convention addressing gender equality was the **2020 G20 Leader Summit**, which was held virtually due to COVID-19 pandemic. In the G20 Leader Summit, the EU and other G20 leaders agreed to set up efforts on women's empowerment to reducing the gender employment gap by 25% by 2025. Members adopted policy guidelines on digital financial inclusion for youth, women and SMEs and policy options to enhance opportunities for all.

1.2. European framework for gender equality

Equality between women and men is one of the European Union's founding values. It is anchored in European Union's fundamental documents and reflected in directives, decisions and policies. The promotion of gender equality in whole society and particularly in areas, such as equal treatment and work and parental leave, give the basis for setting the equality standards in research and innovation.

1.2.1. In an overall society

The **Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union**⁹ advocates for equality between men and women. Its article 23 states that '*equality between men and women must be ensured in all areas, including employment, work and*

⁹ Available at :https://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf

pay. *The principle of equality shall not prevent the maintenance or adoption of measures providing for specific advantages in favour of the under-represented sex*¹⁰. In the same way, articles 2 and 3 of the **Treaty on the European Union**¹⁰ also calls for equality between women and men. The recognition of legal equality between women and men in the European Union is a fact, but the task of achieving effective and real equality between both sexes is still pending. The principle of equal opportunities for women and men is a fundamental element in the political, social and economic construction of the European Union, ensuring balanced participation of both sexes in all spheres of public and private life (Principles 2 and 9 of the **European Pillar of Social Rights**¹¹).

EU main directives on gender equality

EU legislation contains a considerable number of provisions on gender equality, mainly various provisions of the treaty that establishes the European Economic Community and directives on access to employment, equal pay, maternity and paternity leave, social and occupational security, burden of proof in cases of discrimination and self-employment. These directives, among other aspects, regulate the right to equal treatment of women and men at work, the level of pay, social security and access to goods and services. They also provide special protection for pregnant women and women who have recently had children and establish common rules for self-employed women and their assisting spouses.

- **Equal treatment at work**

Article 141 of the Treaty that establishes the European Economic Community lays down the principle of equal pay for male and female workers for equal work under equal conditions. The first step towards achieving this objective of equality at work was the adoption of **Council Directive 75/117/EEC** of 10 February 1975 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to the application of the principle of equal pay for men and women.

The notion of equal pay in **Article 141 of the Treaty that establishes the European Economic Community**, ex Article 119, includes social security benefits related to the various occupational schemes. It is Council **Directive 86/378/EEC of 24 July 1986** on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women in occupational social security schemes, which regulates equal access to and payment of social security benefits.

The Treaty establishing the European Economic Community also established the pillars of European legislation on equal treatment between women and men in employment and occupation, which were laid down in **Council Directive 76/207/EEC of 9 February 1976** on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion and working conditions. This directive was amended in

¹⁰ Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:2bf140bf-a3f8-4ab2-b506-fd71826e6da6.0023.02/DOC_1&format=PDF

¹¹ Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/economy-works-people/jobs-growth-and-investment/european-pillar-social-rights/european-pillar-social-rights-20-principles_en

2002 by **Directive 2002/73/EC** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 September 2002.

In relation to the application of Article 141 of the Treaty and the situations described above, **Council Directive 97/80/EC of 15 December 1997** on the burden of proof in cases of discrimination based on sex was adopted. This Directive provides that the Member States, in accordance with their judicial systems, must take the necessary measures to ensure that, where the plaintiff adduces before a court of law or other competent authority facts from which it may be presumed that discrimination has occurred, it is for the defendant to prove that there has been no breach of the principle of equality.

In order to avoid the dispersion of legislation and to recast all the directives mentioned so far, **Directive 2006/54/EC** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation was adopted in 2006, which synthesises and repeals Directives 75/117/EEC, 76/207/EEC, 86/378/EEC and 97/80/EC. Thus, equality provisions affecting all areas of social life, of which work is unquestionably an integral part, are contained in a single body of law. Three areas can be distinguished in the application of this Directive:

- Access to employment, promotion at work and vocational training.
- Working conditions and pay
- Occupational social security schemes.

Equal pay for equal work and pay transparency

The requirement to ensure equal pay is set out in Directive 2006/54/EC¹² as complemented in 2014 by a Commission Recommendation on pay transparency¹³. Despite this legal framework, the effective implementation and enforcement of this principle in practice remains a challenge in the EU. Lack of pay transparency has been identified as one of the key obstacles. Therefore in March 2021, proposal for a **Directive of the European Parliament and of The Council to strengthen the application of the principle of equal pay for equal work or work of equal value** between men and women through pay transparency and enforcement mechanisms was approved.¹⁴ The directive would require for example, the transparency of pay setting and career progression policy or reporting on pay gap between female and male workers.

Pregnant workers and parental leave

Council Directive 92/85/EEC of 19 October 1992 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding

¹² Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation (OJ L 204, 26.7.2006, p. 23).

¹³ Commission Recommendation 2014/124/EU of 7 March 2014 on strengthening the principle of equal pay between men and women through transparency (OJ L 69, 8.3.2014, p. 112).

¹⁴ Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021PC0093>

provides special protection for workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding. Pregnant workers are protected from discrimination in the aforementioned Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006.

Provisions on job protection and conditions for parental leave for workers are laid down in Council **Directive 2010/18/EU** of 8 March 2010 implementing the revised Framework Agreement on parental leave concluded by BUSINESSEUROPE, UEAPME, CEEP and ETUC and repealing Directive 96/34/EC. This directive calls for a commitment by states to sanction employers in case of non-compliance with the measures agreed in this directive.

- **Equal treatment in statutory social security schemes**

Under **Council Directive 79/7/EEC** of 19 December 1978 on the progressive implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women in matters of social security, the European Union obliges the Member States to implement the principle of equal treatment in the field of social security, both for the active population, including workers on sick leave, injured or unemployed and jobseekers, as well as retired and disabled workers.

- **Self-employed workers and their spouses**

Directive 2010/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 July 2010 on the application of the principle of equal treatment between men and women engaged in an activity in a self-employed capacity and repealing **Council Directive 86/613/EEC** on the application of the principle of equal treatment between men and women engaged in an activity, including agriculture, in a self-employed capacity, and on the protection of self-employed women during pregnancy and motherhood serves as a complement to legislation on equal treatment in employment and occupation relating to social security.

In particular, it lays down a number of measures applicable to self-employed workers and spouses assisting them in their work without having the legal form of employees or partners. Provisions relating to the establishment of a company or the participation of assisting spouses in the social security system are included in this Directive.

- **Access to goods and services**

As a consequence of the protection afforded by Article 13 of the Treaty establishing the European Economic Community, which provides for the adoption of Community rules against discrimination on the grounds of sex in areas other than employment, **Council Directive 2004/113/EC** of 13 December 2004 implementing the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services is adopted. This directive aims to

combat discrimination based on sex in access to goods and services, particularly in the field of insurance.

EU main decisions and conclusions on gender equality

In accordance with Article 249 of the Treaty of the European Communities, a decision is an individual legal act of a Community institution addressed to one or more addressees and binding on them in its entirety as to its elements, form, means and outcome. The main decisions of the European Union in the field of equality between men and women are:

- Commission Decision 82/43/EEC of 9 December 1981 setting up an Advisory Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men.
- Council Decision 2000/750/EEC of 27 November 2000 establishing a Community action programme to combat discrimination.
- Decision No 848/2004/EEC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 establishing a Community action programme to promote organisations active at European level in the field of equality between men and women.
- Decision No 771/2006/EEC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 May 2006 establishing the European Year of Equal Opportunities for All (2007): Towards a Just Society.
- Decision No 1672/2006/EEC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 2006 establishing a Community Programme for Employment and Social Solidarity.

Despite the EU Council conclusions have no legal effects, they are relevant documents to express policy positions on issues related to EU policy areas. Many have been the conclusions that have been adopted by the EU council on gender equality, being a relevant one for the present study the **Conclusion 14254/19 on 'Gender-equal economies in the EU: The way forward'**¹⁵. Drafted within the framework of the annual review of the implementation of the UN agenda for gender equality and women's empowerment by the EU and its member states (Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action, adopted in 1995), the conclusions acknowledge the progress achieved by the EU in certain areas, such as the adoption of the work-life balance directive, the increased share of women on the boards of large companies and the reduced number of women and men at risk of poverty or social exclusion. At the same time, the conclusions call on member states and the Commission to further promote gender equality as a political priority and through concrete measures.

The EC has also published a great number of recommendations on gender equality. Some of them and relevant for the present analyses are the 1) **Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/951 of 22 June 2018 on standards for equality bodies**¹⁶ and 2) **Commission Recommendation of 7 March 2014**

¹⁵ Available at :<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-14254-2019-INIT/en/pdf>
¹⁶ Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32018H0951>

on strengthening the principle of equal pay for women and men through transparency¹⁷ .

EU Action Plan, strategies and initiatives on gender equality

Many are the initiatives that the European Union has put into place over the years to promote and realize gender equality and women's empowerment. The European Union has recently adopted several initiatives to take steps to further equality between women and men. The **Gender Action Plan III for 2021-2025 (GAP III)**¹⁸ was endorsed¹⁹ by the 24 EU Member States in December 2020 and set out an ambitious agenda to promote gender and women's empowerment through external action of the European Union: external policies, diplomacy and political dialogue, sectors and aid modalities at country and regional and multilateral levels. The EU intends to achieve progress in the following key areas of GAP III:

- i) Freedom from all forms of gender based violence;
- ii) Promotion of sexual and reproductive health and rights;
- iii) Strengthening of economic and social rights and empowerment of women and girls;
- iv) Advancement of participation and leadership;
- v) Implementation of the EU policy framework on Women, Peace and Security agenda;
- vi) Harnessing the challenges and opportunities of the green transition and digital transformation.

In March 2020, the EC presented the **EU Action Plan for 2020-2024 on human rights and democracy**²⁰. The action plan emphasizes that the heart of the EU's response may lie on a gender responsive approach and the EU commits to act on women's empowerment, preventing and combatting sexual and gender-based violence, addressing multiple and intersecting forms of discrimination, promoting rights-based and gender responsive justice and improving access to justice and legal assistance. Some of these provisions are also included within the **Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2024**²¹, a key instrument to achieve a Union of Equality²². The Strategy defines policy objectives and actions to be taken to progress towards a gender-equal Europe. It pursues the key objectives of: 1) ending gender-based violence; challenging gender stereotypes; closing gender gaps in the labour market; achieving equal participation across different sectors of the economy; addressing the gender pay and pension gaps; closing the gender care gap and achieving gender balance in decision-making and politics. The Strategy also stresses gender mainstreaming as a key tool for the Commission's gender equality work.

¹⁷ Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32014H0124>

¹⁸ Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/international-partnerships/system/files/join_2020_17_en_final.pdf

¹⁹ Available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-13947-2020-INIT/en/pdf>

²⁰ Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:e9112a36-6e95-11ea-b735-01aa75ed71a1.0002.02/DOC_3&format=PDF

²¹ Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0152>

²² Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/commissioners/2019-2024/dalli/announcements/union-equality-first-year-actions-and-achievements_en

In order to contribute to the promotion and strengthening of equality between men and women, the EU Parliament and the Council established the **European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)**, based in Vilnius (Lithuania). The Institute implement measures such as gender mainstreaming in all EU and national policies and combats gender discrimination and promotes awareness of gender equality by providing technical assistance to the EU institutions. Among other activities, it is involved in collecting, analysing, and disseminating data and methodological tools. EIGE is also responsible for monitoring EU advances on the Beijing Platform. Last year in 2020, EIGE published the report 'Beijing+25: the fifth review of the implementation of Beijing Platform for Action in the EU Member States'²³ as 2020 marked 25 years of the BDPA adoption. The report tracks progress against the long-standing challenges identified in the BDPA and goes beyond by assessing new challenges that have emerged in recent years, including those that have appeared by digitalisation or recent migration flows, among others.

EU response to the COVID-19 pandemic from the point of view of the role of women

During the first week of the COVID-19 crisis, the EU and the Member States signed a statement together with 145 UN Members and Observers, under a call made by the UN Secretary General to put women and girls at the heart of the pandemic response plans and addressing the dramatic rise in gender-based violence. The statement claimed zero tolerance towards gender-based violence and recognised the role of women in the fight against COVID-19.

The EIGE Institute documented the impact due to the pandemic from a gender perspective. The report 'Coronavirus puts women in the frontline'²⁴ addresses different aspects that have been affecting by the health crisis, including men's mortality rates; extra challenges for public transport users; concern for severe job losses in women-dominated professions; unpaid care work; physical distancing; domestic abuse; and women decision-makers.

1.2.2. In research and innovation

The European Union, and more specifically the European Commission, are strongly committed to promoting gender equality in research and innovation. The **European Research Area (ERA)** is the drive to create a borderless market for research and innovation across the EU, helping countries strongly aligning their research policies and programmes. Gender equality in research and innovation is a priority of the ERA. Under the ERA Communication Framework, the EC set 3 objectives to work with EU countries and boost institutional change:

- Gender equality in scientific areas.
- Gender balance in decision making.

²³ Available at: <https://eige.europa.eu/publications/beijing-25-fifth-review-implementation-beijing-platform-action-eu-member-states>

²⁴ Available at: <https://eige.europa.eu/news/coronavirus-puts-women-frontline>

- Integration of the gender dimension into the content of research and innovation.

The **Communication on the ERA**²⁵ includes a common action between EU countries to strengthen gender equality provisions. Action 12²⁶ invites EU countries to develop concrete plans to promote gender equality, diversity and inclusiveness in science, research and innovation. The ERA, in conjunction with the Communication on the ERA, the Skills Agenda²⁷ and the new Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027,²⁸ also pursues to reinforce increasing participation of women in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM).

The **Conclusions on advancing Gender Equality in the ERA**²⁹ recognises the need to foster sustainable cultural and institutional changes in the ERA national action plans or strategies to implement the ERA Roadmap for achieving gender equality and including the gender dimension in R&I content and programmes; and encourages Member States to make institutional change a key element of their national policy framework on gender equality in R&I. The conclusions also highlight the role that awareness raising, education, training and exchange of best practices in relation to advancing gender equality in R&I can play at institutional level. The conclusions also invite the Member States and research funding organisations to provide incentives to encourage research performing organisations, including universities, to revise or develop gender mainstreaming strategies, gender equality plans including the gender dimension in R&I content and programmes and mobilise adequate resources to ensure their implementation. Research organisations are also invited to support flexible and family-friendly working conditions and arrangements for both women and men in R&I, including supporting equal sharing of care responsibilities and reviewing the assessment of researchers' performance to eliminate gender bias. These organisations are encouraged to implement institutional changes by implementing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). Funds to Research Performance Organizations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) to develop and implement their GEPs are provided through Horizon 2020.

Concerning the new **Horizon Europe**³⁰ programme, gender equality continues being considered a crosscutting priority. Strengthened provisions are included³¹ in order to better implement the EU gender equality objectives by research and innovation organisations across the EU, being these: 1) more women participating in research and innovation programmes; 2) better integration of the gender dimension in the content of research and innovation projects; 3) more participation of EU widening countries in actions dedicated to gender equality in research and innovation organisations, and 4) broadening gender equality

²⁵ Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/education/resources-and-tools/document-library/eea-communication-sept2020_en

²⁶ Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-law-and-publications/publication-detail/-/publication/aae418f1-06b3-11eb-a511-01aa75ed71a1>

²⁷ Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1223>

²⁸ Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/education/education-in-the-eu/digital-education-action-plan_en

²⁹ Available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-14846-2015-INIT/en/pdf>

³⁰ Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe_en

³¹ Factsheet on gender equality in Horizon Europe:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/strategy_on_research_and_innovation/documents/ec_rtd_gender-equality-factsheet.pdf

policies in research and innovation to intersections with other potential grounds for discrimination such as ethnicity, disability and sexual orientation. The new provisions include: 1) that public bodies, research and higher education organisations will be required to have a GEP in active to be able to get funding from the programme; 2) flagship measures and activities promoting gender equality under the European Innovation Council (EIC), including a target of 40% women-led companies invited to pitch their projects, a target of 50% women among members of advisory structures, a prize for women innovators and a dedicated initiative to support women-led start-ups new eligibility criterion to get access to the programme funding; 3) particular attention will be paid to ensuring gender balance in evaluation panels and in other relevant advisory bodies, such as boards and expert groups; 4) the integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation content becomes a requirement by default across the whole programme; 5) specific funding will be made available for actions supporting the development of inclusive GEP in research and innovation organisations across Member States and associated countries under 'Widening Participation and Strengthening the ERA' part of the programme. Institutional change through the implementation of GEPs is a strategy aiming at removing barriers to gender equality inherent to the research system and adapting the practices of the research organisations.

The recovery instrument '**Next Generation EU**'³² is aiming at helping repair the economic and social damage caused by the COVID-19. It is the most extensive stimulus package ever financed in Europe, amounting to 1.8 trillion euros. A significant amount will be devoted to supporting the modernisation of research and innovation via Horizon Europe, paying particular attention to gender equality. The recovery plan requires Member States to explain how the measures in their national recovery plans will contribute to gender equality, thus ensuring a gender equal and fair recovery in the EU.

The expert group funded by H2020 '**Gendered Innovations**' produced a policy report³³ providing researchers and innovators with tools to develop sex, gender and intersectional analysis. The report also addresses key research and innovation areas for Horizon Europe missions, clusters, and partnerships, including climate change, urban planning, agriculture, health, artificial intelligence and robotics, and the COVID-19 pandemic, among others.

The **Erasmus+ programme** will complement Horizon Europe's provisions supporting gender equality, including strong synergies for higher education institutions and the European Universities alliance.³⁴

The European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers³⁵ is a recommendation launched of good practice for researchers and employers and/or funders of researchers issued by the

³² Available at https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/recovery-plan-europe_en

³³ Available at https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/gendered-innovations-2-how-inclusive-analysis-contributes-research-and-innovation_en

³⁴ More information available at https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/node_en

³⁵ Available at: https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/am509774cee_en_e4.pdf

European Commission Directorate-General for Research to make the research an attractive career. The document, launched in 2005, proposes the rights and duties of researchers and their funding institutions and outlines principles for hiring and appointing researchers.³⁶ As of 2021, 1280 organisations have endorsed the Charter & Code principles.³⁷ Among the general principles and requirements of the Charter applicable to employers and funders is, inter alia, the principle of *gender balance* (*employers and/or funders should aim for a representative gender balance at all levels of staff, including at supervisory and managerial level*). Within good practice in recruitment is, for example, a recommendation that the *career breaks and other multidimensional career tracks should not be penalised*.³⁸ The implementation of the document was left to peer pressure and can serve as a quality certificate for research institutions. As of 15 May 2018, institutions that are willing to endorse the Charter and Code are initiating the application for the "HR Excellence in Research Award", which implies a long-term commitment.³⁹

³⁶ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter-code-researchers>

³⁷ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter/declaration-endorsement>

³⁸ Available at: https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/am509774cee_en_e4.pdf

³⁹ More on the HRS4R application process, visit <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/node/5765/#hrs4r-tabs-tab-1-name>

2. Status of gender equality in the partners' countries

The overall status of gender equality in the partners' countries provides the background of promoting gender equality in the research and higher education organisations.

Following the Gender Equality Index (GEI), the scores in 2020 rank from the lowest 54.4 score in Romania to the highest 72-point score in Spain out of the maximum 100-point score. Although most countries recorded improvements in the last decade, none of the countries reached the maximum score of 100 points. Moreover, Romania, Slovakia, Poland, Bulgaria, Portugal and Italy fall below the EU-27 average (67.4), while Slovenia slightly above (67.7) and Spain at the 72-point score.⁴⁰

Figure 2 Overall Gender Equality Index Scores (EIGE, 2020)

Source: EIGE Statistics Database, Gender Equality Index scores, domain scores and sub-domain scores [index_data__index_scores]

The GEI's score consists of six domains scores work: money, knowledge, time, power and health reflecting the EU gender equality framework. The domain of work compares the position of women and men in the European Union's labour market. It measures gender gaps in participation in the labour market, duration of working life, sectoral segregation patterns and quality of work (such as flexibility of working time and career prospects). The domain of money examines inequalities in financial resources and the economic situation of women and men. It measures gaps in earnings and income, as well as the risk of poverty and income distribution. The domain of knowledge shows differences between women and men in terms of education and training. This domain measures gaps in participation in tertiary education, segregation in educational fields and lifelong education. The domain of time measures inequalities in the allocation of time that women and men spend for different activities. It measures gender gaps in the involvement of women and men in caring for their children or grandchildren, older

⁴⁰ EIGE (2020). Gender Equality Index. <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2020>

people and people with disabilities, as well as their involvement in cooking and housework in comparison to time spent on social activities. The domain of power measures gender equality in decision-making positions across the political, economic and social spheres. The domain of health measures gender equality in three health-related aspects: health status, healthy/unhealthy behaviour and access to health services.⁴¹

The domain scores reveal which areas pull the gender equality in the countries down. While the work participation and health domains scores are often above the EU-27 average, the score of time, power and knowledge domains indicate series of drawbacks in the gender-fair environment.

Bulgarian national team reported that from Eurostat data, we see that Bulgaria is in SECOND place in the EU in terms of the share of managerial positions held by women - as much as 49% compared to an average of 39% for the EU. This once again confirms and proves that there is no inequality in terms of those distributed in high positions on the basis of gender. At the same time, the "advanced countries" from which Bulgaria usually like to learn, such as Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, France, are significantly behind Bulgaria in this respect.⁴²

Table 1 Gender Equality Index domain scores (2020)

COUNTRY	Work	Money	Knowledge	Time	Power	Health
Bulgaria	69	62,3	54,9	42,7	61,5	77,2
Spain	73,2	77,8	67,6	64	69,4	90,1
Italy	63,3	79	61,9	59,3	48,8	88,4
Poland	67,3	75,5	57,2	52,5	30	83,1
Portugal	72,9	72,8	55,7	47,5	51,1	84,6
Romania	67,6	63	52,4	50,3	37,5	71,2
Slovenia	73,1	83	55,9	72,9	55	86,9
Slovakia	66,6	75,1	61,2	46,3	29,6	85,5
EU-28 average	71,4	81,6	62,8	64,9	53,1	87,8

Source: EIGE Statistics Database, Gender Equality Index scores, domain scores and sub-domain scores [index_data__index_scores]

Despite relatively high scores in the GEI money domain, based among others on mean monthly earnings (PPS) and equalised net income (PPS), the latest available data on gender overall earnings gaps present persistent gaps to the detriment of women. This synthetic indicator considers three types of disadvantages for women in the labour market: lower hourly earnings, lower hours worked in paid work, and lower employment rates due to interruptions in childcare or other dependent family members.

⁴¹ EIGE, Gender Equality Index. <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2020>

⁴² Report on national status in gender equality in research for BULGARIA (2021), not published

Table 2 Gender overall earnings gap (% , 2018)

COUNTRY	Gender overall earnings gap ⁴³
Bulgaria	24,1
Spain	33,0
Italy	43,0
Poland	30,7
Portugal	20,6
Romania	25,3
Slovenia	21,0
Slovakia	35,5
EU-28 average	n/a

Source: Eurostat, Gender overall earnings gap [TEQGES01]

Nevertheless, even countries such as Spain, Italy, Slovenia, all scoring high in GEI in comparison to other countries, report that despite a solid basis for gender equality, full recognition of GE is insufficient.

Bulgarian partners stated that the progress on gender equality is evolving curvilinearly, and a new impetus is needed. There are still differences in education, employment, pay, care, participation in government and pensions. Too many people in the Member States still violate the principle of gender equality through sexist hate speech and by blocking action to combat gender-based violence and gender stereotypes. Some citizens of Bulgaria are no exception in this context. Gender-based violence and harassment persist, and this is a cause for concern.⁴⁴

2.1. Legislative framework

Following the legislative framework of the analysed countries, equality of men and women is a fundamental principle defined and grounded in the Constitutions. According to the national reports, gender equality is reflected in the constitutional law in broader terms, while the full recognition of gender equality has not proved to be sufficient. Countries also vary on the level and ways to meet international legal acts and EU Directives. Following EEC Directives No. 75/117 and No. 76/207 on equal pay and equal treatment between men and women meant some amendments or adjustments to the countries' labour code/acts. Some countries reflected these directives through anti-discrimination acts (Slovakia, Slovenia, Romania, Portugal, Bulgaria) or act on equal opportunities (Slovenia, Romania, Italy, Spain), in case of Poland Law on the Implementation of some EU Provisions on Equal Treatment was adopted (see detailed list of the relevant acts in Annex

⁴³ The gender overall earnings gap is a synthetic indicator. It measures the impact of the three combined factors, namely: (1) the average hourly earnings, (2) the monthly average of the number of hours paid (before any adjustment for part-time work) and (3) the employment rate, on the average earnings of all women of working age - whether employed or not employed - compared to men (Eurostat, 2020, [TEQGES01])

⁴⁴ BG national report within Athena project, not published.

1). Despite the differences, the EU has had a significant influence on gender mainstreaming in all of the consortium's countries.

Here we provide several examples of the main legislative framework promoting gender equality in society as a whole and specific areas.

A significant part of the national legislation in the Republic of **Bulgaria** related to equal opportunities for women and men has been adopted in the process of its harmonisation with the *acquis communautaire*. In this process, national norms have been aligned with EU primary and secondary legislation, notably in the areas of equal treatment for women and men, equal opportunities for all and the fight against all forms of gender-based violence.

Historically, the principles of equality and non-discrimination between the sexes are laid down in the provisions of the Constitution of the Bulgarian Principality, adopted on 16 April 1879, which pass into the Constitution of the Republic of Bulgaria (Promulgated, SG No. 56/1991). The Labour Code (Promulgated, SG No. 26/1986) categorically prohibits all forms of discrimination, privileges, restrictions on the grounds of sex and introduces the principle of equal pay for women and men. Anti-discrimination provisions in relation to gender are contained in the Employment Promotion Act (Promulgated, SG No. 112/2001), the Social Assistance Act (Promulgated, SG No. 56/1998), the Employment Act. higher education (Promulgated, SG No. 112/1995), the Law on Defence and the Armed Forces of the Republic of Bulgaria (Promulgated, SG No. 112/1995) and others. The Family Code (Promulgated, SG No. 41/1985) is based on the principle of "Equality between men and women ...", the Social Security Code (Promulgated, SG No. 110/1999) introduces the principles of obligation and universality of insurance and equality of insured persons. The Penal Code (Promulgated, SG No. 26/1968) qualifies as crimes against the person rape, incitement to prostitution and trafficking in human beings, as well as coercion to sexual acts through the use of official or material dependence of the person. The Law on Protection against Discrimination (Promulgated, SG No. 86/2003) largely achieves compliance with the *acquis communautaire* in the field of equal treatment, equality of opportunity and participation in public life, effective protection against discrimination of gender, protection from harassment, sexual harassment, equal pay, equality in employment and the exercise of the right to work, the protection of pregnant women and the reverse burden of proof.

The **Spanish Constitution** of 1978 states that equality is one of the highest values of the legal system (art. 1) and proclaims that all Spanish people are equal before the law, prohibiting any discrimination based on sex (art. 14). Likewise, the Constitution declares the full legal equality of men and women in marriage (Art. 32) and condemns discrimination on grounds of sex in employment, including wages (Art. 35). Paradoxically, it places men ahead of women in the order of succession to the throne (Art. 57).

These constitutional references to equality are part of what is known as formal equality, which often become useless if they are not accompanied by corrective measures to make them real; in other words, it is not enough to recognise formal

equality if real equality is not also recognised. The Spanish Constitution incorporates this principle so that equality policies are aimed at removing the obstacles that prevent or hinder full equality, as well as facilitating the participation of all citizens in political, economic, cultural, and social life (art. 9.2). The Spanish Constitution, therefore, makes it possible to adopt corrective mechanisms for inequality, even before the UN approved the CEDAW, an instrument of great importance - as we have already seen - to articulate an international legal framework for equality, since it requires States Parties not only to not discriminate, but also to modify the traditional role of men and women in society and in the family. In addition, it allows them to adopt positive action measures, of a temporary nature, aimed at accelerating the equality between men and women (art. 4 CEDAW).

As far as secondary legislation is concerned, two Community rules led Spain to adjust its legal framework: Directive 2002/73/EC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women, regarding the access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions; Directive 2004/113/EC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women in the access to goods and services.

Its mandatory implementation in our national law led to the approval of Organic Law 3/2007, of 22 March, on Effective Equality between Women and Men (LOIEMH). One of the main characteristics of this law is precisely the implementation of the principle of mainstreaming and its projection in all policies at all levels and orders.

Decree-Law 6/2019 (“on the urgent measures to guarantee equal treatment and opportunities for women and men in employment and occupation”) included new measures to promote equality between men and women in the workplace (it also included various provisions to gradually increase statutory paternity leave to 16 weeks by 2021). In this regards, Royal Decrees 901/2020 (Gender Equality Plan) and 902/2020 (Gender Pay Reporting) will enter into effect on 14 January 2021, and 14 April 2021, respectively. Mainly, the new regulation extended the existing obligation to **implement a gender equality plans in Spain to companies** with 50 or more employees (previously 250 or more employees). Among other obligations, the above referred companies shall be required to develop wage registries showing average pay levels disaggregated by gender; and such registries have to be made available to the workers’ legal representatives for review. Employers must be aware that any differences between average pay by gender of 25% or more shall be justified. Failure to establish an equality plan can result in significant financial penalties for the employer.⁴⁵ An Equality Plan aims to achieve equality between women and men in the workplace. For this purpose, the law stipulates that in every plan the company must ensure that this equality is attained in various areas:

Selection and recruitment process; Job classification; Training; Career advancement; Working conditions, including an equal pay audit; Co-responsible exercise of the rights to a personal, family and work life; Under-representation of

⁴⁵ Gender Equality Plans in Spain (2020), Available at: <https://avantges.com/gender-equality-plans-in-spain/>

women; Remuneration and Prevention of sexual and gender-based harassment.⁴⁶

In the sphere of the **Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands**, the recent modification of the Statute of Autonomy of the Canary Islands, approved by Organic Law 1/2018 of 5 November, introduces for the first time the equality rights between women and men, embedded as a guiding principle in Article 17. The principle of equality between women and men and non-discrimination is guaranteed, favouring the participation of women in public life under conditions of equality, which was not part of the consolidated text of the 1982 Statute of Autonomy. New articles related to equality between women and men are incorporated, such as Article 11. Right to equality and co-operation, and Article 17. Right for gender equality.

Two important laws have been passed with the main objectives of promoting equality between women and men and protection against gender-based violence: Law 1/2010, of 26 February, of the Canary Islands on equality between women and men, and Law 16/2003, of 8 April, on the Prevention and Comprehensive Protection of Women against Gender Violence, amended by Law 1/2017, of 17 March, which incorporates into the regional regulations the provisions set out in the Istanbul Convention and the resolutions of international bodies. This way, it aims to extend the scope of application to all forms of violence against women. Furthermore, the Resolution of 27 June 2017 should be considered, as it includes the agreement establishing the guidelines on how to prepare and basic content to include in gender impact reports in draft laws, regulatory provisions and plans approved by the Government of the Canary Islands.

In **Poland**, the gender equality principle is enshrined in the Constitution adopted in 1997, which states that (article 33) "the male and female have an equal right to education, employment and promotions, to equal remuneration for work of equal value, to social security and to occupy positions, perform functions and obtain public dignity and decorations".⁴⁷ In addition, Poland has ratified most of the international legal acts supporting equality, including the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), as well as the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action. Ratified international agreements constitute a particularly important source of the legal framework of equality policy in Poland, as they are listed as sources of universally-binding legislation in the Polish constitution (Article 87).

Accession to the EU has contributed to a general improvement of the legal framework for equality, including significant changes in the labour code introduced in compliance with European principles. Both the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union are supreme over national law. In 2010 the Polish parliament adopted The Act on the Implementation of Certain Provisions of the European Union in the Field of Equal Treatment. The Act implements several EU directives, including the Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the

⁴⁶ Equality Plan in Spain: Everything you need to know; Available at: <https://rosclar.com/equality-plan-in-spain-everything-you-need-to-know/>
⁴⁷ EIGE, "Gender Equality in Academia and Research. National backgrounds: Poland", 2020. Retrieved from: https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/countries/poland?fbclid=IwAR0vvMOjoT2FJpha_EnTQN_BBkKkKcKXkR-nUFj0E0jCzvGfySd6L6Xbmo [01.05.2021]

implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation; and Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation. The Act sets general framework conditions for equal treatment policy in Poland and it specifies the competent bodies in equal-treatment issues, that is, the Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment and the Commissioner for Human Rights.

In **Portugal** Gender equality is inscribed in the Portuguese legal system as a fundamental principle, since the last Constitution of the Portuguese Republic of 1976, through Article 13 et follows, establishes that (1.) all citizens have the same social dignity and are equal before the law and (2.) no one can be privileged, benefited, discriminated, deprived of any right or exempt from any duty on grounds of ancestry, sex, race, language, territory of origin, religion, political or ideological convictions, education, economic situation, social condition or sexual orientation. Portugal is a State Party to the main binding international instruments in these matters, and the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) and the Council of Europe Convention on the Prevention and Combating of Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (Istanbul Convention) are the main examples. Portugal has also made a commitment, in particular in the framework of the United Nations, the Council of Europe, the European Union (EU) and the Community of Portuguese-speaking Countries (CPLP), to other numerous political commitments in these areas, including the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action and commitment documents arising from its revisions, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the European Pact for Gender Equality 2011-2020 and the Strategic Commitment for Gender Equality 2016-2019, the 2010 Strategic Plan for Gender Equality and Empowerment Cooperation (CPLP) and the 2010 Strategic Plan for Gender Equality and Empowerment of Women (CPLP - 2017-2020), and recommendation CM/Rec(2010)5 of the Committee of Ministers to The Member States of the Council of Europe on measures to combat discrimination on grounds of sexual orientation or gender identity.

Since January 2018, in Portugal it must be respected the balanced representation of WM in management and supervisory bodies in public sector corporate administrations and listed companies. Parity is established by a minimum representation of 33.3% women in the management bodies of state business sector and 20% in listed companies. Law 26/2019 approved the regime of balanced representation between WM in management of State direct and indirect administration bodies, public higher education institutions and public associations, such as professional associations. The appointment of such office holders and bodies shall be subject to a minimum threshold of 40% balanced representation between WM. Regarding senior management posts subject to the scrutiny of a Public Administration Recruitment and Selection Committee, the 40% parity is taken in the composition of the candidates list.

Additionally, Law 60/2018, of August 21, creates mechanisms to promote equal pay between women and men for equal work and work of equal value. This law creates a duty for companies to have transparent pay policies based on the

application of gender-neutral job evaluations; improves national data on gender pay gap; strengthens the role of Labour Inspectorate (through a specific mechanism to notify companies to produce a plan to evaluate pay disparities and correct those amounting to discrimination) and the Commission for Equality in Labour and Employment (which now has the power to issue binding opinions on situations of potential pay discrimination).

The Portuguese Autonomous Regions of the Azores and Madeira have legal and political autonomy in this area and develop their own public policies through their own institutions and instruments. In the case of the Azores Archipelago⁴⁸ this work was carried out in the Regional Plan for The Prevention and combating Domestic Violence (2010-2012), followed by the II Regional Plan for the Prevention and Combat of Domestic and Gender Violence (2014-2018), proposed and accompanied by the Regional Directorate of Social Solidarity (DRSS), following the implementation of the III Regional Plan for the Prevention and Combat of Domestic Violence 2019-2022.

In the context of equal opportunities and the fight against domestic and gender violence, the former Regional Secretariat for Social Solidarity and now the Vice-Presidency of the Regional Government of the Azores have promoted through the DRSS a number of projects: the creation of 5 Local Poles for the Prevention and Combating of Domestic Violence (2010 and 2011); the establishment of the Socio-Economic Support Fund for Victims of Domestic Violence (2011); creation of the Information and Monitoring System of the Phenomenon of Domestic Violence in the RAA (2011); the creation of the Regional Line Against Domestic Violence (2015); the focus on the training and qualification of professionals and the focus on continuous monitoring of the reality of domestic and gender violence and dating violence, also using in-depth studies.⁴⁹

All these projects were accompanied by the existing response structures in the Region, funded by the Azores Social Security Institute, such as Casas Abrigo, Reception Center, multidisciplinary technical teams and vocational training.

The Government of the Azores has been working together with institutions, key partners in the prevention of discrimination and violence, in the protection and support of victims, as well as in the implementation of innovative programmes for the rehabilitation of aggressors and prevention of victimisation of victims' children.⁵⁰

The **Slovakian** Constitution Act No. 460/1992 Coll. declares that the Slovak Republic is a sovereign, democratic and legal state. It is not tied to any ideology or religion. The Constitution sets out equality between human beings in dignity and rights and prohibits discrimination on the ground of sex (Article 12). The act does not follow only the gender aspect in the principle of equality but follows the intersectional approach guarantying the fundamental rights and freedoms to everyone regardless of sex, race, the colour of skin, language, faith and religion,

⁴⁸ Please check: <https://portal.azores.gov.pt/>.

⁴⁹ The study "Discrimination and Violence: Results of the survey of young secondary and vocational students from the Autonomous Region of the Azores" is highlighted by the study "Discrimination and Violence: Results of the survey of young secondary and professional students from the Autonomous Region of the Azores", authored by Novo Dia - Association for Social Inclusion, 2019.

⁵⁰ Noteworthy is the Contigo Program started in 2008, resulting from the pioneering project of the Regional Directorate of Social Solidarity and The Institute of Social Security of the Azores, in conjunction with the Public Prosecutor's Office, PSP, General Directorate of Reintegration and Prison Services and Center for Family Therapy and Systemic Intervention. Subsequently, this project was disseminated and implemented at the national level.

etc. The Constitution also recognises the special treatment and protection of women, people with health disabilities and person's underage.⁵¹ However, the Preamble of the Constitution appeals, among other general principles, also to the Cyril-Method spiritual, i.e. Christian heritage, thus opening space to broad conservative support.

The most significant step reaching the goal of the equality principle was the establishment the Act no. 365/2004 Coll. on Equal Treatment in Certain Areas and Protection against Discrimination (the Antidiscrimination Act). This act transfers international anti-discriminatory EU directives into the Slovak legal system. According to the act, the anti-discriminatory principle is defined as the duty not to discriminate and prevent discrimination.⁵² Hence, the CEDAW Committee admonished the Slovak Republic that the definition is not consistent with the principle of substantive gender equality of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, multiple discrimination is missing, and the women's access to justice is limited.⁵³

A relevant principle to remedy the historically and politically rooted sex/gender disadvantages is Article 8a of the Anti-Discrimination Act that allows the adoption of **temporary balancing measures** (positive affirmative action). The temporary balancing measures can be adopted and applied in all public administration bodies and legal entities.⁵⁴ So far, positive affirmative actions have been adopted in complex state programs to support specific regions and vulnerable groups, e.g. Roma and other minorities. A good example is a demand-led call to help family and working life reconciliation to balance gender inequalities in employment. The project targeted the less developed regions and inclusion of the mothers with young children (also with special educational needs) on the labour market by promotion of flexible jobs, especially after returning from parental leave.⁵⁵ **The CEDAW Committee recommends adopting temporary special measures in more areas**, e. g, to promote non-traditional educational choices of women and girls in mathematics, science, and technology and accelerate women's appointment to the highest positions in academic institutions⁵⁶.

The equal treatment and prohibition of discrimination are also mirrored in **Act no. 311/2001 Coll. Labour Code**. The regulation sets, among others, the rules on working time, flexible working conditions and fair remuneration. The Labour Code also defines the right for **maternal or parental leave for mothers and fathers**. Firstly, women have a right to use a maternal leave from work which lasts 34 weeks (37 weeks for single women). After that, women can continue to take full custody of a child (or children) for up to 3 years in the form of parental leave (If a parent takes care of a child with health problems, the parental leave can be extended). Men can also use maternal and parental leave; both leaves can be used by both parents. Every employer must require the same working position for the women and men returning from parental leave. Not all parents gain the eligibility of the leave and benefits due to short time being socially insured. In

⁵¹ Lamačková, D.; Becková, D. (2009). Právne východiská arámce pre politiku rodovej rovnosti v akademickom prostredí a na univerzite. In Jesenková, A. (Ed.) Rodová rovnosť na univerzite – kontexty a perspektívy. Recenzovaný zborník vedeckých prác. <https://unibook.upjs.sk/img/cms/2019/FF/rodova-rovnost-na-univerzite-web.pdf>

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ CEDAW/C/SVK/CO/5-6 - E - CEDAW/C/SVK/CO/5-6 -Desktop (undocs.org)

⁵⁴ <https://www.equalitylaw.eu/downloads/5303-slovakia-country-report-gender-equality-2020-pdf-1-37-mb>

⁵⁵ http://www.snsip.sk/wp-content/uploads/DVO_2018.pdf

⁵⁶ CEDAW/C/SVK/CO/5-6 - E - CEDAW/C/SVK/CO/5-6 -Desktop (undocs.org)

2016, 26% of women and 12% of men aged 20-49 (potential parents) were not eligible for maternity / parental allowance in Slovakia.⁵⁷

Social security during childcare is protected in several acts. **Act no. 461/2003 Coll. Social Insurance Act** defines the condition of the maternal benefit. The maternal benefit calculation is about 75% of the gross income. It is conditioned by the paid sickness insurance for 270 days within the last two years (covered by an employer in the labour costs). These conditions are problematic for doctoral students who receive a scholarship, which does not cover the sickness insurance. Doctoral students have a right to the Parental benefit. The Parental benefit is about 275,90€/month (for those who did not meet the criteria with the paid sickness insurance for at 270 days within last two years) or 378,10 € (for those who met the criteria). Parents can also ask for a child allowance which is about 25,50€/month. This benefit can be reached by one parent for one child up to 3 years old. The amount of the allowance is in comparison to average monthly wage very low and caused a considerable decrease in family income and impacts women's future pension claims.

The Social Insurance Act in Slovakia has recently brought two new benefits – **Pregnancy benefit and Pregnancy scholarship**. Pregnancy benefit is given to pregnant women (from the 13th pregnancy week until the delivery) and is about 200€/per month minimum (calculation is made from the gross income). It is conditioned by the paid sickness insurance for at 270 days within the last two years, which excluded students. In this case, adult students (both high school and university students) have a right to the Pregnancy scholarship, which is 200€/month (from the 13th pregnancy week until the delivery). This scholarship is defined by the Higher Education Act and by the School Act. After the delivery, women who were students can ask for the Parental benefit. The benefits for parents are more significant for those who had been working before the maternal or parental leave. Before 2021, all students had to rely only on the Parental benefit, which is relatively low, mainly because students did not meet the criteria on the paid sickness insurance tied to the working contract. Putting it into the GE in a research context, even with the new Pregnancy scholarship, this situation leaves many PhD students (mostly female) in a very precarious position.

In terms of work-life balance policies, the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic recently supported the **establishment of the kindergartens at HEIs**. The purposes are to make the academic environment more attractive and expand the capacities of the public pre-primary facilities. The subsidies out of the total 1 million EUR allocation were provided to 5 universities so far.⁵⁸ In general, there have been around 11 000 rejected applications for placement of a child in a pre-school facility in Slovakia in 2020.⁵⁹

The current legislation and regulations do not fully protect women from disadvantages in Slovakia. Moreover, the **enforcement of anti-discrimination and equal treatment principles is limited** in Slovakia. This is due to unclear

⁵⁷ MPSVR SR, 2021, Responses of the Slovak Republic to CEDAW, CEDAW/C/SVK/QPR/7

⁵⁸ B. Gröhling: Materské školy v priestoroch vysokých škôl pomáhajú zvyšovať dostupnosť vzdelávania | Ministerstvo školstva, vedy, výskumu a športu Slovenskej republiky (minedu.sk)

⁵⁹ Spúšťa sa povinná škôlka, miesta riešia na poslednú chvíľu - SME

definitions, lack of relevant data and information to prove the unequal treatment, and limited competencies of Slovak courts to apply the related legislation.⁶⁰

The **Romanian** Constitution provides for equality and non-discrimination in broad terms. From a legislative point of view, in Romania, equality among all citizens is guaranteed by the Constitution, Art. 4 (2): '*Romania is the common and indivisible homeland of all its citizens, without any discrimination on account of race, nationality, ethnic origin, language, religion, sex, opinion, political adherence, property or social origin*', and Art. 16 (1): '*Citizens are equal before the law and public authorities, without privileges and discriminations.*'⁶¹

The area of gender equality is mainly framed in Romania by Law 202/2002⁶². The Law contains provisions concerning the promotion and implementation of gender equality principles and the elimination of all forms of gender discrimination in all public and private social spheres of activity. The law also has the role of juridical harmonization of the national legislation with the existing international and mandatory European regulations in the area of gender.

The main legislation transposing and implementing the EU's gender equality directives consists of:

- Law no. 202/2002 on equal opportunities and equal treatment for men and women, amended by Government Ordinance No. 84/2004, Law No. 501/2004, Law No. 340/2006, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 56/2006, Law No. 340/2006, Law No. 507/2006, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 68/2010, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 83/2012, Law No. 115/2013, Law No. 229/2015, Law No. 178/2018, Law No. 232/2018 (implementing Article 157 TFEU and Recast Directive 2006/54/EC);
- Government Ordinance No. 137/2000 regarding the prevention and sanctioning of all forms of discrimination⁶³, amended by Law No. 48/2002, Government Ordinance No. 77/2003, Law No. 27/2004, Law No. 324/2006, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 75/2008, Law No. 61/2013, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 19/2013, Law No. 189/2013, Law No. 153/2017 (general multi-ground antidiscrimination law, implementing the Racial Equality Directive (Directive 2000/43/EC) and the Equality Framework Directive (Directive 2000/78/EC));
- Government Emergency Ordinance No. 96/2003 regarding the protection of maternity at the workplace⁶⁴, amended by Law No. 25/2004, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 158/2005, Law No. 154/2015 (implementing Directive 92/85/EEC and relevant provisions of Directive 2006/54/EC regarding pregnancy);
- Government Emergency Ordinance No. 61/2003 regarding the implementation of the principle of equal treatment between women and men

⁶⁰ 2020_SK-GE country report ready for web (equality/law.eu)

⁶¹ "Constituția României", The Constitution of Romania, 29 October 2003 [Revised]. Available at <http://www.cdep.ro/pls/dic/site.page?id=371> (in English at <https://www.presidency.ro/en/the-constitution-of-romania>)

⁶² Romanian Parliament, "Legea nr. 202/2002 privind egalitatea de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați" ("Law no. 202/2000 on equal opportunities and equal treatment for women and men"), 7 June 2002 (Amended 10 August 2020). Available at <https://lege5.ro/Gratuit/geytinjsy/legea-nr-202-2002-privind-egalitatea-de-sanse-si-de-tratament-intre-femei-si-barbati>

⁶³ Romanian Government, "Ordonanța nr. 137/2000 privind prevenirea și sancționarea tuturor formelor de discriminare" ("Government Ordinance no. 137/2000 regarding the prevention and sanctioning of all forms of discrimination"), 31 August 2000, (137/2000). Available at <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocument/24129>

⁶⁴ Romanian Government, "Ordonanța de Urgență nr. 96/2003 privind protecția maternității la locurile de muncă" ("Government Emergency Ordinance no. 96/2003 regarding the protection of maternity at the workplace"), 27 October 2003, (96/2003). Available at <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocument/47216>

with respect to access to goods and the provision of services⁶⁵, amended by Law No. 62 of 1.4.2009, Law No. 128 of 26.4.2013 (implementing Directive 2004/113/EC);

- Government Emergency Ordinance No. 111 of 8.12.2010 on the leave and monthly allowance for child rearing⁶⁶, amended by Law No. 132 of 27.6.2011, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 124 of 27.12.2011, Law No. 166 of 9.10.2012, Law No. 187 of 24.10.2012, Law No. 126 of 23.9.2014, Law No. 66 of 19.4.2016, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 82 of 16.11.2016, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 6 of 18.1.2017, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 82 of 8.11.2017, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 15 of 7.3.2018, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 81 of 13.9.2018, Law No. 89 of 2.5.2019 (implementing Directive 2010/18/EU⁶⁷).

The Law, as mentioned above, has been amended several times to reflect better European and global contexts in the area of gender equality. The 2015 amendment introduced **definitions of sex and gender** ('sex' is understood as the combination of biological and physiological features that define women and men; 'gender' is understood as the combination of roles, behaviours, features and activities that society considers to be appropriate for women and men, respectively). The Government Ordinance No. 137/2000 regarding the prevention and sanctioning of all forms of discrimination provided the legal framework for dealing with **multiple discrimination**, stipulating that '*Any distinction, exclusion, restriction or preference based on two or more of the criteria foreseen in para. 1 shall constitute an aggravating circumstance in establishing the contravention responsibility, unless one or more of its components is not subject to criminal law.*'⁶⁸

The amendment contained in *Law no. 178/2018* introduced the **definition of gender violence** (in conformity with the Istanbul Convention) and regulated, for the first time, **the profession of equal opportunity expert and equal opportunity specialist**. The new amendment also created the possibility, although not the obligation, of public and private employers with more than 50 employees to assign the competences mentioned above to an employee or to **hire an expert and/or a specialist in equal opportunities/chances** (the specialist is officially called "technician" in Romanian- quite an uninspired choice). Consequently, these occupations are now officially recognized and included in the Occupation Classifications in Romania (positions 242230, respectively 341207)⁶⁹. *Law no. 232/2018* for the modification and completion of Law 202/2002 introduced, for the first time, concrete clarifications and sanctions for

⁶⁵ Romanian Government, "Ordonanța de Urgență nr. 61/2008 privind implementarea principiului egalității de tratament între femei și bărbați în ceea ce privește accesul la bunuri și servicii și furnizarea de bunuri și servicii" ("Government Emergency Ordinance no. 61/2008 regarding the implementation of the principle of equal treatment between women and men with respect to access to goods and the provision of services"), 14 May 2008, (61/2008). Available at <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocument/93183>

⁶⁶ Romanian Government, "Ordonanța de Urgență nr. 111 din 8 decembrie 2010 privind concediul și indemnizația lunară pentru creșterea copiilor" ("Government Emergency Ordinance no. 111 of 8 December 2010 on the leave and monthly allowance for child rearing"), 8 December 2010, (111/2010). Available at <http://www.mmuncii.ro/j33/images/Documente/Legislatie/2016/OUGnr111din2010.pdf>

⁶⁷ Official Journal of the European Union, "Directive 2010/18/EU implementing the revised Framework Agreement on parental leave concluded by BUSINESSEUROPE, UEAPME, CEEP and ETUC and repealing Directive 96/34/EU", 2010 (2010/18/EU).

⁶⁸ Romanian Parliament, "Legea nr. 324 din 14 iulie 2006 pentru modificarea și completarea Ordonanței Guvernului nr. 137/2000 privind prevenirea și sancționarea tuturor formelor de discriminare" ("Law no. 324/2006 for the amendment of Government Ordinance no. 137/2000 regarding the prevention and sanctioning of all forms of discrimination, 14 July 2006. Available at <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocument/Afis/73606>

⁶⁹ Ministry of Labour and Social Protection (Justice), "Lista ocupațiilor din COR în ordinea crescătoare a codurilor" (List of COR occupations in ascending order"), Republished 2021. Available at: <http://www.mmuncii.ro/j33/index.php/ro/2014-domenii/munca/c-o-r>

any form of harassment, **sexual harassment** or psychological harassment behaviours in public or private spaces^{70,71}

In Slovenia, the enforcement of equality between women and men is guided by two main acts and governmental resolution:

Equal Opportunities for Women and Men Act (Zakon o enakih možnostih žensk in moških) (Uradni list RS, št. 59/02, 61/07 – ZUNEO-A, 33/16 – ZVarD in 59/19)

The Act defines general and special measures for the creation of equal opportunities determines the holders of tasks, their competencies and obligations, introduces special informal treatment of cases of alleged unequal treatment of the sexes and the advocate of equal opportunities as an authorized person and the obligations of the entities involved in these cases. Ministries responsible for education and work and other responsibilities in the field of education and vocational training shall ensure equal treatment of the sexes, in particular in the preparation, adoption and implementation of publicly valid education or vocational training programs, in the validation of textbooks and teaching materials, and in the introduction of organizational innovations and changes in pedagogical or andragogical methods, and each within its competences to establish an appropriate system of measures to eliminate the identified forms of unequal treatment of the sexes. An unbalanced representation of the sexes in the sense of the previous paragraph is defined with the representation of one sex in an individual area of social life or its part lower than 40%.

Protection against discrimination Act (Zakon o varstvu pred diskriminacijo (ZVarD)

(Uradni list: 33/2016, 21/2018-ZNOrg); Active since: 23. 5. 2016⁷²

This law provides for the protection of every individual (hereinafter: individual) against discrimination regardless of gender, nationality, race or ethnic origin, language, religion or belief, disability, age, sexual orientation, sexual identity and sexual expression, social status, financial status, education or any other personal circumstance (hereinafter: personal circumstance) in various areas of social life, in the exercise of human rights and fundamental freedoms, in the exercise of rights and obligations and in other legal relations in political, economic, social, cultural, civil or other field. It ensures protection against discrimination or equal treatment of all persons, in particular as regards: a) conditions for access to employment, self-employment and occupation, including selection criteria and conditions of employment, regardless of the type of activity and at all levels of the occupational hierarchy, including promotion; b) access to all forms and to all levels of career guidance and counselling, vocational and technical education and training, further vocational training and retraining, including work placements; c) employment and working conditions, including termination of the employment contract and wages; d) membership of and involvement in an organization of

⁷⁰ Romanian Parliament, "Legea nr. 232 din 2 august 2018 pentru modificarea și completarea Legii nr. 202/2002 privind egalitatea de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați" ("Law no. 232 of 2 August 2018 for the amendment of Law no. 202/2002 regarding equal opportunities and equal treatment for women and men"), Published 6 August 2018. Available at http://irdo.ro/pdf/drepturi_femei/13Legea%20232%202018.pdf

⁷¹ For further legislation in Romania, see the annex 1.

⁷² Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, "Zakon o varstvu pred diskriminacijo" (ZVarD), ("Protection against discrimination Act") (Uradni list: 33/2016, 21/2018-ZNOrg); Active since: 23. 5. 2016; (In Slovenian: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO7273>); (In English: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/cm?idStrani=prevodi>).

workers or employers or in any organization whose members pursue a particular profession, including the benefits provided by such organizations; e) social protection, including social security and health care; f) social benefits; g) education; h) access to and supply of goods and services available to the public, including housing.

Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2015–2020 (Resolucija o nacionalnem programu za enake možnosti žensk in moških 2015–2020 (ReNPEMŽM15–2) (Uradni list RS, št. 84/15))⁷³

The new national program sets out general priority areas for improving the situation of women and men and ensuring the sustainable development of gender equality in the Republic of Slovenia, and identifies key challenges and problems for the period 2015–2020. It builds on the experience of the previous document and builds on the findings of the Evaluation of the Implementation of the Resolution on the National Program for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men (2005-2013) on how the implementation of measures and activities achieved the objectives set out in the National Program 2005-2013, and what were the results and effects of these processes. The new national program focuses on eight priority areas: equal economic independence, reconciling work and private and family life, a knowledge society free of gender stereotypes, social inclusion, health, balanced representation of women and men, violence against women and gender equality in foreign policy; international development cooperation. The key objectives are: a) the elimination of gender imbalances and gender segregation in employment and the elimination of unemployment; b) improving the position of women and men in the field of social inclusion; c) the removal of obstacles to the easier reconciliation of work and family and private life; d) closing the gender gap and gender segregation in education; e) eliminating inequalities in science and higher education; f) the elimination of stereotypes in society, especially in the media, culture and sport; g) improving the health of women and men; h) removing obstacles to the achievement of a balanced representation of women and men in the various fields of political and social life; i) zero tolerance for violence against women; j) strengthening the integration of the gender perspective in Slovenian development, peace and other foreign policy initiatives.

In Italy, with respect to the need for equal pay, currently Italy does not have any law that guarantees equal treatment between men and women. This means that no law obliges the employer to pay workers who perform the same duties within the same company in the same way but, by law, only the minimum wage provided for by the national collective bargaining agreement must be respected.

The 2021 Italian budget law established, at the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies, the Fund for the support of gender salary equality, with an endowment of 2 million euros per year starting from 2022, for interventions aimed at supporting and recognition of the social and economic value of gender pay equality and equal opportunities in the workplace.

⁷³ Government of Republic Slovenia, "Resolucija o nacionalnem programu za enake možnosti žensk in moških 2015–2020", ("Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2015–2020"), (2015), (ReNPEMŽM15–2) (Uradni list RS, št. 84/15), <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=RESO108>

Measures to reconcile professional life and family life are included in the numerous rules governing the labour market, and funds have been allocated to promote further working typologies more compatible with family care and to create an appropriate social infrastructure. The Budget Law (L. 205/2017 art 1, paragraph 218), which introduced two further paragraphs to art. 26 of Legislative Decree. 198/2006 (entitled “Harassment and sexual harassment” of the Code of equal opportunities between men and women), recognises broader protections for female workers and for male workers who report discrimination owing to harassment or sexual harassment. Family Law recognises a perfect equality between men and women and confers the same rights to children born in and out of marriage.

Italy has a good law for maternity and paternity. The rules governing leave and leave for the protection of maternity and paternity are contained in Legislative Decree no. 151 of 26 March 2001 and its modifications. The law establishes a period of five months of compulsory maternity leave and ten days of mandatory paternity leave.

The law (Legislative Decree no. 151/2001) and its amendments provide for an optional period of absence from work for parents due to their child's birth. This period can be added to the compulsory maternity leave due for 5 months and the ten days of paternity leave. Indeed, the worker is allowed to take time off from work, after this period, for another six months, within the first year of the child's life, during which the job must be kept (Article 7, paragraph 1 of Legislative Decree no. 151/2001) [5], in addition to the period of illness of the child under the age of three, upon presentation of a medical certificate (art. 7, co. 2 of Legislative Decree no. 151/2001).

However, the care of children in the first years of their life is mainly in charge of mothers. In 2015 the paternity leave in Italy was only one day, subsequently increased to 10 days in article 1, paragraph 363 of the law 30 December 2020, n. 178 (budget law 2021)

2.2. National bodies

Gender equality is dominantly the agenda of a ministry of labour and social affairs in the seven partners' countries. The agenda is represented by a selected unit (department, Plenipotentiary) or commissions that may have cross-sectional impact. Some countries face a decreasing power and influence of the institutional infrastructure of GE promotion (Slovakia, Poland, Romania). On the other hand, Canary Islands may be promoted as an example of working state machinery with the Canary Islands Institute for Equality (ICI), created by the Law 1/1994 of 13 January 1994, a consultative and advisory body. Its comments must be taken into consideration in the procedures for creating provisions by the Government of the Canary Islands.

As GE is a cross-sectional issue, it remains a challenge to effectively reflect on different fields and levels. From the countries' comparison, it seems that when there is a cross-sectional competent body it may help to promote the issue. On the other hand, limiting GE as an issue of a family policy or equal opportunities

under a ministry of labour and social issues, the reflection of gender in research (and other relevant fields, e.g. gender budgeting) remains a challenge. Another significant challenge within all the countries is GE monitoring and evaluation. This also applies to countries with strong GE policy backgrounds (e.g. Spain, Portugal).

Even though the Commissioners for Human Rights (Ombuds-persons) are also strong bodies for promoting GE within the countries, their interventions and impacts on GE in research and HEIs remain unknown. Moreover, with ongoing gender backlashes in some countries, his/her position may be questioned. This is strongly visible in Slovakia - her annual reports on findings concerning the respect of public authorities for the fundamental rights and freedoms have been met with resistance from the side of the conservative parliament, objecting to low support for traditional family and protection of freedom of religious expression.

In some of the countries, the national and regional gender equality bodies are well-established operational mechanisms.

For example, in **Italy**, in 1997, the Department for Equal Opportunities was established at the Presidency of the Council. It was created as a support structure for the activity of the Minister and with the task of promoting and coordinating equality policies, it has progressively expanded its competencies also in the field of the fight against racial discrimination and other forms of discrimination. The functions of the Department concern, in particular, the promotion and coordination of the policies of personal rights, equal opportunities, equal treatment and the removal of all forms and causes of discrimination, prevention and contrast of sexual and gender-based violence, persecutory acts, trafficking and exploitation of human beings, as well as female genital mutilation and other harmful practices.

For the promotion of equal opportunities in the world of work at the Ministry of Labour, the National Committee for the implementation of the principles of equal treatment and equal opportunities for workers (National Equality Committee) has been operating since 1991, an advisory body of the Minister with duties of study and promotion in the field of equality in the sector of vocational training and work (Article 8, Legislative Decree No. 198/2006, as amended by Legislative Decree No. 151 of 2015).

In the Italian landscape, the establishment of the National Equality Councillor for the promotion and control of the implementation of the principles of equality of opportunity and non-discrimination between men and women in the world of work was relevant. Similar Equality Councillors were established at the regional level, metropolitan cities and large-area entities.

According to the **Bulgarian** Ombudsman Act (Promulgated, SG No. 48/2003), the National Ombudsman and his deputy are responsible for investigating violations of civil rights and freedoms by state or municipal bodies and their administration, including party providing public services.

Bulgaria is a party to the implementation of a number of international conventions (UN, ILO, etc.), as well as international human rights law. In the field of gender equality, the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action on Women's Rights, adopted at the Fourth United Nations Conference on Women (1995), and the Convention are the most important determinants of the future strategic policy framework in this area, to eliminate all forms of discrimination against women. An important aspect of the implementation of the country's international commitments in the field of gender equality is the reporting on the implementation of international legal acts to which the Republic of Bulgaria is a part.

Within the United Nations framework, Bulgaria actively cooperates with the UN-Women - a UN structure to achieve gender equality and empower women. Our country's commitments and achievements in gender equality are presented annually to the international community during the Commission on the Status of Women - the main intergovernmental body at the global level dedicated entirely to promoting equality and women's empowerment.

The need to give formal coverage to gender equality policies in **Spain** has been approached from a double perspective. The first refers to the legislation and legal regulations that develop them. The second refers to a whole administrative structure whose central axis is the promotion and encouragement of equality of both sexes, as well as the facilitation of the conditions for the effective participation of women in political, cultural, economic, and social life.

Within the scope of the General State Administration as well as in the Ministry of Health, Social Affairs and Equality, the State Secretariat for Social Services and Equality, they are included the Government Delegation for Gender Violence and the Institute for Women and Equal Opportunities (IMIO). The purpose of the latter, as an autonomous body, is to promote and foster the conditions that make social equality of both sexes possible, as well as the participation of women in political, cultural, economic, and social life. Within its duties, it is included the prevention and elimination of all kinds of discrimination against people on the grounds of birth, sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion, ideology, orientation, sexual identity, age, disability or any other personal or social condition or circumstance. Its activity is mainly carried out through the signing of collaboration agreements with other public and private organisations and institutions in the cultural, educational, sporting, economic and social spheres. In addition, the Women's Institute for Equal Opportunities, through public calls for grants and subsidies, finances activities and projects aimed at promoting equal opportunities between women and men, especially research on gender and the knowledge and dissemination of the situation of women.

Since 2010, the **Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands** has had the Canary Islands Institute for Equality (ICI), created by the Law 1/1994 of 13 January 1994, whose predecessor was the Canary Islands Institute for Women. The Canary Islands Government's involvement in the defence and promotion of the real equality of women and men has given the ICI a wide range of functions and competencies that go far beyond the mere coordination of actions, the carrying out of activities, advice or the promotion and encouragement of

measures aimed at achieving equality policies. In this sense, the ICI's actions, functions, and competencies include the monitoring of current legislation and its application, as well as the drafting of proposals for legislative reform aimed at eliminating obstacles that hinder or prevent real and effective equality between the sexes. As a consultative and advisory body, it must be taken into consideration and it has the capacity to make proposals in the procedures for drafting general provisions promoted by the Government of the Canary Islands. Finally, its power to draw up protocols for the prevention and protection of victims of sexual harassment and harassment on the grounds of sex cannot be overlooked.

In **Poland**, the Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment (*Pełnomocnik Rządu ds Równego Traktowania*), appointed and dismissed by the Prime Minister of the Republic of Poland, until the end of 2005, constituted the main national institution responsible for gender equality. The Plenipotentiary was tasked with: the government's ET policy (ET – equal treatment with respect to gender, race, ethnicity, nationality, religion, faith, worldview, disability, age or sexual orientation); comments on ET legislation; analysis of the legal framework from the perspective of ET; acting on unequal treatment; analysis and evaluation of the legal and social situation in ET and coordinating tasks to achieve ET/preventing discrimination; monitoring compliance with the principle of ET; promoting ET issues; and cooperating with NGOs, including trade unions and employers.

In 2013 the Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment and a network of coordinators in all government departments prepared the National Action Programme (NAP) for Equal Treatment 2013-2016 (adopted by the Council of Ministers in December 2013).⁷⁴ The NAP for ET was a strategic document that gathers and ranks key equality activities performed by the Government across departments and subsidiary units. It is a coordinated programme of the entire Government and includes tasks on racism, xenophobia, and other dimensions as well as gender. With the change of government in 2015, the marginalisation of the gender equality principle in the Polish legislation and public sphere started.⁷⁵ In January 2016, an additional post of Government Plenipotentiary for Civil Society was established. It was unified with the Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment as the Government Plenipotentiary for Civil Society and Equal Treatment (*Pełnomocnik Rządu ds Społeczeństwa Obywatelskiego i Równego Traktowania*). The significance and influence of the office Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment has decreased considerably ever since. Currently, the Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment has been functioning as a

⁷⁴ The Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment (2013), *Krajowy Program działań na rzecz równego traktowania na lata 2013-2021* (National Action Program for Equal Treatment for 2013-2021). Available at: https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/wp-content/uploads/sites/15/2019/11/Poland_National-Action-Program-for-Equal-Treatment-2013-2016.pdf [01.05.2021]

⁷⁵ The Policy Department for Citizens' Rights and Constitutional Affairs, European Parliament, "The use of EU funds for gender equality in Poland", 2017. Available at: [www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2017/583146/IPOL_IDA\(2017\)583146_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2017/583146/IPOL_IDA(2017)583146_EN.pdf) [20.04.2021]

separate post once more⁷⁶, public consultation continues.⁷⁷ Up to now, the new National Action Programme for Equal Treatment has not been developed.⁷⁸

The second central institution responsible for implementing the equality policy, indicated by the Act on the implementation of some regulations of the European Union in the field of equal treatment suggests, is the Commissioner for Human Rights (the Ombudsperson).⁷⁹ The Commissioner for Human Rights is responsible for the implementation of the principle of equal treatment under the conditions and in the modes set out in the Act of 15 July 1987 on the Commissioner for Human Rights. The Commissioner provides independent assistance to victims of discrimination and publishes reports containing recommendations on the required legal changes. Interventions by the Ombudsperson cover various issues, such as strengthening the electoral rights of women, selected aspects of gender equality in the labour market (e.g. the gender pay gap, recruitment to the police), gender equality in the pre-school curriculum, and violence against women. The Commissioner, implementing the principle of equal treatment, may use a wide range of procedural rights, including the opportunity to demand the initiation of proceedings in civil cases, as well as taking part in any pending court proceedings or applying to the Constitutional Tribunal for examination of the compliance of legal provisions with the Constitution of the Republic of Poland and ratified international agreements.

In **Portugal**, the Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality (CIG) is the national body responsible for promoting and defending gender equality, seeking to respond to the deep social and political changes in this matter. The IEA is part of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, is a service of the direct administration of the State (based in Lisbon and a service unfocused in Porto), under the tutelage of the Secretariat of State for Citizenship and Equality.

The CIG manages several sources of funding, such as the Social Games, the Small Grant, the EEA Grants Portugal and the Operational Program Social Inclusion and Employment, with which projects from civil society, NGOs, Higher Education Entities, among others within the IEC's work area, are supported, in addition to executing its own projects. It currently coordinates more than twenty projects, with a budget of more than three million euros.

The IEC has been designated operator of the Conciliation and Gender Equality Programme, in partnership with Norwegian Equality and Anti-discrimination Ombud (LDO), under the EEA Grants 2014-2021. Through this Program, innovative and structuring projects have been funded for the country, aligned with ENIND, in the following areas: Gender Equality; work-life balance, personal and family life; violence against women and domestic violence; good governance.

At the level of research and higher education, the CIG currently helps to promote projects to support gender balance under this National Strategy, and specifically

⁷⁶ The Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment, Press release. Available at: <https://www.gov.pl/web/rownetraktowanie/anna-schmidt-rodziewicz-nowym-pelnomocnikiem-rzadu-do-spraw-rownego-traktowania> [27.04.2021]

⁷⁷ <https://www.gov.pl/web/rownetraktowanie/konsultacje-publiczne-projektu-krajowego-programu-dzialan-na-rzecz-rownego-traktowania-na-lata-2021-2030> [02.07.2021]

⁷⁸ The Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment (2013), Krajowy Program działań na rzecz równego traktowania na lata 2013-2021 (National Action Program for Equal Treatment for 2013-2021), <https://www.gov.pl/web/rownetraktowanie/krajowy-program-dzialan-na-rzecz-rownego-traktowania>

⁷⁹ EIGE, "Gender Equality in Academia and Research. National backgrounds: Poland", 2020. Retrieved from: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2020> [01.05.2021]

the Ge-HEI project "Gender Equality in Higher Education Institutions", which aims to understand why, in the context of the growing number of female students, teachers and researchers, women are still under-represented in leading research centres and higher education in Portugal.

The two **Portuguese Autonomous Regions of Madeira and the Azores** have their own bodies to design, conduct and evaluate public policies in the area of gender equality.

In the Azores, the Regional Commission for Equality in Labour and Employment (CRITE-A) was created by Regional Legislative Decree No. 3/2011/A. The mission of CRITE-A is to promote equality and non-discrimination between men and women at work, in employment and in vocational training; to protect parenthood (maternity and paternity) and to promote the reconciliation of professional activity with family and private life.

In **Slovakia**, the institutional mechanism targeting gender equality has been challenged for years in Slovakia. The first attempts were initiated in 1991, the newly Government Committee for Women and the Family lasted for two years. In the years 1996 - 2002, there was a Coordinating Committee for Women's Issues in Slovakia, which also struggled with its competencies. In 1999, a department of equal opportunities was established under the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic. Within the year, the agenda was re-created and supplement for anti-discrimination, family policy and gender equality. From 2007 till recently, the department had operated under the name the Department of Gender Equality and Equal Opportunities, until it was renamed to the actual title the **Department of equality between women and men and equal opportunities** due to anti-gender policies in the Ministry. The department is responsible for national policy in gender equality, its creation and monitoring, preparing strategic materials on GE and equal opportunities.

The **Department of Horizontal Principles** performs and ensures tasks related to horizontal principles of equality between men and women and non-discrimination in projects financed from the European Structural and Investment Funds in the Programming Periods, including the upcoming period 2021 – 2027. The goal is to adhere to horizontal principles aimed at eliminating inequalities and promoting equality between women and men and combating discrimination based on sex.

The **Slovak National Center for Human Rights** is a national anti-discrimination body and a national institution for protecting and promoting human rights in Slovakia. The Centre monitors, evaluates and issues expert opinions on compliance with the equal treatment principle and the Anti-Discrimination Act, provides legal assistance (including legal representation) to victims of discrimination, prepares and publishes reports and recommendations on issues related to discrimination, and carries out training and awareness-raising activities. The Centre is responsible for providing assistance to the victims of discrimination on all grounds covered by the Anti-discrimination Act, including sex/gender.⁸⁰

⁸⁰ Gender Mainstreaming Approach - Slovakia (europa.eu)

Another independent gatekeeper is **the Public Defender of Rights (Ombudsperson)**. The Ombudsperson participate in protecting the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons and legal entities with respect to the activities, decision-making or inactivity of public administration bodies.⁸¹ The current authority of the public defender repeatedly points to protection of women's rights in obstetric care and women's reproductive rights. Her annual reports on findings concerning the respect of public authorities for the fundamental rights and freedoms have been met with resistance from the side of the conservative parliament, objecting to the low support for traditional family and protection of freedom of religious expression.

The **Council of the Government of the Slovak Republic for Human Rights, National Minorities and Gender Equality** operates as an advisory and coordinating body of the Government of the Slovak Republic. There are several committees focused on equality issues within the council. The most relevant is the **Committee on Gender Equality**, which function is to advise and propose measures and review all relevant strategic documents related to gender equality. Although the Committee also consists of representatives of relevant women's and feminist's non-governmental organisations, the body's operational effectiveness is limited.⁸²

In Slovenia, the Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities of Republic Slovenia is responsible for the GE policies and their implementation, monitoring and evaluation.

In Romania, the central Law no. 202/2002 specifies the national institutional frame in the area of implementing gender equality policies in Romania. At the governmental level, the **National Agency for Equal Opportunities for women and men (ANES)** represents the public national official structure that assures promotion of gender equality principles and combating domestic violence⁸³. ANES works under the subordination of the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection and is responsible for: designing and implementation the gender equality national strategy, harmonization of EU regulations in the area with the national ones, representing the Romanian state internal and external in the area. Starting from 2005, in all administrative territorial units of Romania (41 counties and the capital-Bucharest), county commissions in the area of gender equality (called **COJES**) have been created to support ANES's mission. There is also a National Commission in the area of equal opportunities for women and men (called **CONES**) created to sustain ANES activities, mainly with regard to the integration of gender perspectives in all sectorial policies and programs. It is composed of representatives of various ministries and bodies at the level of national administration, including civil society. Other public authorities with attributions and responsibilities in integrating the gender equality principles and promotion of gender equality are as follows: **Ministry of Labour and Social Protection (Justice)**, the **National Institute for Statistics**, the **Social and Economic Council** (special commission), **trade unions**. Special Commissions

⁸¹ www.vop.gov.sk - Public defender of rights : Home

⁸² Výbor pre rodovú rovnosť - MPSVR SR (gov.sk)

⁸³ The National Agency for Equal Opportunities for women and men, "Home". Available at: <https://anes.gov.ro/>

on Equal Opportunities are in place both at the Senate and the Chamber of Deputies of the **Romanian Parliament**. Since 2001, there is also **The National Council for Combating Discrimination**⁸⁴, which guarantees the observance and application of the principle of non-discrimination, in accordance with the domestic legislation in force and with the international documents to which Romania is a party.

A number of specialised **NGOs** are active in monitoring the government initiatives and developing their own gender-sensitive agenda. With the support of such NGOs, several important projects with strong gender-sensitive components, including education, have been developed: *Discrimination in universities* (2015, Romanian Academic Society-SAR, EEA Grants); *Gender Barometer. Romania* (2018, FILIA Centre, EU funds); “*Non-discrimination in Education. An Analysis of the State of Affair from the Perspective of Non-discrimination in many Sectors within the Education Sector in Romania*” (2020, Centre for Juridical Resources, EU-PROGRESS Program). A solid **Coalition for Gender Equality**⁸⁵ has been recently established and, due to its visibility, succeeded in having a representative elected in the Economic and Social Council. At this moment, the Coalition is involved in an extensive project called *EGALIS: Gender Equality through social change and education*, a project supported by SEE and Norwegian Grants 2014-2021 through the Active Citizens Fund in Romania, gendering education being an important component of the project.

From a legal and institutional perspective, Romania might be, at first glance, a case of good practice. Romania signed the CEDAW Convention 35 years ago, and in 2016 (by Law 30/2016) signed the Istanbul Convention. Legislation has improved permanently in the spirit of the EU requirements. There is quite a solid formal institutional infrastructure designed to deal with equal opportunities/gender equality issues. There is also a critical mass of gender experts produced by higher education institutions and professional NGOs and ANES. Notably, the profession of ‘expert in equality of opportunities/chances’ and ‘technician in equality of opportunity/chances’ are occupations officially recognised and included in the Occupation Classifications in Romania. The know-how in the area of gender mainstreaming research projects and/or do gender-focused studies exist. See, for example, the Polirom collection on Gender Studies or the Journal for Gender and Feminist Analysis⁸⁶, to which a lot of Romanian specialists brought their contribution.

2.3. Strategic documents promoting GE in society

All of the joint countries have been implementing strategies on gender equality or equal opportunities in recent years. Poland deals probably with the most serious gender backlash, with the decrease of the influence of the Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment. No new action programme has not been implemented since 2016 (The Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment, 2013). In other countries (Bulgaria, Slovenia), the strategic period for some documents has just finished with no specific answer what are the next steps or

⁸⁴ The National Council for Combating Discrimination, “About CNCD”. Available at: <https://www.cncd.ro/despre-cncd-prezentare-general-a/>

⁸⁵ Coalition for Gender Equality, “Coalition for Gender Equality”. Available at: <https://ongen.ro/>

⁸⁶ Journal of Gender and Feminist Studies, “Analyze Journal”. Available at: www.analyze-journal.ro

plans towards the strategic period. Slovakia has just approved its new strategy. It is worth adding that the Strategy on equality between women and men was also prepared to meet the conditionality to utilise EU structural funds.

Portugal has been implementing public policies for equality for about 20 years, which have been under the guidelines of National Equality Plans and from March 2018 to 2030 by the National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination 2018-2030 – Portugal + Equal (ENIND).⁸⁷ Recognizing Equality and Non-Discrimination as a condition for building a sustainable future for Portugal, the XXI Constitutional Government has defined strategic axes and objectives by 2030. This long-term vision of ENIND is structured in the following three action plans that defined concrete measures and targets for the four-year period until 2021: Action Plan for Equality between Women and Men; Action Plan for the Prevention and Combating of Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence; Action Plan to Combat Discrimination on grounds of Sexual Orientation, Gender Identity and Expression, and Sexual Characteristics. These plans are monitored and evaluated and this information is crucial for the formulation of new multiannual plans.

The Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality (CIG) has been designated operator of the Conciliation and Gender Equality Programme, in partnership with Norwegian Equality and Anti-discrimination Ombud (LDO), under the EEA Grants 2014-2021. Through this Program, innovative and structuring projects have been funded for the country, aligned with ENIND, in the following areas: Gender Equality; work-life balance, personal and family life; violence against women and domestic violence; good governance.

At the level of research and higher education, the IAM currently helps to promote projects to support gender balance under this National Strategy, and specifically the Ge-HEI project "Gender Equality in Higher Education Institutions", which aims to understand why, in the context of the growing number of female students, teachers and researchers, women are still under-represented in leading research centres and higher education in Portugal.⁸⁸

The cooperation between the central administration and the local administration has resulted in the conclusion of Protocols between the IEC and the Municipal Councils. The connection of this theme to local public policies dates back to the 1990s, with an awareness-raising work initiated by the I.C.I. with the Municipalities, which resulted in local-level interventions through Municipal Plans for Equality, coordinated by the Municipal Councils.

The Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) transmitted by the Government to the Parliament on 15 January 2021 to relaunch national development in its draft form identifies three transversal priorities: Gender Equality, Youth and the South. The Plan contains actions favouring gender equality through support for female employment and entrepreneurship, implementing various interventions on social services (such as nursery schools)

⁸⁷ Approved by the XXI Constitutional Government on March 8, 2018, it is published in Diário da República (Resolution of the Council of Ministers No. 61/2018, of May 21). see: <https://dre.pt/application/conteudo/115360036>

⁸⁸ <https://www.eeagrants.gov.pt/pt/programas/conciliacao-e-igualdade-de-genero/projetos/projetos-pre-definidos/pdp2-ge-hei-gender-equality-in-higher-educations-institutions/>

and adequate policies aimed at guaranteeing effective balance between professional and private life. The interventions financed through the Plan also integrate some strategic measures contained in the Family Act (single universal allowance for children, measures on parental leave and working hours, support for families for children's education costs)⁸⁹

Romania has been permanently active in adjusting and transposing through the lens of laws and within major national public strategies, the EU regulations in the area of gender equality. The interest has been partially pragmatical and opportunistic, as funds from the EU depended on these fulfilment criteria. For example, Romania's recent **Government Program for 2020–2024**⁹⁰ stipulates the government's main strategic directions to be followed by each Ministry and makes reference to the area of equal opportunities several times. The Ministry of Work and Social Protection is, for example, accountable in this strategic frame "to develop national policies and programs in accordance with the principle of equal opportunities and treatment between women and men, elder and young people, as well as disabled and vulnerable persons" (p. 151).

Another important strategic document (under public debate at this moment) is the **National Strategy for the Promotion of Equal Opportunities and Treatment for Women and Men and Fighting against Domestic Violence for 2021-2027**⁹¹. It is the first time after 1990 that this type of strategy is based on extensive documentation and data mapping exercise (using internal and external reliable databases, such as EIGE or EUROSTAT), consultations with various actors and, more importantly, on the introduction of gender sensitive instruments for impact assessment and an intersectional approach within its content. The document takes note of the EU Gender Equality Strategy (2020-2025), which clearly mentions that the existence of a national strategic framework on equal opportunities and treatment is necessary for the accession of European funds for the next EU financial years.

The Strategy is also designed to correlate with different EU policies and directives on gender equality, as follows (selection): **Directive 2010/41/EU** of the European Parliament and of the Council of Europe, of July 7th 2010, on the application of the principle of equal treatment between men and women who are self-employed (it also repeals the Directive 86/613/CEE of the Council of Europe); **Directive 2010/18/EU** of the Council, of March 8th 2010, implementing the revised Framework Agreement on parental leave established by BUSINESSEUROPE, UEAPME, CEEP and the ESC (it also repeals the Directive 96/34/EC); **Directive 2006/54/EC** of the European Parliament and of the Council, of July 5th 2006, on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in employment; **Council Directive 2004/113/EC** of December 13th 2004, on the application of the principle of equal treatment between women and men regarding the access and the supply of goods and services; **Council Directive 79/7/EEC** of December 19th 1978, on the gradual application of the

⁸⁹ http://documenti.camera.it/leg18/dossier/pdf/ID0007.pdf?_1620806411298.

⁹⁰ Romanian Government, "Program de Guvernare 2020 – 2024" ("Government Program 2020 – 2024"), 23 December 2020. Available at https://gov.ro/fisiere/pagini_fisiere/Program_de_guvernare_2020_2024.pdf

⁹¹ Ministry of Labour and Social Protection (Justice), "Strategia națională privind promovarea egalității de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați și prevenirea și combaterea violenței domestice pentru perioada 2021-2027" ("National Strategy for the Promotion of Equal Opportunities and Treatment for Women and Men and Fighting against Domestic Violence for 2021-2027"), Published 19 April 2021. Available at http://www.mmuncii.ro/j33/images/Documente/MMPS/Transparenta_decizionala/09032021Anexa_1_SNESVD_cu_ANDPDCA_CNPP_29_01.pdf

principle of equal treatment between men and women in the field of social security.

Overall, the legislative framework on gender equality in Romania is good. There are nevertheless some limitations. Provisions related to equal treatment based on sex/gender **do not apply** within religious denominations and within the private life of individuals; there is a lack of national protection against discrimination for transgender, intersex and non-binary persons; there are no legal regulations in case of surrogacy; no national legislation to recognize unmarried relationships (it recognizes only married spouses in the context of the Directive 2010/41/EU with respect to public pensions and the public health insurance schemes).

The general legal framework in the field of gender equality, including the above-mentioned restrictions, has implications for the gender equality issues within each organization, such as the University of Bucharest.

In **Poland**, there is no system of monitoring of implementation of the in-force anti-discrimination legislation. Gender mainstreaming is practically invisible. Even in specific policies, such as for example, related to domestic violence, the attention to gender is minimum. The collection of gender disaggregated data is not regulated by law, which does not help in creating gender-specific interventions. There is no practice of gender budgeting/auditing.

The primary binding policy documents approved by **the Slovak** government are **the National Strategies for Gender Equality and its Action Plans**. Slovakia recently approved the third Strategy in a row and its action plan (2009 – 2013, 2014 – 2019, 2021 – 2027). Throughout the years, implementing the tasks assigned to different ministries and equality bodies was hampered by a lack of personal and financial resources and low political commitment and anti-gender resistance, resulting in formal fulfilment or even non-performance of the tasks. The latest Strategy and its Action plan (currently in an approval process), prepared already by the conservative administration, is even less ambitious and shifted more on the promotion of motherhood and family support than eliminating the women's disadvantages in society. It is worth adding that the Strategy on equality between women and men was also prepared to meet the conditionality to utilise EU structural funds.

The Slovenian **Periodical Plans for Implementation of the Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men for years 2016-2017⁹² and 2018-2019⁹³** thoroughly address areas of work and measures to be taken accordingly to accomplish gender equality in different public and private spheres. According to this document, gender equality and science/education are currently not balanced and different types of gender inequalities have been recognised. The share of girls in educational programmes and fields of study where they are significantly underrepresented will be

⁹² Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, "Periodical Plan for Implementation of the Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men for years 2016-2017", available at <https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MDDSZ/Dokumenti/Enakost-spolov/12abf7bed8/NPZEMZMPeriodicni20162017.pdf>.

⁹³ Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, "Periodical Plan for Implementation of the Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men for years 2018-2019", available at <https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MDDSZ/Dokumenti/Enakost-spolov/489adce54f/NPZEMZMPeriodicniNact20182019.pdf>.

increased by promoting educational programmes and curricular activities with a special emphasis on encouraging girls to enrol in science and technology studies. Participation of women in science and higher education will be stimulated by adopting policies and strategies to eliminate obstacles for women having academic careers, and supporting programmes and projects that promote women in science. Studies on gender equality will be promoted.

Bulgarian policies on promoting gender equality in the country is guided by the the **Common Strategy for Gender Equality in Bulgaria 2021-27**. The document contains indicators for monitoring the implementation of the Strategy in five priority areas: Increasing women's participation in the labor market and equal degree of economic independence; Reducing the gender pay and income gap; Promoting equality between women and men in decision-making processes; Combating gender-based violence and protecting and supporting victims; Changing the existing gender stereotypes in society in various spheres of public life. Since 2005, the Strategy has been implemented through annual National Action Plans for the Promotion of Equality between Women and Men, which are adopted by the Council of Ministers. The plans contain specific measures within the competences of various institutions and organizations in the priority areas of the Strategy, responsible bodies, financial resources and performance indicators.

In Spain, since the end of the 1990s, plans/programmes promoting gender equality have been developed at central, regional and – to some extent - local level. The main objectives of these plans have been to address gender equality in the workplace, the empowerment of women, and gender-based violence.

Equality Plans are the instruments most frequently used to implement gender equality provisions and these have been developed at state, regional and local level. Equality Plans are, however, non-mandatory policy instruments in which the government's roadmap is applied to achieve gender equality. Each department decides the policy or concrete action that will be adopted to increase gender equality in its respective field of competence.

The National Equal Opportunities Strategic Plan 2014-2016 (Plan Estratégico de Igualdad de Oportunidades 2014-2016, PEIO) includes a commitment to gender mainstreaming in all policy areas, stating that the principle of equal treatment and opportunity is not exclusive to equality bodies and should involve all public agents. Notable sectoral plans are the Action Plan for Equal Opportunities of Women and Men in the Information Society (2014-2017), the Plan for Rural Women 2015-2018, or the most recent Plan for Equality within the State Administration 2015.

The main national action plan on gender equality is the National Equal Opportunities Strategic Plan 2014-2016 (Plan Estratégico de Igualdad de Oportunidades 2014-2016). One of the seven axes of this plan is devoted to 'tools to integrate the equality principle in all policies of government', such as improvement of knowledge, statistics and research, training and awareness, evaluation of gendered impacts, and budgeting. This was followed by a draft plan, the Equal Opportunities Strategic Plan 2016-2020. However, the draft was not

approved but instead replaced in 2018 by a draft of the newly created Equal Opportunities Strategic Plan 2018-2021.⁹⁴

2.4. Initiatives on promoting GE in society

The implementation of the gender equality plans is supported by nationwide projects or campaigns in more of the partners' countries. The initiatives are implemented either by governmental bodies or by non-governmental organisations active in women's rights promotion in the long run.

In 2016, the Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities of the Republic of **Slovenia** implemented a pre-defined project entitled "**Towards Equalising Power Relations between Women and Men**"⁹⁵. The project's overall aim was to understand better equal and unequal power relations between women and men to identify adequate responses to persistent imbalances in gender-based power structures in Slovenian society. One of the project objectives was to enhance the ability to monitor changes in men's and women's behaviour, attitudes, and perceptions regarding selected gender equality issues in Slovenia, specifically focusing on women's participation in economic and political decision-making and the issue of work-life balance. The Ministry commissioned the SINUS Institute to carry out a two-phase survey combining qualitative and quantitative methods.⁹⁶

Several awards related to GE are operating in Slovenia:

- a. GEMA certificate⁹⁷ is specially designed to be given to companies, which dedicate their activities and operations to implementing gender equality. It is a very new certificate, so far awarded only in 2019. Although all three companies, which received the certificate, are business-related, the certificate could have the potential to also award research and educational institutions, while all private and public organisations or companies can apply.
- b. All award is dedicated to diversity and inclusion in the business sector. It developed out of the Female-Manager Friendly Company award (between 2002-2016), which succeeded the Women Friendly Company award (established in 1991).
- c. Female Engineer of the Year⁹⁸ is award, which addresses the problem of the "invisibility" of female engineers in society. The aim of the selection is to get to know Slovenian engineers to show how they do interesting things and how they contribute to progress with their knowledge and work.

In **Slovakia**, campaigns, awards, and projects addressing GE in Slovak society are implemented by state authorities or women's and feminist's non-governmental organisations. The nationwide state campaigns and non-governmental advocacy campaigns are conditioned mainly by the available funding from the EU funds. In recent years, the financial support from

⁹⁴ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/countries/spain>

⁹⁵ Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, Department The Equal Opportunities, "Towards Equalizing Power Relations between Women and Men (2013–2016)", (2016), Gender Equality in Slovenia.pdf (globalwps.org).

⁹⁶ Reference: <http://www.mddsz.gov.si>

⁹⁷ CASPER-Certification-Award Systems to Promote Gender Equality in Research, Deliverable No. 3.3:State of the Art Analysis: mapping the awarding certification landscape in Higher Education and Research, 2020, https://zenodo.org/record/4561664#.Y17oNB_itPY

⁹⁸ Award "Inženirka leta" ("Female Engineer of the Year"), <https://inzenirka-leta.si/o-projektu/>

independent donors increased its relevance due to the anti-gender approaches of the current administration.

The Equal Pay Day campaign organised each year points to the gender pay gap and is “celebrated” on the day when women work in Slovakia for free until the end of the year. Depending on the actual gender pay gap, it is usual in November when press releases or public discussions on the reasons and impact of the gender pay gap and unfair remuneration are organised.⁹⁹

Another campaign is called **Sexist howler** (org. Sexistický kix), which is dedicated to raising awareness on sexist advertisements and promote ethical and gender competence. It is organised annually by the NGO Alliance of Women.¹⁰⁰ An awareness of GE in employment is promoted through **the Special Employer award** – Via Bona Slovakia (until 2019, it was explicitly called The Employer Sensitive towards family, gender equality and equal opportunities and was given under the auspices of the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of SR). This award is funded by the Rights, Equality and Citizenship Programme EU programme of EU (2014-2020) and organised by the private Pontis Foundation.

On the other hand, **in Poland, we see a deterioration of GE in society.** The most recent and important gender equality topics, vividly discussed and protested in the Polish public sphere, are reproductive rights and gender based violence. The Polish Constitutional Tribunal on October 22 2020, ruled that abortions in cases of foetal defects were unconstitutional, setting up a legal framework that amounts to a near total ban on pregnancy termination in Poland. In July 2020 Polish government has announced its plan to withdraw from the Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence (Istanbul Convention).

Romania has also initiatives on promoting GE in society. For example, the introduction in the Occupation Classification in Romania of the **qualifications of ‘expert in equality of opportunities/chances’ and ‘technician in equality of opportunity’** has the potential to gender mainstream the labor market.

Portuguese, Spanish and Italian´ teams did not provide any information on the initiatives on promoting gender equality in their countries.

⁹⁹ <https://www.totojrovnost.eu/index.php/2020/10/21/tlacova-sprava-poznate-hodnotu-zenskeho-eura-v-roku-2020-je-to-806-centa-a-pandemia-covid-19-situaciu-zien-na-pracovnom-trhu-este-zhorsuje/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.sexistickykix.sk/>

3. Status of gender equality in research and higher education

Before zooming to the legal and policy framework, let us describe the situation by standardised EU indicators of women in science.

The share of women PhD graduates is more than 50% in all the partners' countries. In engineering, the share ranges from 22 % in Spain to 42 % in Poland. The proportions of PhD women's graduates in information and communications technologies are even more diverse among the countries. While in Poland the percentage of women is 10%, in Bulgaria 56%.

Table 3 Proportion of women among PhD graduates (% , 2016)

COUNTRY	All fields of study	Engineering, manufacturing and construction	Information and Communication Technologies
Bulgaria	52,8	37	56
Spain	50,8	22	22
Italy	51,8	37	25
Poland	53,9	42	10
Portugal	55	37	28
Romania	54,8	38	43
Slovenia	61,3	32	24
Slovakia	52,4	31	12
EU-28 average	47,8	29	21

Source: Eurostat, Education statistics and OECD (Graduates by field)

The share of women researchers (FTE) is under 50% in all the partners' countries. In recent years the share dropped slightly down even in Bulgarian and Slovenia. However, the gender pay gap in science and development (NACE rev. 2, division 72, 2014) is not high in some countries. For example, in Bulgaria, it is even -1,4 %, Romania -6,4%, Slovenia 3,5%., Italy 6,4%. But in Spain 16,6% and Slovakia 20,6%.

Table 4 Share of women researchers out of total number of researchers (FTE, %, all sectors)

COUNTRY	2008	2010	2012	2014	2016	2018
Bulgaria	48	50	50	50	49	44
Spain	38	39	39	39	39	39
Italy	33	35	36	36	36	34
Poland	38	38	37	35	34	35
Portugal	44	44	45	44	43	43
Romania	46	45	45	45	46	46
Slovenia	33	35	34	35	33	31
Slovakia	42	42	42	41	40	39

Note: The values are rounded

Source: Eurostat, Share of women researchers, all sectors [ta_resdig_sctech_rdperes_perf__tsc00006]

Regarding indicators on career advancement, we see that the share of grade A staff among all academic staff is gender unbalanced and opens the questions about the conditions and measure how women and men are proceeding in their scientific careers. Not only the share of A grade staff considerably varies between the countries, but the share of women is lower by 1/3 percentage points or even half in comparison to men in all the countries. The Glass ceiling index (GCI) shows the difference between women and men in terms of their chances of being promoted. The higher the value, the stronger the glass ceiling effect. The GCI was the highest in Spain and Italy, the lowest in Bulgaria in 2016.

Table 5 Proportion of grade A staff among all academic staff by sex (% , 2016)

COUNTRY	Women	Men	Glass ceiling index ¹⁰¹
Bulgaria	11,3	18,9	1,16
Spain	7,3	19,0	1,85
Italy	10,6	24,7	1,68
Poland	6,6	16,6	1,78
Portugal	1,9	5,1	1,69
Romania	15,9	16,1	1,04
Slovenia	19,3	32,6	1,39
Slovakia	8,2	19,8	1,74
EU-28	7,4	16,7	1,64

Note: A grade is the single highest grade/post at which research is normally conducted within the institutional or corporate system (equivalent to full professor in most countries)

Source: European Commission, She Figures 2018¹⁰²

In terms of gender-balance in decision making, the data indicate that while in Bulgaria, Spain, Slovenia and Romania, the gender balance among members of the highest decision-making bodies of RFO was reached in 2021, in the national academies of sciences, the participation of women in decision-making is much more skewed. Except for Bulgaria, in all other countries, the share of women is below the EU-28 average. In the Higher Education Sector, the gender balance in terms of heads of HEIs is imbalanced well. The “best” situation is in Slovenia (32,4%) and Portugal (28,9%). The lowest share is in Spain (8%) and Bulgaria (14,8%). Worst to say, that the overall EU-28 average is considerable low (21,7%).

Table 6 Share of women among members of the highest decision-making body and heads of HEI (% of total)

COUNTRY	National academies of sciences			Research funding organisations			Heads of Higher Education Institutions
	2017	2019	2021	2017	2019	2021	2017
Bulgaria	51,9	55,6	55,6	44,4	40	50	14,8
Spain	11,8	12,5	15,7	40	58,3	56,4	8,0
Italy	0	12,5	12,5	n/a	30,4	30,4	24,4

¹⁰¹ The Glass Ceiling Index (GCI) is a relative index comparing the proportion of women in academia (grades A, B, and C) with the proportion of women in top academic positions (grade A positions; equivalent to full professors in most countries) in a given year. The GCI can range from 0 to infinity. A GCI of 1 indicates that there is no difference between women and men in terms of their chances of being promoted. In other words, the interpretation of the GCI is that the higher the value, the stronger the glass ceiling effect and the more difficult it is for women to move into a higher position (European Commission (2019) She figures 2018)

¹⁰² She figures 2018 - Publications Office of the EU (europa.eu)

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gender equality to unlock
research potential

Poland	8,2	15,7	15,1	21	27,9	21	18,2
Portugal	20	20	14,3	33,3	41,7	41,7	28,9
Romania	0	0	0	n/a	44,9	44,9	15,5
Slovenia	0	7,7	15,4	42,9	42,9	57,1	32,4
Slovakia	18,2	13,6	9,1	16,7	15,4	15,4	17,1
EU-28 average	21,6	25,9	26,6	37	37,8	40,3	21,7

Note: The data are based on the EIGE's standardised methodology¹⁰³

Source: EIGE, Gender Statistics Database, National academies of science: presidents and members of the highest decision-making body

Bulgarian and Slovenian project partners provided in their national reports additional statistical profiles of gender equality in research and the higher education sector.

In Bulgaria, according to NSI data for 2015 among scientists in Bulgaria has been achieved approximately gender equality, with 53% of women and 47% of men of the total number of researchers in the public sector and in the Higher Education sector. In this respect, Bulgaria is among the leading countries in the EU. For this reason, the current strategy does not include special measures to increase the relative share of women researchers but will ensure the even distribution of the various academic positions and management positions in scientific organizations. The distribution of scientists by age groups is almost even, with the lowest percentage - 21%, are researchers under the age of 34, and the highest - 27%, is the percentage of scientists between 35 and 44. In government research organizations and in the Higher Education sector there are also scientists over the age of 65, who are 5% of the total number of scientists. These data show that in terms of age distribution no collapse is expected if we manage to keep both young and experienced scientists in Bulgaria. But if Bulgaria wants to reach the average European level for the number of scientists, it is imperative to make significant efforts to attract scientific young people to a scientific career. For this purpose, the National Strategy envisages measures both for retaining scientists in Bulgaria and for attracting and retaining talented scientists, mainly up to 35 years of age.

In Slovenia, in the school year 2019/2020, 66.066 students enrolled in university studies. 5 % of them were PhD students (3.300). According to She figures 2018, the data for 2016 show that the proportion of women among doctoral or equivalent graduates was 61.3 % in 2016, which was the highest level among the EU Member States. Because of small absolute numbers of graduates, small changes in numbers can translate into significant changes in percentage terms. The two most popular fields for female graduates in the EU are natural sciences, mathematics and statistics, and health and welfare. In all the countries examined, at least one of these two fields was among the two top choices for women, apart from Slovenia where Business, administration and law and Social sciences, journalism and information were the most popular choice. Limited employment possibilities in these two fields and relatively large number of students explain struggling of women of these profiles to get adequate jobs. For the period 2008-2015, the average annual growth rate for women researchers declined in natural

¹⁰³ https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/wmid_methodology.pdf

sciences (-6.5 %). Like in almost all countries examined, the proportion of women in grade A positions increased between 2013 and 2016 (from 22.5 % to 28.9 %). In the EU as a whole, 7.4 % of women and 16.7 % of men academic staff were in grade A positions in 2016, while in Slovenia, 19.3 % of women were in grade A positions. The proportion of women among the heads of higher education institutions was the highest in Europe with the exception of Baltic countries (32.4 %).

3.1. Legislation

The legislation that frames or potentially could influence gender equality in research is either the legislation of equal treatment and equal opportunities, gender equality respectively that can be extrapolated to education and research sector, as is the case for example in the Canary Islands. In other countries, the national education law contains explicit or implicit references to gender equality and equal opportunities.

The **Spanish** Organic Law 3/2007, of 22 March, on Effective Equality between Women and Men (LOIEMH) establishes that public administrations must promote teaching and research on the meaning and scope of equality between women and men (art. 25). Because of the approval of this regulation, in the modification of the Organic Law on Universities that took place through Organic Law 4/2007, of 12 April, the preamble includes the role of universities as transmitters of values. In it, it emphasises on the importance of achieving a tolerant and egalitarian society in which fundamental rights, freedoms and equality between women and men are respected. To this end, the Law proposes that universities incorporate the value of equality as their own objective, that they establish systems to achieve parity in representative bodies, and that they promote greater participation of women in research groups, as well as the creation of specific programmes on gender equality. For the development of these functions related to the principle of equality of women and men, the Law establishes that universities will have equality units within their organisational structures (12th Additional Provision).

Much more specific is the **Canarian Islands Law 1/2010, of 26 February**, on equality between women and men, which imposes a series of mandates on the Canarian university system (Arts. 22 y 23): to promote equal opportunities in relation to professional careers; to develop measures for the reconciliation of family and work for all staff, both teaching and non-teaching; to include teaching on equality in curricula; to create postgraduate courses on gender equality and gender violence; to promote balanced representation in the composition of collegiate governing bodies and in selection and evaluation committees; promote a balanced presence in the field of research, science and technology; promote the work of university classrooms and women's institutes; promote the recognition of gender studies as a merit in the evaluation of the teaching, research and management activities of teaching and research staff.

In **Poland**, only in 2018, together with the new law regulating higher education and science in Poland, the issue of parenthood among scientists was tackled by the Ministry of Science. The 2018 Law on Higher Education and Science¹⁰⁴ guarantee students of first-, second-, long-and third-cycle programs to extend their study periods on the basis of child-care leaves. It prohibits denying access to individual education programmes to female students expecting a child and students, who became parents - regardless of their gender. It allows taking (parental) leaves by students and PhD candidates at their request. Moreover, it also states that child-care leaves extend the time of employees' internal evaluation process. In the case of young researchers, they are not included in the calculation of time of holding the doctoral title while applying for the minister's stipend.

Apart from the above mentioned recognition of scientists' role as parents, there are no other signs of gender mainstreaming in the field of R&I in Poland at the national level. To conclude, a general reform of Polish science was initiated in 2018 and it did not include gender in any way (except the 'family mainstreaming'). Although there is no official law on gender in research and higher education, universities set up their internal regulations that prevent discrimination (including this based on sex) and/or refer to equality between women and men in their statutes and strategies for development to meet requirements set by the European Charter & Code for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers and in order to obtain very prestigious HR Excellence in Research logo. Based on the most important university act – the Statute - only 6 universities in Poland (the Gdańsk University of Technology, University of Gdańsk, University of Łódź, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, University of Warsaw, Medical University of Warsaw) include equal treatment at this level of their regulations, however usually only mentioned very generally. Only the Medical University of Warsaw deals with equal rights directly pointing out gender issues.¹⁰⁵ The non-discriminatory clauses are usually incorporated into Staff Rules, in which Universities quote directly the articles of the Labour Code. Some references to equal opportunities for women and men might be found in the Codes of Ethics, however, they do not refer to gender equality directly. Seldom, universities refer to gender equality in their strategies (the Jagiellonian University¹⁰⁶ or the University of Łódź¹⁰⁷).

In terms of legal framework in **Portugal**, the Constitution of the Portuguese Republic (CRP) states that it is the fundamental task of the State to “promote equality between men and women” (art. 9), also enshrining the Principle of Equality, which states that “no one can be privileged, benefited, harmed, private from any right or exempt from any duty, on account of ancestry, sex, race, language, territory of origin, religion, political or ideological convictions, education, economic status, social status or sexual orientation” (art. 13). With

¹⁰⁴ Ustawa z dnia 20 lipca 018 r. Prawo o szkolnictwie wyższym i nauce, Dz.U. Nr 2018 poz. 1668. Retrieved from: <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20180001668/U/D20181668Lj.pdf>

¹⁰⁵ Gender Equality in Central and Eastern Europe, “Tackling gender inequalities at universities in Poland”, 2020. Available at: <https://geincee.act-on-gender.eu/Blog/tackling-gender-inequalities-universities-poland> [20.04.2021]

¹⁰⁶ Jagiellonian University, Strategia rozwoju Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego (Development Strategy of the Jagiellonian University), 2014. Available at: <https://www.uj.edu.pl/documents/10172/84593596/Strategia-Rozwoju-UJ-2014-2020.pdf/f490b8e5-83f9-4509-9f9e-f88a1d89bd3c> [01.05.2021]

¹⁰⁷ University of Lodz, Strategia rozwoju (Development Strategy), 2011. Available at: (<https://iso.uni.lodz.pl/wp-content/uploads/2011/04/Strategia-U%C5%81.pdf>) [01.05.2021]

regard to Education, Science and Culture, the CRP enshrines the full right of everyone to education, culture and teaching, with equal opportunities, and "scientific creation and research, as well as technological innovation, are encouraged and supported by the State" (art. 73). Equal opportunities and the democratization of the Education System are also the principles that govern access to Higher Education, enshrining, in the same way, the "statutory, scientific, pedagogical autonomy..." (art. 76) of Education Institutions Higher, without prejudice to the assessment of the quality of education.

In turn, the Basic Law of the Educational System (Law no. 46/86) is based on the effective equality of opportunities in school access and success (art. 2), establishing as a fundamental organizational principle "to ensure equal opportunities for both the sexes, namely through the practices of co-education and school and professional guidance", and "sensitize, for this purpose, all those involved in the educational process" (art. 3). Regarding Higher Education, Law No. 46/86 ensures "democraticity, equity and equal opportunities" (art. 12), considering among its objectives: "to stimulate cultural creation and the development of the scientific and entrepreneurial spirit (...)", "encourage the work of research and scientific investigation, aiming at the development of science and technology, the humanities and the arts, and the creation and dissemination of culture and, in this way, develop the understanding of man and the environment in which he belongs." (art. 11). With regard to Scientific Research, the same Law states that the "State must ensure the material and cultural conditions for scientific creation and Research" (art. 18).

It is also important to mention the Law No. 26/2019, which regulates the regime of balanced representation of men and women in the management staff and in the organs of the Public Administration, and which in Article 4 indicates as a minimum threshold of balanced representation the proportion of 40%, also requiring that the application lists for the collegiate bodies meet the following criteria of ordination: the first two candidates may not be of the same sex; and, there can be no more than two same-sex candidates in a row. For higher education institutions, Article 6 requires compliance with article 4 above and the threshold set, in addition to the composition of the boards of trustees of public higher education institutions of a founding nature.

In **Romania**, the legislation in force contains explicit and implicit references and/or measures to promote equal opportunities between women and men in HERI. For example, the "**National Education Law**" (**Law 1/2011**) (republished and updated; articles 114 - 231 are related to Higher Education) is the main national legislative norm that regulates higher education and universities' organization and functioning in Romania. Art. 118 al.1 stipulates that the national higher education system in Romania is based first and foremost on the principle of university autonomy. The university autonomy gives the right to the university community to establish its own mission, institutional strategy, structure, activities, its own organization and functioning, management of material and human resources, in accordance with the legislation in force. The fundamental aspects of the university autonomy are stipulated within **University Charter**, approved by the University Senate, in accordance with the legislation in force."

More importantly, Art. 118 al. 1 reiterates all principles underlying university's organization and functioning, but equal opportunities or gender equality are not explicitly among them; yet the same article stipulates that "Discrimination based on age, ethnicity, sex, social origin, political or religious orientation, sexual orientation or other types of discrimination are not permitted in higher education, except for affirmative actions provided by law."¹⁰⁸

In **Slovakia**, protection from discrimination is also highlighted in Act no. 131/2002 Coll. Act on Higher Education Institutions and Amendments to Certain Acts (the Higher Education Act) prohibits discrimination based on sex, gender, age, and other characteristics.

3.2. Strategies, action plans, programs

Gender equality is rarely promoted in research in the form of a separate strategy or action plan on gender equality in science. The only exception is **Spain, which implements the 1st Gender Equality Action Plan 2021-2023 of the National Agency of Research** for I+D+I.¹⁰⁹ The development and objectives of the specific GEP are worth mentioning for inspiration to other countries:

The **Spain** National Agency of Research (AEI), assigned to the Ministry of Science and Technology (MCIN), is responsible for the finance of the public funds of Spain for I+D+I, as well as for promoting Science and technology in all study areas. In November 2018, this institution created the Strategic Group for Gender Equality to implement gender perspective and enhance gender equality. These are defined in the Guidelines for developing the European Space for Research (ERA) in Spain 2016-2020.

In this context, the AEI develops its first gender equality diagnosis at the beginning of 2019, and afterwards, the 1st Gender Equality Action Plan 2021-2023 of the National Agency of Research for I+D+I¹¹⁰ financed activities is designed by the Strategic Group of Gender Equality.

Together with the work and diagnose carried out by the AEI in gender equality, this tool prioritises the work in three areas with seven objectives and include thirteen parts. To obtain more information about these, please read the Action Plan.

Area 1. Structures and mechanisms for gender equality. Objectives:

- Improve the analysis, monitoring and broadcasting of the data separated by sex.
- Enhance and consolidate the structures of the AEI that sustainably implement the gender equality measures considering time.

Area 2. Awareness, training, and organisational culture. Objectives:

- Improve the specialist training in gender equality in the administration of the scientific-technological application process at the AEI.

¹⁰⁸ Romanian Parliament, "Legea națională a educației" (National Education Law), 1/2011, published 10 January 2011, applicable since 9 February 2011. Retrieved From: <https://lege5.ro/gratuit/geztsobvgi/legea-educatiei-nationale-nr-1-2011>

¹⁰⁹ Agencia Estatal de Investigación. (2021). 1 Gender Equality Plan of the State Research Agency of Spain for R&D&I funding activities. https://www.ciencia.gob.es/stfls/MICINN/AEI/ficheros/I_GENDER_EQUALITY_PLAN.pdf

¹¹⁰ Agencia Estatal de Investigación, "1 Gender Equality Plan of the State Research Agency of Spain for R&D&I funding activities", 2021. Available at: https://www.ciencia.gob.es/stfls/MICINN/AEI/ficheros/I_GENDER_EQUALITY_PLAN.pdf [30/04/2021].

- Promote a better integration of gender perspective in I+D+I projects presented in application processes at the AEI.

Area 3. Scientific evaluation and monitoring. Objectives:

- Coordinate adequate implementations of gender equality criteria, establish in the legal texts.
- Integrate gender perspective in a systematic way in the scientific-technical evaluations and monitoring of the grants.
- Identify all possible factors that would contribute to creating a gap between women and men in their success as Head Researchers in a research project.

The implementation of the measures included in the 1st Gender Equality Action Plan must be done by the Strategic Group of Gender Equality of the AEI, the Equality Unit and the Unit of Women and Science of the MCIN, as well as the project SUPERA¹¹¹.

In Portugal, the Resolution of the Council of Ministers No. 61/2018, promulgates the main document on gender equality in Portugal, the ENIND. For the first time, **the National Strategy focuses on gender equality in Higher Education and in R&I as a strategic axis**, namely “egalitarian, inclusive and future-oriented scientific and technologic development” (in line with SDG 5). The ENIND also sets, for the first time, intersectionality as one of its core transversal lines. Therefore, ENIND aims to involve almost all ministries.

Regarding the field of Research and Higher Education in Portugal, the main strategic goal (4) is “to promote GE in Higher Education Institutions (HEI) and in the scientific and technologic development”. This main goal is divided into two specific objectives:

- to integrate the GE perspective in scientific and technologic productivity" (4.1.) and
- to integrate the GE perspective in higher education" (4.2.).

Among the measures to be developed, the following stand out: “development of actions to promote digital skills for women and girls within the scope of Portugal INCoDE.2030”; “renewal of the protocol between the CIG and the FCT in order to promote calls addressing the national scientific community for R&I projects in Gender, Social Relations and Policies for GE”; “support for the creation and implementation of GEP, and for advanced training in the field of discrimination, namely inter-sectoral, in HEI”.

Two key indicators of ENIND in higher education are the conduct of a study, with recommendations, for the integration of the gender perspective in governance and management practices, in educational content, and in organic units with curricula and extracurricular curricula of higher education institutions and the definition of criteria, from the perspective of gender equality, to be integrated into the evaluation and accreditation of Portuguese higher education institutions¹¹².

However, the Portugal project partners encounter major obstacles and corresponding challenges in Portugal, specifically in the Azores' Autonomous Region, for the implementation of gender equality and gender equality. One of

¹¹¹ SUPERA aims to support the promotion of equality in research and the academic world. For more information: <https://www.superaproject.eu/>

¹¹² Journal of the Republic, 1st series — No. 97 — May 21, 2018, p. 2221. The document can be found in full at: <https://dre.pt/application/conteudo/115360036>

the major challenges at both national and local levels is integrating the gender perspective in all areas of political action, both internally and within the territory, based on mechanisms for diagnosing, monitoring, and evaluating the various actions and municipal equality plans. In this way, more inclusive and egalitarian cities, towns and civil parishes can be designed.¹¹³

Italy is preparing a national strategy on gender equality, which will also focus on the integration of gender perspective in research¹¹⁴. The MIUR has made available the document titled “Indications for Positive Actions of the MIUR on Gender Issues in University and Research”.¹¹⁵ This document explains the good practices identified at the European level, indications for the integration of the gender dimension in research funded by MIUR, indications for address documents addressed to the CRUI, universities and research bodies concerning the mechanisms for selecting teaching and research staff, and indications for the evaluation of universities and research institutes.¹¹⁶

Romania, Slovakia, and Bulgaria reflect the gender issue in HEI and research within the national GE strategies or strategies in research and education.

In Romania, no national strategy is specially adopted for implementing gender equality in higher education, research, and innovation (HERI). However, the legislation in force as well as several national strategic documents, contain explicit and implicit references and/or measures to promote equal opportunities between women and men in HERI.

National Strategy for Equal Opportunities and its Implementation Plan for 2021-2027 elaborated by the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection (ANES). The National Strategy reminds us the still underdeveloped internal regulations, policies and provisions on gender equality in the field of education, which is in contrast with one of the main aims of the former national strategy on equal opportunities (2018-2021) that had sought to prioritize the integration the gender dimension in education (p. 28)¹¹⁷. Two main directions are currently being prioritized in order to promote gender equality in education: a) fighting against gender stereotypes through the introduction of the gender perspective in school curricula as well as in initial and continuous training campaigns for gender experts and teaching staff working in institutions and units at undergraduate level; b) as for HE, the strategy focuses on science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) as domains that most strongly reflect gender imbalances, despite the general increasing share of women in education at university level¹¹⁸.

¹¹³ Athena – PT national report.

¹¹⁴ See the Annex 2.

¹¹⁵ https://www.miur.gov.it/documents/20182/615845/Documento_+Indicazioni_azioni_positive_MIUR_su_temi_genere.pdf/23e81cb6-f15a-4249-9bd6-cf4fdcd113a8?version=1.0&t=1526057127577

¹¹⁶ Athena National report T2.2 for Italy

¹¹⁷ Ministry of Labour and Social Protection (Justice) (2021), Proiect de Hotărâre privind aprobarea Strategiei naționale privind promovarea egalității de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați și prevenirea și combaterea violenței domestice pentru perioada 2021-2027 și a Planului de acțiune pentru implementarea Strategiei naționale privind promovarea egalității de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați și prevenirea și combaterea violenței domestice pentru perioada 2021-2027 (Draft Decision approving the National Strategy for the Promotion of Equal Opportunities and Treatment for Women and Men and the Prevention and Combating of Domestic Violence for the period 2021-2027 and the Action Plan for the implementation of the National Strategy for the Promotion of Equal Opportunities and Treatment for Women and Men and the prevention and combating of domestic violence for the period 2021-2027). Retrieved from: <http://www.mmuncii.ro/j33/index.php/ro/transparenta/proiecte-in-dezbatere/6230-proiect-de-hotarare-privind- aprobarea-strategiei-nationale-privind-promovarea-egalitatii-de-sanse>

¹¹⁸ Ministry of Labour and Social Protection (Justice) (2019), Includiune și egalitate de șanse post-2020 – Cadru strategic național de politică pentru incluziunea socială și egalitatea de șanse post 2020 (Inclusion and Equal Opportunities Post-2020 - National strategic policy framework for social inclusion and equal opportunities post 2020). Retrieved from: <https://mmuncii.ro/j33/index.php/ro/proiecte-programe/in-curs-de-implementare/2019-sipoca653>

National Strategy for Sustainable Development 2030 (elaborated under the coordination of the Ministry of Education by the Romanian Academy)¹¹⁹

refers to 17 policy objectives (each one is treated in a separate chapter), including: chapter 4 on qualitative education, chapter 5 on gender equality, chapter 8 on decent work and economic development, chapter 9 on industry, innovation and infrastructure and chapter 10 on reducing inequalities between rural and urban areas. The chapter on education reminds us of the principle of academic autonomy that governs HE, which is always referred to within the main university strategic documents (such as the University Charter or the Code of Professional Ethics). The same chapter also underlines that sustainable development in HE can be achieved through entrepreneurship within the university environment, in order to increase the competitiveness of Romanian universities. However, no correlation is made between sustainable development, higher education and gender equality. The strategy only reiterates the aim of including the principle of sustainable development and the specialization in this area within HE, with a special emphasis on the role of interdisciplinary research in the development of a sustainable society. The chapter 4 also refers to the first strategies in the field of vocational education and training that have been adopted: the *Strategy for reducing early school leaving 2015-2020*, the *National Strategy for Tertiary Education 2015-2020*, the *National Strategy for Lifelong Learning 2015-2020* and the *National Education and Professional Training Strategy in Romania for 2016-2020*. The chapter 5 on gender equality addresses the need to deconstruct gender stereotypes related to the role of women in society and at the level of family life, as well as to increase women's participation in decision-making, to decrease gender pay gap and to combat violence against women and girls in the public and private spheres; the chapter does not contain any explicit reference to gender equality within HERI; Chapter 8 refers to the target of achieving sustainable economic growth and decent work and living conditions for all, regardless of gender, geographical location and family kinship; nevertheless, HERI is not correlated to employment policies; without being correlated to higher education or gender equality, research and innovation are included in chapter 9 related to industry and national infrastructure; the chapter does not contain any reference to gender equality or higher education and it focuses mainly on the very low share of public expenditures on research - development - innovation (RDI), constantly under 0.5% of GDP (p. 62); the chapter 10 correlates the concern for inequalities and the issue of vulnerability tackled from an intersectional perspective (women, disabled people, Roma, discriminated persons, etc.); the document stipulates the need for increasing social allowances for children, young people, elders and disabled persons as well as other vulnerable social categories, aiming at reducing all forms of discriminations; however, once again, there is no correlation between gender inequalities and the field of HERI.

In the National Strategy for Tertiary Education (2015-2020), elaborated by the Ministry of Education, competitiveness is the main principle underpinning the elaboration of the whole document; the strategy aims above all to enhance the quality of tertiary education in order to increase the labour force and its

¹¹⁹ Department of Sustainable Development (2018), *Strategia Națională pentru Dezvoltare Durabilă a României 2030 (Romanian National Strategy for Sustainable Development 2030)*. Retrieved from: <https://www.edu.ro/sites/default/files/Strategia-nationala-pentru-dezvoltarea-durabila-a-României-2030.pdf>

correlation with the labour market. The document identifies the main problems of tertiary education in Romania (constant decrease in students' enrolment, inflexible and inadequate funding mechanisms, lack of correlation with the labour market, low participation in tertiary education of disadvantaged categories – such as disabled, or students from families with low incomes, orphans or coming from foster centres, ethnics from abroad, Roma students and students from rural areas, and also reduced international mobilities for students and teaching staff). Although the strategy refers to the need to respect the principle of gender equality (for example, Art. 72, p. 30), yet no specific objective/measure aims at its implementation; the strategy does not refer to gender disaggregated beneficiaries¹²⁰.

National Strategy for Research, Development and Innovation (2014-2020): elaborated by the Ministry of Education¹²¹ was elaborated in 2014. The document underlines that, due to insufficient financial resources, the field lacks the human resource necessary for its development. However, there is not any explicit or implicit reference or concern for gender, gender equality, equal opportunities or gender mainstreaming in the field of research and innovation (the problem of insufficient human resources is treated as if it were not gendered).

National Employment Strategy 2014-2020 and its Implementation Plan (elaborated by the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection), along with the need to improve education and the training systems in place, mentions “gender equality” only once, as it refers to this principle as a specific challenge for the Romanian labour market that still remains characterized by an important gap between women and men in terms of employment rate (p. 39). However, the Strategy's Implementation Plan stipulates 4 main directions of action among which the need to improve the general employment structure through women's participation in the labour market; this objective was supposed to be achieved through, among others, work-life balance measures, provisions for childcare facilities and support services for dependent family members, awareness-raising activities on flexible working time arrangements, campaigns against gender stereotypes, etc.¹²²

We see that in the case of Romania, several strategies on equality and research exist, nevertheless, the depth of the practice is, according to the national report is questionable. It demonstrates that even existing regulations and policies may not be sufficient when combating a tradition of ignorance (or even discrimination).

Bulgaria does not have a developed comprehensive national strategy and action plan related to gender equality in science. Separate indicators and policies can be found in the Common Strategy for Gender Equality in Bulgaria 2021-27 and in the Roadmap for Research and Innovation. The first document contains indicators for monitoring the implementation of the Strategy in five priority areas:

¹²⁰ Ministry of Education (2015), Strategia Națională pentru Învățământul Tertiare 2015-2020 (National Strategy for Tertiary Education 2015-2020). Retrieved from: <https://edu.ro/strategia-națională-pentru-învățământ-terțiar>

¹²¹ Ministry of Education (2014), Strategia Națională de Cercetare, Dezvoltare și Inovare 2014 – 2020 (National Strategy for Research, Development and Innovation 2014-2020). Retrieved from: <https://www.edu.ro/sncdi2014-2020>

¹²² Ministry of Labour and Social Protection (Justice) (2014), Strategia Națională pentru Ocuparea Forței de Muncă 2014-2020 și Planul de Implementare (National Employment Strategy 2014-2020 and its Implementation Plan). Retrieved from: <http://mmuncii.ro/j33/index.php/ro/minister-2019/strategii-politici-programe/5216-sn-ocupare-forța-vmunca-2018>

- Increasing women's participation in the labour market and equal degree of economic independence;
- Reducing the gender pay and income gap;
- Promoting equality between women and men in decision-making processes;
- Combating gender-based violence and protecting and supporting victims;
- Changing the existing gender stereotypes in society in various spheres of public life.

Since 2005, the Bulgarian Strategy has been implemented through annual National Action Plans for the Promotion of Equality between Women and Men, which the Council of Ministers adopts. The plans contain specific measures within the competences of various institutions and organizations in the priority areas of the Strategy, responsible bodies, financial resources and performance indicators. However, outside the General Strategy for Gender Equality in Bulgaria 2021-30, there is no specialized national law / policy to encourage public research institutions (research organizations, universities and research funding agencies) to adopt measures for gender equality, including gender action plans.

In Slovakia, a **comprehensive national strategy or roadmap on gender equality in research and innovation is missing**. Neither gender equality in science nor gender in the content of research integrated as a cross-cutting topic into strategic policy documents in R&I. We did not find any national strategy for promoting gender equality in HEIs.

The currently most relevant research and innovation strategy in Slovakia is the **Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation of the Slovak Republic (RIS3)**, adopted in 2013 and its implementation plan from 2017.¹²³ The elaboration and acceptance of RIS3 by the European Commission was an ex-ante conditionality for the Multiannual Financial Framework 2014 -2020. The smart specialisation strategies of the Member States of the European Union should contribute to meeting the objectives of the Europe 2020 strategy for **smart, sustainable and inclusive growth** by strengthening the EU's regional and national research and innovation potential. The RIS3 also defines measures for meeting the objectives of the National Reform Program and specific recommendations of the Council for the Slovak Republic. The RIS3 and implementation plans **do not reference gender equality research and innovation** and are completely gender insensitive, i.e. "gender-neutral". The only reference to gender appears in the demographic chapter describing the sex distribution of the population. The gender distribution is not further mentioned even when describing students' population in various academic areas and sciences. The strategic objective of improving the human resources for innovative Slovakia does not deal with gender equality. It focuses on the following six measures:

- Improving the quality of secondary education - mainly harmonisation of education with market demands;

¹²³ <https://www.mirri.gov.sk/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/EN.pdf>

- Improving the quality of higher education - similar focus on the employability of graduates;
- Improving business involvement in education - to improve linkages between education and practice;
- Improving the quality of life-long education - to elaborate a system of quality verification;
- Increasing emphasis on education in fields of RIS3 priority areas - mainly in the area of financing and motivational tools;
- Supporting the mobility of highly skilled workers - focus on the return of highly skilled Slovak workers from abroad.

Slovak Long-term plan in educational, research, development and other creative activities for universities for the years 2016 - 2021¹²⁴ adopted by the Ministry of education, science, research and sport of the Slovak Republic does not mention gender equality or equal opportunities. However, focus on ensuring accessible and diverse higher education, improving the quality and relevance of higher education and increase its efficiency and credibility by promoting the openness and transparency of the higher education environment.

The newly adopted Slovak **Strategy National strategy for equality between women and men and equal opportunities in the Slovak Republic for 2021-2027** contains a section titled Education, science and research. It is mainly devoted to tackling gender horizontal and vertical segregation in education. One of its operation aims is to promote a higher representation of women in science, research and higher education. However, in the action plan, no task is planned in these terms. The CEDAW Committee is concerned about the persistent gender segregation in education, the low level of participation of women and girls in mathematics, science and technology studies and the low level of representation of women in teaching positions in higher education for a long time and recommends to adopt measures, including temporary special measures in this area.¹²⁵ So far, no comprehensive programs or initiatives have been proposed in these terms. However, specific goals to promote GE in research and HEI may be adopted by the institutions individually in Slovakia. For instance, the most prominent university in Slovakia, Comenius University, does not include any promotion of GE in its strategic plan.¹²⁶ Even though the issue is not present in strategic documents of the HEIs, several of them declare to participate in The Human Resources Strategy for Researchers- HRS4R projects.

In **Slovenia**, no common GE strategy in research exists. However, GE is reflected in more strategic documents on research, innovation and ERA. In the document **Strategy of work and development of Research Agency of Republic Slovenia (ARRS) 2016-2020**¹²⁷, the Agency lists different indicators to evaluate its activity and impact on research. One of the fields to monitor is the number of women working on research projects and number of women among project leaders. Gender balance in decision-making and the enhancement of women's participation in research are regulated by the Rules on the Procedures of the

¹²⁴ <https://www.minedu.sk/data/att/10633.rtf>

¹²⁵ CEDAW/C/SVK/CO/5-6 - E - CEDAW/C/SVK/CO/5-6 -Desktop (undocs.org)

¹²⁶ <https://uniba.sk/fileadmin/ruk/legislativa/2014/dlhodoby-zamer-uk-2014-2024.pdf>

¹²⁷ Research Agency of Republic Slovenia (ARRS), "Strategija delovanja in razvoja Javne agencije za raziskovalno dejavnost Republike Slovenije 2016 – 2020", ("Strategy of Work and Development of ARRS 2016-2020"), (2016), <http://www.arrs.si/sl/agencija/inc/2017/Strategija-ARRS-2016-2020.pdf>.

(co)financing and Assessment of Research Activities and on Monitoring the Implementation of Research Activities: Article 35 (in the case of absence of the researcher due to parental leave in the duration of at least six months, this should be taken into account at project applications and also prolongs the period until PhD defence); and Article 172i (all permanent and temporary bodies of the Agency should be gender-balanced)

The area of Research and Innovation in Slovenia is regulated by the **Resolution on Research and Innovation strategy 2011-2020**. Measure 34 foresees an Action Plan for Improving Career Opportunities for Researchers in all Career Periods and for Ensuring the Gender Equality Principle. In the Task “Improvement of career opportunities for researchers, and inclusion of the gender equality principle”, it is stated that the basic requirement for establishment of career opportunities for researchers is effective information network on possibilities of research work in Slovenia and abroad. Besides, a living environment that will attract people from abroad, and encourage domestic researchers for international mobility is mentioned as important. Foundation for the establishment of career opportunities as an introduction of encouraging statutory provisions that will assure social security for researchers, favourable working conditions, and clear employment procedures was proposed. It is put to necessary to reduce vertical segregation, therefore, support from a decision-making level for changes, and modernisation of research organizations, are stated as very important. The subsequent steps to obtain these goals were to adopt measures for gender equality, to change legislation, and to focus attention to the role of gender in research, in pedagogic work, and in management.

In order to increase the participation of women in science, for improving scientific excellence, connections with European Research Area (ERA) and its goals, the **Slovenian Strategy for Strengthening the European Research Area 2016-2020** (Slovenian ERA Roadmap 2016-2020)¹²⁸ was put into force in 2016. One of the priorities was gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research (priority area 4). The implementation of these measures is evaluated in the **Assessment of Slovenian ERA 2016-2020: Progress Report 2018**¹²⁹. The five objectives in priority area 4 comprehensively address the topic of gender equality in research in Slovenia. The existing vertical and horizontal gender differentiation is suitably addressed through as many as eight measures, which range from design of action plans to continuous support to the Commission for Equal Opportunities (ex-commission on Women in Science) and data gathering. However, the very fact that gender equality is among the ERA Roadmap priorities stipulates discussion on the issue and especially publicly funded research institutions pay more attention to gender mainstreaming. Additional effort in this priority should be put forward by the Slovenian Research Agency, which could stimulate more actively gender balance through eligibility criteria for research projects and Junior researchers’ programme. None of these national policy/legal documents and its measures mentions rewarding, certification or accreditation system, that would explicitly consider gender equality in higher education or

¹²⁸ Slovenian Strategy for Strengthening the European Research Area 2016-2020 (Slovenian ERA Roadmap 2016-2020), available at https://era.gov.at/object/document/2763/attach/SI_ERA_Roadmap.pdf

¹²⁹ Assessment of Slovenian ERA 2016-2020: Progress Report 2018, http://mizs.arhiv-spletisc.gov.si/fileadmin/mizs.gov.si/pageuploads/Znanosti/pdf/ERA_Roadmap/SI_ERA_roadmap_progress_report_2018.pdf

research institutions. The measures also do not consider intersectional discrimination. The link between public funding programmes and gender equality is established. According to CASPER report ARRS also considers gender equality when evaluating projects (Rules on the Procedures of the (co)financing and Assessment of Research Activities and on Monitoring the Implementation of Research Activities: Article 35).¹³⁰ (reference: CASPER report).

In **Poland**, the issue is only recognized within the family policies framework in the legislation. Policies on GE or research are missing. Although the situation differs across the countries, usually universities and RFOs adopt their regulations to prevent discrimination, primarily to requirements set by the European Charter & Code for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers and HR Excellence in Research. Horizon program is also an important motivator to adopt policies on an institutional level, mostly when gender issue is viewed as a controversial topic.

Poland does not have any comprehensive national strategy or road map to advance gender equality in research and innovation. There is no official document on gender in HEI and R&I sector, and the Act of 3rd December 2010 on the Implementation of Certain Provisions of the European Union in the Field of Equal Treatment does not tackle the issue of discrimination based on gender in higher education and research institutions. In terms of gender equality, women are perceived only as mothers. The measures that tackle the issue of women's participation in research and innovation cover only reconciliation of pregnancy and motherhood with performing at the research centres and HEIs. This is why the institution responsible for implementing those measures had been the Ministry of Labour and Social Policy for a long time. In 2014 project 'Toddler in the Academia' (2014-2016) and in 2016 'Toddler +' (ongoing) were launched by the Ministry - providing funds to, among others, universities to set up nurseries or care centres for children under the age of 3, in order to fulfil the needs of scientists-parents.

Some Polish HEIs have also established bodies responsible for equal treatment (e.g. the University of Warsaw¹³¹, the Adam Mickiewicz University¹³², the Jagiellonian University¹³³, the Nicolaus Copernicus University¹³⁴, the Wrocław University¹³⁵, the Gdansk University¹³⁶). Although some Polish universities work on developing gender equality plans, the very first one was adopted only in August 2020 by the University of Warsaw¹³⁷. Some gender mainstreaming strategies had been implemented before at the Faculties' level (e.g. Institute of Physics and the Jagiellonian University), but the GEP at the Warsaw University is the first plan at the HEI level.

¹³⁰ CASPER report

¹³¹ University of Warsaw, "Equality specialist", Press release, 2017. Available at: <http://rownowazni.uw.edu.pl/glowny-specjalista-ds-rownowprawnienia-na-uw/> [01.05.2021]

¹³² Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, "The Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment", Press release. Available at: <https://amu.edu.pl/studenci/pelnomocnik-ds-rownego-tractowania> [01.05.2021]

¹³³ Jagiellonian University, "Pełnomocniczka Rektora UJ. ds bezpieczeństwa studentów i doktorantów" (Representative of the Rector of Jagiellonian University for the security of students and doctors), press release, 2020. Available at: <https://bezpieczny-student.uj.edu.pl/pelnomocnik> [01.05.2021]

¹³⁴ Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, "Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment". Available at: <https://www.umk.pl/uczelnia/wladze/pelnomocnicy/> [01.05.2021]

¹³⁵ University of Wrocław, "Anti-discrimination Ombudsman". Available at: <https://uni.wroc.pl/rowny-uwr/o-rzeczniku-kontakt/> [01.05.2021]

¹³⁶ University of Gdansk, "Office of the Ombudsman for Equal Treatment and Counteracting Mobbing". Available at:

https://ug.edu.pl/o_uczelni/universytet_odpowiedzialny_spolecznie/biuro_rzeczniaka_ds_rownego_tractowania_i_przeciwdzialania_mobbingowi [01.05.2021]

¹³⁷ University of Warsaw, "Zarządzenie nr 194 Rektora Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego z dnia 27 sierpnia 2020 r. w sprawie „Planu równości pici dla Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego oraz planu działań równościowych na lata 2020-2023" (Decree No. 194 of the Rector of the University of Warsaw of 27 August 2020 on the "Gender equality plan for the University of Warsaw and the equality action plan for 2020-2023)", 2020. Available at: <https://monitor.uw.edu.pl/Lists/Uchway/Attachments/5574/M.2020.371.Zarz.194.pdf> [01.05.2021]

The regulations, equality bodies, and GEPs at universities aim to guarantee that gender equality measures will be provided in the Polish scientific organisations. So far, they include: flexible work arrangements (paid sabbatical leave, flexible working hours, part-time, tele- and task-oriented work), anti-harassment, -mobbing, and/or –discrimination policies and bodies; programs dedicated for parents coming back to work after parental leaves; policies taking into account gaps in employment resulting from maternal, paternal or parental leaves.

Growing attention needs to be paid to **the emerging and existing gender backlash** in the countries that might hamper the strategic direction of GE in research. The promotion of GE in research and HEIs is therefore an effort by each organization rather than a national strategy. This tension may grow in future and it may result in only partial results and un-coordinated activities. In Slovakia, the label “gender” is also perceived as something negative and the GE agenda is constantly narrowed by local authorities.

3.3. Initiatives and projects on promoting GE in research

Civil society and non-governmental initiatives often operate as a vital substitute when governmental policies are insufficient or slow in their implementation. The issue of gender equality should be no exception. Nevertheless, the number of such initiatives identified in national reports are limited, and there may be different reasons for this state. Due to the lack of funding and a constant backlash, these initiatives may have weakened or disappeared in recent years. In some cases, the possible explanation is that these initiatives focus on GE's other aspects (e.g. gender based violence) and their intersection with GE in research is not visible. Regardless of the reason, we find it important to point out that the project consortium partners should evaluate in more detail existing initiatives in their countries to promote GE as these initiatives may be an important partner, having the expertise and know-how.

Often, existing initiatives are tied up to funding from the EU. **Horizon programme** is the most important factor which leads RPOs and RFOs across the countries to deal with GE in research. This is usually reflected only by individual institutions when the organizations want to meet eligibility criteria in the programme. In the case of Poland, it is often in contradiction to the national policies and social discourse.

In some countries, national programmes often link to support from EEA grants, usually focusing on family policies and gender-based violence gender balance in decision-making. The systematic continuation of these programs remains a challenge. In Slovenia and Slovakia, project partners refer to awards for employers, usually from the business sector, which aims to promote fair and equal opportunities for men and women and work-life balance.

In **Portugal**, the Ge-HEI project "Gender Equality in Higher Education Institutions" has been implemented thanks to EEA grants, aiming to build concrete tools to analyse current practices in HEI, to promote women representation and, also, to create recommendations that facilitate the inclusion of equality criteria into the Portuguese evaluation and accreditation system of HEI (Torres, 2019).¹³⁸

In Portugal, we can highlight some initiatives and projects that aim to place gender equality on the agenda and in the life of research and higher education institutions:

- **FCT - GENDER RESEARCH 4 COVID-19 – June 2020:** Special support for research projects on the impact of health emergency caused by COVID-19 on gender inequalities and violence against women and domestic violence.
- **UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA:** Projeto SPEAR - Supporting and Implementing Plans for Gender Equality in Academia and Research (H2020)¹³⁹. There are other initiatives at the Universidade Nova de Lisboa in the context of gender equality aimed at boosting and encouraging women's participation in areas where they are normally less represented (ICT) such as the "Mathematical Women's Conference" or the "Engineers for one day" project. Another example is "NOVA Women in Business", a club that aims to empower young women to embrace professional challenges.
- **UNIVERSITY OF COIMBRA:** GendER@UC - working together for an inclusive Europe; SUPERA Project: aims to combat inequalities between women and men in academia by implementing action plans for gender equality (GEP) in six entities of the European scientific system (including the University of Coimbra). "Understanding gender inequalities in academia as a structural, cross-cutting, complex and multidimensional phenomenon, the project aims to contribute to the integration of the gender dimension into the policies and practices of implementation partners in four key areas. Three of the areas correspond to objectives defined by the European Commission, notably within the framework of the European Research Area: (i) remove barriers to women's recruitment, retention and career progression; (ii) eliminate gender imbalances in decision-making; (iii) Strengthen the gender dimension in research programmes and educational content. The fourth area is cross-cutting and concerns (iv) Gender biases and stereotypes, often on the basis of gender imbalances observed in previous areas"¹⁴⁰.
- **MINHO UNIVERSITY - Gender Equality Plans for Information Sciences and Technology Research Institutions (EQUAL UNIVERSITY)** emerges within a European network, ERCIS - European Research Centre for Information Systems – and aims to "identify and introduce a set of good gender equality practices into the academic community; understanding what drives the two genders – male and female – to opt for the area of technology and how they evolve in this area, both academically and professionally, was the researchers' initial concern"¹⁴¹.

¹³⁸ <https://www.eeagrants.gov.pt/pt/programas/conciliacao-e-igualdade-de-genero/projetos/projetos-pre-definidos/pdp2-ge-hei-gender-equality-in-higher-educations-institutions/>

¹³⁹ <https://www.unl.pt/investigacao/projetos-financiados>

¹⁴⁰ <https://www.uc.pt/supera/projeto>

¹⁴¹ https://www.eng.uminho.pt/pt/media/_layouts/15/uminho.portaisueoi.ui/pages/eventsdetail.aspx?id=50400

- UNIVERSITY OF LISBON - IGOT Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning Institute (IGOT + IGUAL) (H2020 – Gearing Roles) Plan for Gender Equality. "The project has the firm purpose of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to academic careers, and contributing to real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational and multisectoral collaboration is supported by training actions, mentoring activities, awareness-raising campaigns, as well as videos, podcasts, workshops and conferences for dissemination of results, sharing of good practices and networking"¹⁴².
- UNIVERSITY OF AVEIRO - The University of Aveiro, in partnership with six other institutions from Germany, Cyprus, Spain, Greece, Poland and Portugal, leads the project *O'bias - Overcoming gender Bias in Career Opportunities*, which aims to contribute to overcoming existing gender imbalances in youth and adult access to career opportunities and personal development ¹⁴³.
- UNIVERSIDADE DA BEIRA INTERIOR (UBI) - UBIGUAL - Gender Equality Plan - Center for Social Studies. It should be noted that UBI pioneered the implementation of GEP ¹⁴⁴.

In **Romania**, apart from the national strategies¹⁴⁵ and policies that have a more or less direct impact on gender equality in higher education¹⁴⁶, research and innovation, there are also important **national plans and programs** aiming at reforming the entire educational system, such as "**Educated Romania**"¹⁴⁷, project under the auspices of the Romanian Presidency for 2018-2030. The project refers to social inequalities as one of the most important factors that reinforce inequalities related to access to education, without, however, mentioning the principle of gender equality¹⁴⁸. For instance, as regards tertiary education, the document mentions the following objectives:

- Increasing university autonomy while increasing the universities' public accountability;
- Developing the internationalization of tertiary education;
- Ensuring the quality of education in accordance with the international norms and recommendations;
- Developing research within universities and increasing the performance of doctoral schools in accordance with the principles of transparency, ethics and academic integrity;
- Professionalizing university management;
- Developing a tertiary education system that fosters the access of all students to quality study programs. (p. 42).

TARGET¹⁴⁹ is another important example of Romanian programs aiming at implementing gender equality within RPOs and RFOs in the Mediterranean basin.

¹⁴² http://www.igot.ulisboa.pt/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/PGE_IGOT_Conselho-de-Escola.pdf

¹⁴³ <https://obiasproject.eu/>

¹⁴⁴ http://www.igualdadedegenero.ubi.pt/index.php?option=com_content

¹⁴⁵ Romanian Government, "Strategia de Cercetare si Inovare 2014-2020" (Research and Innovation Strategy 2014-2020). Retrieved from:

http://www.cdi2020.ro/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/STRATEGIA_Versiunea-tehnica_Februarie-2014.pdf

¹⁴⁶ Romanian Parliament, "Legea națională a educației" (National Education Law), 1/2011, published 10 January 2011, applicable since 9 February 2011.

Retrieved From: <https://lege5.ro/gratuit/geztsobvigi/legea-educatiei-nationale-nr-1-2011>

¹⁴⁷ Romania Educata, Project Results 2020. Retrieved from: <http://www.romaniaeducata.eu/rezultatele-proiectului/>

¹⁴⁸ Romanian Parliament, "Legea nr 202 din 19 aprilie 2002 privind egalitatea de sanse si de tratament intre femeii si barbati" (Law no. 202 of April 19, 2002 on equal opportunities and treatment between women and men). Published 5 June 2013. Retrieved from: <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/35778>

¹⁴⁹ TARGET Project website, <http://www.gendertarget.eu/about/>

The program has been conducted during 2017-2021 and it includes 3 research performing organizations from Serbia, Morocco and Greece, 3 research funding organizations from Romania, Italy, and Cyprus as well a Mediterranean Engineering School's network (RMEI). The program has been coordinated by the Institute of Advanced Research from Austria and included, among its partners, the Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ARACIS)¹⁵⁰, which elaborated a Gender Equality Plan¹⁵¹ focused on the following four directions: human resources, decision structures, research content and transversal measures (the GEP is not yet publicly available).

As regards Research & Innovation, another important program in which Romania also participated is **GENERA** project (2015-2018) as part of Horizon 2020; the project aimed at continuing, monitoring and improving the Gender Equality Plans of Research Institutions and Organizations specifically in the physics research field. GENERA comprised a Consortium of 13 beneficiary partner Research Performing and Research Funding Organizations, including Horia Hulubei National Institute for R&D in Physics and Nuclear Engineering (IFIN-HH). Although the GENERA Network participates in a new Horizon 2020 project, ACT, as a testbed for advancing Communities of Practice in the area of gender equality in research.¹⁵² The Romanian Institute is not mentioned anymore as part of the network.

Last but not least, different initiatives aim at stimulating (young) women in research, especially in the fields of life science and physical science. For example¹⁵³, the **L'Oréal - UNESCO Private Scholarship Program for Women in Science** was Launched in Romania in 1999. In 2020, the 11th edition of the program took place. As a result, during the last dossier-based competition, 4 Romanian female scientists, under the age of 40, were granted scholarships.

Recently the NGOs Coalition for Gender Equality launched an extensive project called **EGALIS: Gender Equality through social change and education**, project supported by SEE and Norwegian through the Active Citizens Fund in Romania, gendering education being an important component of the project.

Slovenian initiatives (awards, benchmarking, or other) that encourage institutions of the public research sector to promote structural changes/modernisation as to promote gender equality are:

1. The Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science, which assists the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport.
2. Participation in EU projects (CHANGE, GARCIA)
3. GEMA certificate, All award, L'Oréal awards for young female researchers.
4. L'Oréal-UNESCO For Women in Science International Award

One of the most important catalysers of gender equality promotion in **Polish** science and research is European Union. Linking funding with gender equality provisions encourages HEIs and research institutions to accelerate their efforts

¹⁵⁰ ARACIS, Raport de activitate (Activity Report), 2020. Retrieved from: http://www.aracis.ro/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Raport_de_activitate_al_ARACIS_2018.pdf

¹⁵¹ ARACIS, "Participarea ARACIS la proiectul international. Adoptarea unei abordări reflexive a egalității de gen pentru transformarea instituțională – TARGET" (ARACIS participation in the international project. Adopting a reflective approach to gender equality for institutional transformation – TARGET), 2018. Available at: <https://www.aracis.ro/target/> [Accessed 30 April 2021]

¹⁵² <https://genera-project.com/index.php/act-genera-network>

¹⁵³ Dana Cosman, "L'Oréal și UNESCO au desemnat câștigătoarele burselor L'Oréal – UNESCO Pentru Femeile din Știință", 2020. Available at: <https://start-up.ro/bursele-l-oreal-unesco-pentru-femeile-din-stiinta-castigatoarele-din-romania/> [Accessed 30 April 2021]

towards gender equality. Especially, Horizon 2020 framing program played an important role. Since its establishment, many Polish research and HE institutions have been implementing projects focusing on the development of gender equality policies, measures or/and plans (for example, GENERA¹⁵⁴ and ACT¹⁵⁵ project implemented at the Jagiellonian University in Krakow). Most of the currently developed measures are aimed at helping women to reconcile their family and scientific work. Good examples of such initiatives are “**WRACAM**”¹⁵⁶ program at the Poznań University of Economics and Business, which is a grant program with funding up to 15 000 zł (ok. 3600 euro) for persons who have returned from parental leave or “**POMOST**”¹⁵⁷ run by Foundation for Polish Science, which supports scientists raising small kids or expecting a baby through grants. It is worth stating though, that both projects have already ended and were not continued on a larger scale, as a part of public policy in science.

In the absence of other provisions, those tackling scientists' role as parents are important in addressing gender equality in the scientific world. However, there is a great lack of a comprehensive approach to gender issues, which would go beyond reconciling parenthood and scientific career.

In **Slovakia**, Initiatives and projects devoted to institutional change towards more gender-balanced working conditions and research institutions overall occurred dependently on the funding or grant-awarding of such initiatives. For projects currently focused on preparing or implementing gender equality plans, see section 2.2.3. Additionally, sporadic initiatives to increase awareness of women's situation in research or promote women in research usually occur on the International day of women and girls in science (11th February). Unfortunately, these are generally only one-moment event without any follow-up or relevant policies initiation.¹⁵⁸

Several **awards related to women's scientific accomplishment** or support of women in specific research areas are in place in Slovakia:

- **The L'Oréal-UNESCO For Women in Science Program:** despite its ambiguous background, the program was launched in Slovakia in 2016. The program is run in cooperation with the Slovak Commission of UNESCO, the Slovak Academy of Sciences and the Slovak organisation for Research and Development activities (SOVVA). Each year, following the Slovak Academy of Sciences, they declare the criteria for the given year and publish the current application at www.forwomeninscience.com.
- **Scientist of the Year:** The Center of Scientific and Technical Information of the Slovak Republic, the Slovak Academy of Sciences and the Association of Slovak Scientific and Technical Societies announce a call each year for awarding influential Slovak scientists, technologists and young researchers from all fields of science and technology. The award aims to professionally and socially highlight the most influential personalities of scientific life and the best-achieved results in science and

¹⁵⁴ GENEREA Project, <https://genera-project.com/> [26.04.2021]

¹⁵⁵ Gender Equality in Central and Eastern Europe, “On the way to Gender Equality - Community of Practice for Gender Equality in Central and Eastern Europe”, 2019. Available at <https://geincee.act-on-gender.eu/way-gender-equality-community-practice-gender-equality-central-and-eastern-europe> [27.04.2021]

¹⁵⁶ Poznań University of Economics and Business. Available at: <http://ue.poznan.pl/pl/v-edycja-programu-wracam,a68072.html> [30.04.2021]

¹⁵⁷ Foundation for Polish Science. Available at: <https://www.fnp.org.pl/oferta/pomost-granty-powrotowe/> [30.04.2021]

¹⁵⁸ E.g. see (59) Zeny vo vede s Marianou Szapuovou - YouTube;

research in Slovakia. In 2020, the award had five categories: Scientist of the Year SR, Young researcher, Innovator of the Year, Technologist of the Year, Personality of international cooperation. A quick audit on the gender of the laureates revealed that in the last five years (2015 – 2016), out of 25 awarded scientists, only two were women.¹⁵⁹

- **The ESET Science Award** – award granted by the ESET Foundation annually since 2019 in the purpose to recognise individuals of Slovak science through their internationally acclaimed scientific results or breakthrough inventions. The award has three categories: outstanding individual contributor to Slovak science (under the age of 35), exceptional young scientists and outstanding academic. The award is focused on all scientific fields except the social sciences. It is positive, that the statute of the award is written in gender balanced language, i.e. that also the female forms of nouns such as female scientists and female finalists are included. Out of the 15 finalists in 2019, 2 women are nominated, the same also in 2020. The jury, composed by 45 members, involved 12 women in total.¹⁶⁰ The main category laureate “The outstanding individual contributor to Slovak science”, receives a financial prize in the amount of EUR 100,000, the other categories EUR 10,000 each. The award is not bound to any particular purpose.¹⁶¹
- **Slovak Women of the Year:** the award is based on voting for extraordinary women in several categories, one of which is “Science and Research”. Only women are nominated and awarded on publicly honourable event broadcast by the public TV station.¹⁶²

In **Spain**, since 2018, the High Council of Scientific Research (CSIC) awards the Gender Equality Accreditation Distinctive to research institutions within the CSIC. The award aims to promote the gender perspective in all areas of CSIC as well as measures to eliminate gender barriers. The last award call was given in 2021 to the Institute of Mathematical Sciences (ICMAT)¹⁶³, with a total sum of 5000 euros, for its work in the design and implementation of equality policies. In the same way, the Women and Science Unit and the Observatory Women, Science and Innovation from the Ministry of Science and Innovation are developing a distinctive “Gender equality in R + D + I”, with a first call expected for 2021.

In **Italy**, the importance of incentives to promote GE in research is increasing. One example is given by the need to have a Gender Equality Plan for the eligibility in the Horizon Europe Programme is a strong incentive for the research organisations and the Universities to take actions aiming to promote Gender Equality. MIUR, in its document titled “Indicazioni per azioni positive del MIUR sui temi di genere”¹⁶⁴ provides guidelines to be adopted by Universities and RPOs and RFOs. MIUR proposed actions such as the national competition for students titled “STEM: plural feminine” (in Italian, “STEM: femminile plurale”). The

¹⁵⁹ https://ncpvat.cvtisr.sk/sk/popularizacne-aktivita/vedec-roka-sr.html?page_id=973

¹⁶⁰ <https://www.esetscienceaward.sk/en/home>

¹⁶¹ <https://www.esetscienceaward.sk/assets/documents/ESET-Science-Award-Statute-2021-en.pdf>

¹⁶² <https://www.slovenkaroka.sk/o-ankete/>

¹⁶³ CSIC press release. Accessed in 29/04/2021 and retrieved from <https://www.csic.es/en/node/1266445>

¹⁶⁴ https://www.miur.gov.it/documents/20182/991467/Documento_+Indicazioni_azioni_positive_MIUR_su_temi_genere.pdf/23e81cb6-f15a-4249-9bd6-cf4fdcd113a8?version=1.0

competition aimed to encourage reflection on the presence of women in STEM disciplines to contribute to a critical reading of gender prejudices and stereotypes concerning scientific, technological, engineering and mathematical subjects, as well as encourage female students to study these subjects.

The Bulgarian Athena project team did not provide any information on the initiatives promoting GE in research specifically.

3.4. Actors and responsibility in promotion GE in research and HEI

The following text provides information on the responsible national bodies for setting GE policies, who bears the responsibility of promoting, implementing, and monitoring GE in research and HEIs in the partners' countries. Additionally, we explored in which countries and levels the GEPs are already in place or the preparation phase.

- Ministries and bodies that are in charge of setting policy priorities on gender equality

The project partners provided information on the relevant **ministries and bodies that are in charge of setting policy priorities on gender equality** and non-discrimination in institutions of the research sector and HEIs in their countries.

In **Spain**, the Ministry of Science and Innovation oversees the implementation of gender equality policies, following the regulations established in Constitutional Law 3/2007, 22nd March, for the effective equality of women and men, the Science, Technology and Innovation Law and the National Strategy of Science and Technology, and Innovation 2013-2020, which focuses on research and innovation. To carry out its work, several organisations have been established:

- Equality Unit, regulated by the article 77 of the Constitutional Law 3/2007, 22nd March, and the article 3.2 of the Royal Decree 259/2019, 12th April.
- Unit of Women and Science, whose objective is to implement the Order PRE/525/2005, of 7th March, and ensure women access and have a place in research centres.
- Observatory Women, Science, and innovation, which is an interdisciplinary organisation in charge of measuring and advancing gender equality in research institutions, as well as promoting gender equality policies in the Spanish System of Science, Technology, and Innovation.

Together with these organisations, each research institution dependent on the Ministry of Science and Innovation has its own Equality Unit that oversees the implementation of gender policies. The Observatory of Women, Science and innovation, as well as the Cabinet of the Minister of Universities and the General Secretary's Office of Universities are the bodies implementing the GE policies.

The latter organisations carry out their duties through the *Mesa de Género y Universidades*.

In **Italy**, the Department for Equal Opportunities of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers is the office of the Government that deals with the coordination of regulatory and administrative initiatives in all matters relating to the design and implementation of equal opportunity policies. Any policy or law related to the research and university needs to be defined in collaboration with the Ministry of University and Research (MIUR). Any initiative also requires the involvement of the Conference of Rectors of Italian Universities (CRUI) and the network of Committees for equal opportunities (CUGs) that in Italian are named „Comitato Unico di Garanzia“.

In **Poland**, gender equality and non-discrimination issues are regulated under the Constitution, the Labour Code¹⁶⁵ and Act of 3rd December, 2010 on the implementation of certain provisions of the European Union in the field of equal treatment¹⁶⁶. There is no strategy for Research and HE institutions, neither there is an institution or committee dedicated to overseeing the implementation of such a strategy. Supervision of the activities of the research sector and HEIs and their compliance with the law is exercised by the Minister responsible for higher education and science. The supervision of military, artistic and medical universities is exercised by the relevant ministers. Supervision of public theological universities is exercised by the Minister and the Church authorities according to the rules laid down by international agreements concluded with the Holy See.

In **Slovenia**, the Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, the Equal Opportunities Division, is responsible for the area of equal opportunities and coordinates gender equality policy. It proposes, recommends, implements and facilitates programmes and actions aimed at promoting equality between women and men. The tasks of the Equal Opportunities Division include drawing up national programmes for equal opportunities for women and men, carrying out analyses and compiling reports, and conducting awareness-raising campaigns. It is responsible for preparing and implementing different activities, according to the Equal Opportunities for Women and Men Act and the Implementation of the Equal Treatment Act.

The Ministry of Education, Science and Sport is responsible for implementing the Research and innovation strategy of Slovenia (RISS) 2011-2020 and the UNESCO L'Oreal Scholarship. Under the Ministry, there is also a Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science, which is very active in the area (research and data collection; suggestion of legal changes, including changes in order to create an action plan to improve career possibilities of women; awareness-raising; dissemination of research findings; promotion of gender equality, etc.).

The Slovenian Research Agency is responsible for carrying out the Rules on the Procedures of the (co)financing and Monitoring of Research Activities

¹⁶⁵ Ustawa z dnia 26 czerwca 1974 r. Kodeks Pracy, Dz.U. Nr 1974 Nr 24 poz. 141. Retrieved from: <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU19740240141/U/D19740141Lj.pdf>

¹⁶⁶ Ustawa z dnia 3 grudnia 2010 r. o wdrożeniu niektórych przepisów Unii Europejskiej w zakresie równego traktowania, Dz. U. 2010 Nr 254poz. 1700. Retrieved from: <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20102541700>

Implementation. It is also responsible for different tasks regarding research areas in Slovenia (for example, it selects and finances research and infrastructure programmes; it manages young researcher projects; it monitors programmes, evaluates and analyses the implementation of research).

In **Slovakia**, no specific ministry or other state authority is explicitly in charge of setting policy priorities on gender equality/non-discrimination in institutions of the research sector and HEIs. It is assumed that the responsible bodies for setting policy priorities on gender equality/non-discrimination in institutions of the research sector and HEIs should be the same that propose and coordinate the R&I, HEIs and GE policies. In an ideal situation, two ministries would intensively cooperate Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic, Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport. The coordination and implementation of the R&I agenda are mainly distributed within the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport and the Ministry of Investments, Regional Development and Informatization of the Slovak Republic. The Managing Authority of the RIS3 SR Implementation is the Council of the Government of the Slovak Republic for Science, Technology and Innovation, whose cross-sectional, working, coordinating and communication body is the Permanent Commission of the Government Council for Science, Technology and Innovation for RIS3 SR Implementation. It is worth mentioning that the representation in both managing authorities is significantly gendered unbalanced. In the Council of the Government of the Slovak Republic for Science, Technology and Innovation, out of 26 members, there are only two women. In the Permanent Commission of the Council of the Government of the Slovak Republic for Science, Technology and Innovation for RIS3 implementation, there are five women out of 15 members.

- Legal responsibility for advancing GE in research and HEIs

In **Spain**, the Observatory Women, Science and innovation is in charge of advancing gender equality, working together with relevant research and innovation institutions, as well as ten other Ministries: Ministry of Defence; Education and Vocational Training; Presidency, Court Relations and Democratic Memory; Workforce and Social Economy; Inclusion, National Insurance and Migrations; Territorial Politics and Public Roles; Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation; Health; Gender Equality and Universities.

In **Italy**, all the decision level bodies such as the Rectors of universities, presidents of the RPOs and RFOs, general directors, administrative boards, and Committees for equal opportunities (CUGs) and, in general, the decision bodies of the different organisations/universities, are responsible for advancing gender equality in the institutions of research and universities.

In **Poland**, gender equality policies are implemented only by some universities among the Research and HE institutions. Each of them adopts its own way of implementing the strategy and evaluating its progress. In Poland, according to

the law on higher education and science, the university's rector is responsible for the implementation of any strategy at the university. Below the monitoring system of the strategy adopted at the University of Gdansk is presented. In 2019, the University of Gdansk adopted a development strategy for 2020-2025¹⁶⁷ with specific detailed action plans. The implementation of gender equality at the University of Gdansk is one of them. The progress of the implementation of the actions is monitored through the use of so-called *strategic cards* containing: a description of the actions, identification of the entities responsible for their implementation, deadlines for their implementation and potential sources of funds necessary for their implementation. Measurable indicators have been assigned to each of the actions, allowing progress in the implementation of the objectives to be monitored and, as a result, the implementation of the Strategy of the University of Gdańsk to be evaluated. The Project Team is responsible for monitoring project implementation. Upon completion of the project, its results are to be approved by the Rector's College.

The gender equality issue will also be tackled under a dedicated project Modifying Institutions by Developing the Gender Equality Plans (MINDtheGEPs, **Poland**), which will result in an institutional action plan and the development of mechanisms leading to the promotion of gender equality in research and innovation¹⁶⁸.

In **Portugal**, the CIG is the national coordinating body responsible for promoting and defending ENIND, also with regard to gender equality in research and higher education, and is assisted by an ENIND Monitoring Committee and technical monitoring committees for each Action Plan. With regard to higher education and research and innovation, the ENIND Monitoring Committee is part of the Monitoring Committee: a representative of the Directorate-General for Higher Education (DGES); representative of the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT).

DGES as an important role as a promoter of the GE-HEI project, presented in July 2019 and still in progress, whose main objective is: "to develop knowledge, tools and methodologies to mainstream gender equality in the Portuguese HE system". The project is funded by the EEA Grants Portugal, implemented by CIEG (ISCSP). In November 2020, the preliminary results of the GE-HEI project were presented in a webinar. The project is based on two fundamental pillars: knowledge and citizenship.

FCT is the national public agency supporting research in science, technology and innovation and is under the tutelage of the Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education. FCT operates in all areas of knowledge and provides funding for gender equality research projects. FCT organises and promotes competitions for scientific research and technological development projects in the field of gender social relations and policies for equality between women and men in Portugal.

¹⁶⁷ University of Gdańsk, Strategia Uniwersytetu Gdańskiego na lata 2020 – 2025 (Development Strategy of University of Gdańsk for years 2020-2025), 2019. Available at: https://bip.ug.edu.pl/prawo_uniwersytetu/strategia_uniwersytetu_gdanskiego [01.05.2021]

¹⁶⁸ University of Gdansk, "Gender Equality in research and Innovation", Press release, 2020. Available at: https://ug.edu.pl/Informacja_prasowa/97869/rownosc_plci_w_badaniach_i_innowacjach_-_projekt_naukowy_na_uniwersytecie_gdanskim_w_ramach_programu_horyzont_2020 [27.04.2021]

In terms of the implementation of the strategic objective (4) of "promoting the equality of women and men in higher education and scientific and technological development" and in view of the intersectoriality of ENIND, the following ministries are co-responsible: Ministry of Science Technology and Higher Education (MCTES), which assumes as a priority the fight against sexual segregation of scientific career, professions and educational choices; Ministry of Education (Mec); Ministry of the Presidency and Administrative Modernization (MPMA), which oversees the Secretariat of State for Citizenship and Equality, and the Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security (MTSSS). Other entities are also involved, such as the Committee on Equality at Work and Employment (ISCED), higher education institutions and research centres.

In **Romania**, Research and Higher Education are two nested though separate sectors (in some regards, their governing strategies and the related institutional settings, their areas of activity and impact and their staff or objectives can overlap). For clarification reasons, it is preferable to treat them separately.

In research:

As for the national laws and policies that should encourage public research institutions to adopt gender equality measures, two aspects are to be underlined:

- a) On the one hand, the National Strategy for RDI, as the main public policy instrument governing research and innovation, makes reference to general objectives and principles aiming at contributing to the development of the research sector, such as competitiveness, increasing the international visibility of Romanian research, increasing the role of science in society, developing the entrepreneurship and the marketization of research and development results, focusing on specific societal concerns, aiming at excellence by internationalizing research, developing human resources in the field of RDI. However, gender equality or gender mainstreaming are not mentioned at all.
- b) On the other hand, Government Ordinance no. 137/2000 regulates the prevention and legal punishment of all forms of discrimination in education and in all areas of employment, occupation and other economic activities (and implicitly in the field of research and innovation).

In HEIs:

Unlike the Research sector, Higher Education in Romania is at the intersection between different public policy directions (i.e. related to graduate and post-graduate education, research, employment and work-life balance, etc.) that are supposed to integrate the transversal principle of gender equality and equal opportunities for women and men. Therefore, gender equality and the non-discrimination principle in higher education falls under either the umbrella of the legislation in force on gender equality and the related national bodies coordinated by the Ministry of Work, or under the legislation in force and the related institutions in the field of education and research.

According to Law 202/2002 (republished and updated; Articles 14 and 15 are related to education), the Ministry of Education is the main public institution that must promote, directly or indirectly, recommendations for university courses and curricula assessment related to the fight against gender discrimination and

gender stereotypes, as well as monitor, through subordinated institutions and higher education units, the implementation of equal opportunities principle between women and men in education at all levels (Art. 15). Moreover, the same Ministry has to provide appropriate training and instruction for teachers and professors in all forms of education, on the theme of equal opportunities for women and men.

Furthermore, the national law on education (**Law 1/2011**) stipulates all details related to the legal responsibility for the functioning and the organization of HE in Romania, as follows:

- Articles 216-221: the role of the public bodies/institutions that are, at the national level, involved in universities' organization, assessment and monitoring;
- Articles 213-215: regulate universities' administrative structure and hierarchy.

More precisely, university autonomy is the main principle that governs universities' organization and functioning in Romania. Therefore, the Ministry of Education can only make recommendations related to the implementation of gender equality principle in HEIs. However, the Ministry has different responsibilities related to national higher education policies and strategies as part of the European Higher Education Area. For instance, it must monitor and assess the organization and functioning of higher education, university research, financial management, university ethics and quality in higher education, according to the legislation in force (art. 216). Furthermore, the Ministry of Education relies on consultative bodies, at national level, such as: the National Council of Statistics and Prognosis of Higher Education (CNSPIS), the National Council for Attestation of University Degrees, Diplomas and Certificates (CNATDCU), the National Council for Scientific Research (CNCS), the Advisory Board for Research-Development and Innovation (CCCDI), the National Council for Financing Higher Education (CNFIS), National Council of Libraries University (CNBU), the Council of Ethics and University Management (CEMU) and the National Council of Ethics of Scientific Research, Technological Development and Innovation (CNECSDTI). According to art. 217, para. 1, "These bodies may include professors and researchers (...), members of the Romanian Academy and cultural institutions, as well as students (...), or representatives of the business environment in CCCDI or, as observers, in CNFIS."¹⁶⁹

Given the university autonomy principle, the legal responsibility for advancing gender equality in HEIs can only be taken at university level, considering the following:

According to art. 213, para. 1: the **university Senate** represents the highest decision and deliberation body at the university level; para. 2: its attributions are the following (selection): the Senate guarantees the academic freedom and the university autonomy; it elaborates and adopts the University Charter; it approves the strategic plan for institutional development and the operational plans, proposed by the Rector; it approves the structure, organization and functioning of the university; it approves the draft budget and implementation; it elaborates

¹⁶⁹ The Parliament of Romania, "Legea educației naționale nr. 1/2011" ("Law of national education no. 1/2011"), 9 February 2001. Available at https://www.edu.ro/sites/default/files/legea-educatiei_actualizata%20august%202018.pdf

and approves the Code for Quality and the University Code of Professional Ethics and Deontology; the Senate also adopts the University Code of students' rights and obligations; it also controls the activity of the Rector and of Directors' Board (Consiliul de Administratie). At the same time, according to the same art. 213, para. 6, **the Rector** is the university legal responsible and executive manager, leading the Board of Directors¹⁷⁰. However, it is relevant to remind us that only 3 female Rectors act in the 54 public universities in Romania.¹⁷¹

In Slovenia, the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport, with the assistance of an expert body, the Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science, supports promotional and other activities in the field of ensuring equal opportunities in science and follows the principle of balanced representation of both sexes in appointing working bodies.

In Slovakia, we miss a non-governmental body that would represent and network the R&I institution. In recent years, there have been some ambitions from the Slovak Academy of Sciences, which operates an honoured body, the Learned Society of Slovakia. The Learned Society of Slovakia declares to represent the country's scientific community, and one of the missions is to be a voice in ethical issues. In 2019, the Initiative – Vision for a knowledge society and better Slovakia was published by the Learned Society of Slovakia. This brief document primarily focuses on the importance of research for a knowledge society and aims to promote research field for young adults. The issue of GE is not mentioned, and the common masculine language is used in the document. On the other hand, the Slovak Academy of Sciences strategy, which is the biggest RPO in Slovakia, highlights the issue of GE, stating: “to support gender equality at every level of the management”.

- Specific bodies involved in the implementation of gender-related policies

At a regional level in **Spain**, the Government of each region delegates the responsibility to its regional Ministry of Education. Ex: The Regional Ministry of Education, Universities, Culture and Sports of the Canarian Government published on 15th October 2019 the Resolution N^o: 1592 / 2019, Volume: 1, Book: 583 in which it is specified how to design and implement gender equality action plans in public educational institutions¹⁷².

At organisational scale, each research institution is in charge of monitoring and evaluation the impact of gender equality policies through their respectively Gender Equality Units. Ex: the CSIC publish on 17th June 2020 their 4th evaluation of their 2nd equality action plan¹⁷³.

The national laws that encourage institutions of the public research sector to adopt gender equality measures are:

¹⁷⁰ *ibid.*

¹⁷¹ Iosip, Florinela, "Doar trei femei sunt rectori în cele 54 de universități de stat din România! Cifra e sub un sfert față de media UE, de 21%", *Libertatea*, 14 March 2019. Available at: <https://www.libertatea.ro/stiri/doar-trei-femei-sunt-rectori-in-cele-54-de-universitati-de-stat-din-romania-cifra-e-sub-un-sfert-fata-de-media-ue-de-21-2573250> [Accessed 6 May 2021]

¹⁷² The Regional Ministry of Education, Universities, Culture and Sports of the Canarian Government. Resolution N^o: 1592 / 2019. Accessed on 1st May 2021 and retrieved from <https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/educacion/web/programas-redes-educativas/programas-educativos/educa-igualdad/orientaciones-plan-de-igualdad/>

¹⁷³ Ministry of Science and Innovation. CSIC 4th Gender Equality Plan. Accessed on 1st May 2021 and retrieved from <https://www.csic.es/es/el-csic/ciencia-igualdad/igualdad-en-el-csic>

- Art. 14 y 9.2 of the Spanish Constitution 1978 (research performance organisations, universities, and research funding agencies).
- Constitutional Law 3/2007, 22nd March, for the effective equality of women and men (research performance organisations, universities, and research funding agencies).
- Royal Decree 259/2019, 12th April, that regulates Gender Equality Units in National Administrative Organisations (research performance organisations, universities, and research funding agencies).
- Royal Decree 431/2020, 3rd March, that established the basic structure of the Ministry of Universities (Universities).
- Law 14/2011, 1st June, for Science, Technology, and Innovation (research performance organisations, universities, and research funding agencies)
- National Strategy of Science, Technology, and Innovation 2013-2020 (research performance organisations, universities, and research funding agencies)

It is the responsibility of the Gender Equality Unit of each public research institution to put in place a gender action plan. Ex: The Gender Equality Unit of the Canarian Astrophysics Institute is in charge of implementing and overseeing the gender action plan.

In **Italy**, the Gender related legislative/policy measures implementation involves all the decision making bodies of the RPOs, RFOs and Universities. They can involve the Committees for equal opportunities (CUGs) of the different organisations.

In **Romania**, the Executive Unit for the Financing of Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation (UEFISCDI) is another important institution of the public sector that could be involved in the implementation of gender legislative and policy measures in public research/HE institutions. UEFISCDI is a public institution subordinated to the Ministry of Education. It functions as a research funding agency that manages approximately 22% of the public funds allocated to research, development and innovation. One of its main responsibilities is organising competitions and further monitoring the implementation of projects accepted for funding. In 2013, UEFISCDI was selected through competition to elaborate the National Strategy in Research, Development and Innovation 2014-2020.

Another specific body that can be involved in implementing gender-related policy measures is the Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ARACIS), whose mission is to carry out the external evaluation of the quality of education at the graduate level in Romania. All higher education programs in Romania have the obligation to respect ARACIS standards and methodologies. In Romania, there are norms, institutions and actors that can be involved in the implementation of the principle of gender equality, especially since the principle is present in the legislation in force. However, from the perspective of research and innovation, gender (in)equality is not identified as an important target/issue that needs to be addressed to develop the field. Instead, the low level of public funding and the absence of a clearly articulated political interest for RI are

considered to be among the main factors explaining the current underdeveloped state of the field. Moreover, another important problem in research is related to insufficient human resource, as insufficient funds imply the lack of attractiveness for research careers, complemented by the low correlation between university training/formation and the labour market requirements. Under these conditions, although it is mentioned in some of the strategic documents related to Research, Development and Innovation, the principle of gender equality is not being prioritised in any way.

As for higher education, the Ministry of Education can make recommendations regarding the implementation and the monitoring of gender equality in accordance with EU norms and regulations. However, considering the prevalence of the principle of university autonomy, the legal responsibility for implementing gender equality belongs, in fact, to each university (through the Rector and the Senate).

- Monitoring and assessment of the impact of the gender equality policies

In **Slovenia**, the only monitoring in the field of gender equality policy is performed on demand of the Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science, which assists the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport in collecting and analysing data for the effective formulation of equal opportunities policies in science. The Commission cooperates with the Public Agency for Research of the Republic of Slovenia to eliminate discriminatory provisions in obtaining funds for research work or in evaluating applicants who usually appeared in the case of maternity or maternity leave. The result of awareness of all parties about the importance of the equal role of women in science, including decision-making in science, was the adoption of the rules of the Public Agency for Research of the Republic of Slovenia, which determines the gender-balanced composition of permanent and occasional professional bodies. Awards are also an important segment of equality. Therefore, together with the Commission, the Ministry has made great efforts in recent years to make the awarding of state prizes and recognitions in science and technology more balanced. Unfortunately, even in this case, we often encounter a (too) small number of women among the proposed candidates and consequently among the winners. Among the most important activities of the commission is the organization of spring and autumn consultations, which promote discussion on possible causes and obstacles to a greater role of women in science, the wider issue of equal opportunities and the necessary structural changes to ensure equal opportunities in science.

In **Spain**, on a national scale, both the Ministry of Science and Innovation and the Ministry of Universities monitor and assess the impact of gender equality policies. Ex: The Ministry of Universities published on 8th November 2020 a memo with the statistics of gender inequalities at Spanish Universities, taking the data from all students enrolled at university during 2019/2020¹⁷⁴.

¹⁷⁴Ministry of Universities brief note. Accessed on 1st May 2021 and retrieved from https://www.universidades.gob.es/stfls/universidades/ministerio/ficheros/espacio_igualdad/cifras_enero_universidad_MG.pdf

In **Italy**, the MIUR asked the Universities, The RPOs and RFOs to periodically produce the gender budget document to provide a picture of the evolution of gender equality issues.

In **Slovakia**, the impact of gender equalities policies in academia and HEIS is neither properly monitored nor assessed. The Department of equality between women and men and equal opportunities annually prepares a report on GE, usually focusing on a selected issue every year. Yet, the issue of GE in R&I is neglected in these reports. Descriptive statistical data are available s (e.g. Gender equality report by the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic, data published by the Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information on RPOs¹⁷⁵), usually focusing on a proportion of women and men in the research field. These data are publicly available, but further assessment is not applied.

- Laws and policies encouraging to adopt gender equality measures and GEPs

In **Spain**, as per the Organic Law 4/2007 of universities and the Organic Law 14/2011 of science, all HEI and RPOs are obliged to have Equality Units and plans. In 2020, 94% of public universities, 70% of private universities and 75% of RPOs had a valid equality plan¹⁷⁶.

Nevertheless, the gender dimension is usually not taken into account in the accreditation of universities and their academic programmes. The main actor dedicated to such purpose is ANECA. Still, it does not contemplate the gender dimension in its evaluation, accreditation and certification schemes, even though gender and diversity are one of its guiding principles.

The situation is relatively similar at the regional level, with some variation depending on each autonomous community. However, the clear exception is Cataluña. The Agency for the Quality of the University System of Cataluña (AQU) does consider the gender dimension in its accreditation schemes for bachelor and master's degrees¹⁷⁷ and university centres¹⁷⁸. In the evaluation criteria of these schemes, the inclusion of the gender perspective in curricula or the existence of an Equality Unit with an implement and adequate plan is valued positively and can incur a negative evaluation if not present.

The **Italian** Political Authority directly in charge of gender equality and equal opportunities policies in Italy is the President of the Council of Ministers. In September 2014, the President appointed a specific "Gender Equality Advisor to the President of the Council of Ministers". The National Code of Equal Opportunities between Women and Men (approved with DL 198/2006) provides the legal framework for the development of gender equality at the national level. MIUR and CRUI defined guidelines related to Gender equality and related to the

¹⁷⁵ <https://www.vedatechnika.sk/SK/VedaATechnikaVSR/Stranky/StatistickeUkazovatele.aspx>

¹⁷⁶ Unidad de Mujeres y Ciencia "Científicas en Cifras", p. 94.

¹⁷⁷ Agència per a la Qualitat del Sistema Universitari de Catalunya, "Guía para la acreditación de las titulaciones oficiales de grado y máster", 2020. Available at: <https://www.aqu.cat/es/doc/guia-d-acreditacio-gm-2020-es> [15/05/2021].

¹⁷⁸ Agència per a la Qualitat del Sistema Universitari de Catalunya, "Estándares y Criterios para la Acreditación Institucional de Centros Universitarios", 2020. Available at: https://www.aqu.cat/es/doc/doc_44014506_1.pdf [15/05/2021].

definition of gender budgeting. Moreover, the Italian government is working on a national strategy on Gender equality.

There is no explicit national law or policy encouraging institutions of the public research sector to adopt gender equality measures in **Poland**.

In **Slovenia**, the Public Agency for Research of the Republic of Slovenia, which determined the gender-balanced composition of permanent and occasional professional bodies, does not anymore encourage institutions of the public research sector (research performance organisations, universities and research funding agencies) to adopt gender equality measures, including a gender action plan. **Rules on the Procedures of the (co)financing and Monitoring of Research Activities Implementation, Article 172i**¹⁷⁹ included the statement (according to the EIGE report¹⁸⁰) that “*all permanent and temporary bodies of the Slovenian Research Agency should be gender balanced. At least one third of each gender should be represented in science and at least one fifth of each gender in technical disciplines*”. In time of making the current report, the document does not include these statements.

In **Slovakia**, no national law or policy encourages institutions of the public research sector, i.e. research performance organisations, universities and research funding agencies, to adopt gender equality measures, including gender action plans. The only pressure currently stems from the European Union framework in research and innovation, namely programmes such as Horizon Europe, to comply with the requirement to have GEP active to get funding from the programme. Usually, if the adoption of gender equality measures is not legally binding and no sanction stems from the non-compliance, no action will be taken.

- Gender action plans in research in place

In **Poland**, there are not many initiatives to encourage academic institutions to make changes in order to promote gender equality. Two important initiatives indicated as good practices are the Gender Equality plan for the University of Warsaw and the Strategy for the University of Gdansk mentioned above. They aim to increase gender equality at both universities. In addition, in 2018, the Autonomia Foundation developed the Anti-Discrimination Standard for Universities¹⁸¹. This is a model document that every university can use to develop internal solutions, procedures and policies to counter discrimination and violence. It is the result of work carried out under the project *University Standards for Counteracting Violence and Discrimination (2014-2015)*, The Standard was used by, among others, the Silesian Medical University in Katowice, Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Pedagogical University in Krakow, University of Opole

¹⁷⁹ Pravilnik o postopkih (so)financiranja, ocenjevanja in spremljanju izvajanja raziskovalne dejavnosti (neuradno prečiščeno besedilo št. 1), (15.06.2012), (Rules on the Procedures of the (co)financing and Monitoring of Research Activities Implementation), <https://www.arrs.si/en/akti/prav-sof-ocen-sprem-razisk-dej-sept-11.asp>

¹⁸⁰ European Institute for Gender Equality, “Gender Equality in Academia and Research”, (2016) <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/legislative-policy-backgrounds/slovenia>

¹⁸¹ Autonomia Foundation, “Standard antydyskryminacyjny dla Uczelni” (Anti-discrimination standard for the University), 2018. Available at: <https://autonomia.org.pl/publikacje/standard-antydiskryminacyjny-dla-uczelni/> [18.04.2021]

In Poland, gender equality policies are implemented only by some universities. Each of them adopts its way of implementing the strategy and evaluating its progress. Below the monitoring system of the strategy adopted at the University of Gdansk is presented. In 2019, the University of Gdansk adopted a development strategy for 2020-2025¹⁸² with specific detailed action plans.

Out of the Athena project partners, **only the ULPGC implemented Equality Plan**. As a public administration entity and education agency, the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) accepted the creation of a gender equality unit, approved in the Governing Council on 21 July 2010. This unit is responsible for recognising and analysing gender inequality at the university and implementing actions to include a gender perspective. Since its conception, one of the main objectives of the Gender Equality Unit was the formulation of an Equality Plan. For this purpose, a Working Committee for the Creation of the Equality Plan was initiated on 2 February 2015, integrated by different institution members, and headed by Ángeles Mateo del Pino, who was the director of the Gender Equality Unit at the time.

The main focus of the Working Committee for the Creation of the Equality Plan was to design a number of indicators and their respective reference criteria for the diagnosis of the situation of gender equality at the ULPGC. As a starting point, some gender equality plans and policies from different Spanish institutions were taken into account¹⁸³.

Since the implementation of the First Equality Plan 2016-2019 of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, the most significant policies and measures for promotion of gender equality at the institution have been the following:

- Making official awareness-raising of gender equality measures for the whole university community. This includes courses and workshops on gender equality addressed to students, teaching and research staff, and administration and services staff.
- Enhancing educational offering on gender equality, thus incorporating gender studies in all the teaching and research carried out at the university.
- Standardising the use of a non-sexist language in all kind of documents related with the institution.
- Moving towards a more equal presence of men and women between the teaching and research staff and administration and staff services, as well as among students.
- Improving the institutional regulations and procedures in order to accomplish a more equal presence of men and women in committees and selection boards.
- Progressing towards a greater equal pay between the teaching and research staff and administration and staff services.
- Detecting, preventing, and addressing sexual harassment through the formulation of specific measures.

¹⁸² University of Gdańsk, Strategia Uniwersytetu Gdańskiego na lata 2020 – 2025 (Development Strategy of University of Gdańsk for years 2020-2025), 2019. Available at: https://bip.ug.edu.pl/prawo_uniwersytetu/strategia_uniwersytetu_gdanskiego [01.05.2021]

¹⁸³ The required information collected by the Committee showed some relevant statistical data which can be consulted at the Gender Equality Observatory hosted on the institutional website of the Gender Equality Unit (www.igualdad.ulpgc.es).

- Improving the implementation of gender perspective and gender equality in working schedules and shared workspaces.
- Adding to the institutional regulations the existing legislation on coordination of work and family and personal life.

Despite that **Slovakia** does not have any specific gender equality policies in research and academy, several Slovak HEIs adopted their own GE related strategic document in the framework of an EU funded project. Slovak University openly declared the adopted GE strategy and plan is the Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice from 2018. Trnava University participated in the GENOVATE project to implement GEP. However, the university does not promote, even does not publicly mention the GEP on its website.

Besides the ATHENA project, four institutions are currently involved in the Horizon 2020 projects, which aims to adopt GEP:

- Comenius University in Bratislava is implementing the project EQUAL4EUROPE - Gender Equality Standards for AHMSSBL institutions throughout Europe project.¹⁸⁴
- Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica is implementing the project GENDERACTION - GENDER equality in the ERA Community to innovate policy implementation.¹⁸⁵
- The Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava is implementing the CALIPER project: Linking research and innovation for gender equality.¹⁸⁶
- The University of Žilina is implementing the project Change - CHAlleNging Gender (In)Equality in science and research)¹⁸⁷;
- The youngest project is ATHENA - Implementing gender equality plans to unlock the research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe by the Slovak Academy of sciences.

3.5. Gender equality in graduate schools and post docs programmes

In the following section, we focus on integrating the gender dimension in the study programs, bodies responsible for the formulation of the graduate schools' curricula and if the gender equality dimension is integrated into the evaluation of the graduate schools.

- Ways of integration of a gender dimension in graduate schools and post-doc programmes

In **Spain**, the Ministry of Science and Innovation has a programme in which they aim to encourage women to pursue a career in science and research. Their programme consists of a series of podcasts about women in science, visual material such as infographics and events in which they celebrate women's work

¹⁸⁴ Equal4Europe | Gender equality

¹⁸⁵ GENDERACTION

¹⁸⁶ Project Vision – Caliper Project (caliper-project.eu)

¹⁸⁷ The Project | change h2020 (change-h2020.eu)

in science. In addition, they offer a series of educational resources that could be used in schools to encourage more women to be specialised in STEM in the future¹⁸⁸.

The creation of a master's degree in Gender Studies and the effort to train women and men in gender equality is another way in which the Ministries of Science and Innovation and Universities are trying to encourage the gender dimension in graduate schools and post-doc programmes¹⁸⁹.

In **Italy**, many universities are introducing specific courses and masters related to Gender equality in their teaching activities.

In **Poland**, there are no statutory provisions indicating the necessity of including gender dimension in the curricula of graduate schools and post-doc programmes.

In **Portugal**, the integration of equality policies between women and men focuses on diversity in scientific research teams, inclusive recruitment, training and communication processes, and the production of gender-sensitive knowledge that ensure better quality research with more significant impact. These are the essential characteristics that can be identified in Portuguese universities' projects and action plans that the Times Higher Education Impact Rankings elected. It should be noted that within the scope of Higher Education, the teaching offer of Portuguese HEIs includes some important courses of in-depth studies on gender issues and policies. We highlight the doctoral course on Gender Studies, and, by way of example, some master's and postgraduate courses, as shown in the links below.¹⁹⁰

In terms of degrees, gender issues are integrated into the study plans and in the curricula of course units.

In **Romania**, gender (in)equalities in graduate schools and Post docs are visible either through the lens of access to education, or through the lens of the extent to which gender is included (or not) in higher education institutions and curricula¹⁹¹.

For instance, the current National Strategy for Equal Opportunities reminds us that, in Romania, in the field of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) or Engineering, in 2017 only about 30% of the enrolled students were female. On the opposite side, over 70% of the female students were enrolled in the Sciences of Education, Social Sciences, Journalism and Information, Health and Social Assistance fields. At the same time, the share of women continuing

¹⁸⁸ Ministry of Science and Education webpage. Accessed on 1st May 2021 and retrieved from <https://www.ciencia.gov.es/portal/site/MICINN/menuitem.7e0ac5cd345b4f34f09dfd1001432ea0/?vgnnextoid=165a894e42204710VgnVCM1000001d04140aRCRD>

¹⁸⁹ Ministry of Science and Education webpage. Accessed on 1st May 2021 and retrieved from <https://www.ciencia.gov.es/portal/site/MICINN/menuitem.7e0ac5cd345b4f34f09dfd1001432ea0/?vgnnextoid=d4b3e6bd15304710VgnVCM1000001d04140aRCRD>

¹⁹⁰ UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA: <https://www.iscsp.ulisboa.pt/pt/cursos/oferta-graduada/doutoramentos/estudos-de-genero/plano-de-estudos>; <https://www.iscsp.ulisboa.pt/pt/cursos/oferta-graduada/mestrados/familia-e-genero>; <https://www.iscsp.ulisboa.pt/pt/cursos/formacao-avancada-e-especializada/pos-graduacoes/cursos/igualdade-de-genero>; <http://cieg.iscsp.ulisboa.pt/sobre-nos/ensino/pos-graduacao-em-igualdade-de-genero>; UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA: https://www.fcsh.unl.pt/cursos/mestrado_em_estudos_sobre_as_mulheres_as_mulheres_na_sociedade_e_na_cultura; UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA: <https://ces.uc.pt/pt/doutoramentos/programas-de-doutoramento/estudos-feministas>; UNIVERSIDADE ABERTA: <https://portal.uab.pt/mestrado-em-estudos-sobre-as-mulheres-genero-cidadania-e-desenvolvimento/>; INSTITUTO CRIAP: <https://www.institutocriap.com/formacao/especializacao-avancada-igualdade-genero>

¹⁹¹ Băluță, Ionela (2020), "Studiile de gen: un turnesol al democrației românești." ("Gender Studies: a Litmus for the Romanian Democracy") *Transilvania*, no. 11-12 (2020): 34-41. Available at: <https://revistatransilvania.ro/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Transilvania-11-12.2020.04-Ionela-Ba%CC%86lut%CC%A6a%CC%86.pdf> [accessed 30 April 2021]

their studies at the doctoral level generally decreases, if compared to the number of female students enrolled in MA programs, which suggests that less women than men decide to continue their studies at doctoral level, including in feminized fields of education.

As for the graduate schools' curricula, a recently published academic article reveals "the precarious degree of institutionalization of gender studies" in Romania.¹⁹² On the one hand, according to Law 202/2002, "Educational institutions at all levels (...) have to integrate within their educational programs themes and activities related to equal opportunities and treatment between women and men." (art. 14, al. 2) On the other hand, according to the current ARACIS standards, graduate programs in political science can include an optional discipline entitled "Gender and Politics/ Feminist Political Theories", and graduate programs in sociology can include an optional discipline in "Sociology of gender". Consequently, at least 4 Romanian universities have graduate programs in political science that offer courses on gender and politics, and at least 2 universities have graduate programs in sociology that offer courses on gender.¹⁹³ At the same time, that various courses include topics related to gender equality or gender studies, especially in the area of social sciences and humanities, although their visibility and impact are hard to assess.

Moreover, the current ARACIS standards provide instructions for the MA programs' curricula as well. ARACIS refers to professional, teaching and scientific research oriented post-graduate programs, without making specific instructions related to the areas of specialization that can include (or not) gender studies related courses. Therefore, at the national level, different MA programs can provide courses on gender or gender equality (according to courses' titles or descriptions), especially in the field of social sciences and humanities. Nevertheless, in Romania there are currently only 2 MA programs that offer specialization in gender studies: 4 such programs were created in Bucharest, Cluj and Timisoara, but only the 2 programs from the capital city are still in place ("Politici, gen și minorități" from SNSPA and "Politicile egalității de șanse în context românesc și European" from UB).

The Romanian project partners provided valuable comments on how gender could be included in the curricula. Unlike the graduate level, which is evaluated through the lens of a concrete list of "fundamental" and "optional" courses (the list includes gender studies in political science and sociology), the national evaluation standards for the doctoral and for the masters' degree do not refer to curricula's content at these levels. Therefore, the introduction of mandatory gender courses at MA level, at least in social sciences and humanities, would certainly contribute to reinforcing the institutionalisation of gender studies in Romania. ARACIS evaluation standards seem to be the key tool in this regard, as the university curricula, at all levels, has to integrate these standards¹⁹⁴.

Bulgaria provided an example of an extraordinary course of Gender rhetoric that inextricably linked to the humanities curricula at leading Bulgarian universities,

¹⁹² Băluță 2020

¹⁹³ Băluță 2020

¹⁹⁴ ARACIS, Standarde specifice privind evaluarea externă a calității academice a programelor de studii din domeniile de licență și master 2020 (Specific standards for the external evaluation of the academic quality of bachelor's and master's degree program 2020). Retrieved from: https://www.aracis.ro/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/C4-Standarde-_30.07.-2020-2.pdf

which are in the top 10 of Bulgarian higher education. A strong impetus to the rhetoric of the social sex in doctoral programs is made by Carlin Kors Campbell's book "Rhetoric of Women's Liberation: An Oxymoron" 1973. At Sofia University "Kliment Ohridski", at the New Bulgarian University, SWU, University of Ruse "A. Kanchev" (URAK) the rhetorical perception of feminist ideas is modelled by the prevailing ideas in rhetorical theory and criticism: the dominance of the individual over the collective; of the rational over the emotional; of the public over the private. With the development of society and the influence of social theories, literary feminism, discursive theory, postmodernism, poststructuralism and deconstructivism, conditions are created for the challenges of the feminist movement.

Gender Rhetoric programs for PhD students and postdoctoral students in the field of Higher Education in Social Economics and Law require PhD candidates to know the most influential feminist theories and to be able to reveal the role of rhetorical research in their implementation. The main topics are related to the unification of feminist and rhetorical theories in order to effect the movement for gender equality. Doctoral students are given the opportunity to answer the theoretical question, as well as to make a rhetorical analysis of videos with performances of prominent researchers of "Gender", politicians, journalists and others. Examples of topics for a doctoral minimum in Gender Rhetoric are¹⁹⁵:

The programme has the following structure: (A) Gender research, mass culture and ideology; (B) Gender representation; (C) Rhetoric and semiotics of advertising text; (D) Fragmentation and heterogeneity of the female audience; (E) Gender research and feminist critique; (F) Ancient interpretation of gender relations; (G) Anti-gender rhetoric in the Middle Ages; (H) Women's participation in governance.

In **Slovenia**, gender studies are organised as the third level Doctoral program (4 years) at the University in Ljubljana, Faculty of Social Sciences.

- Responsibility for the formulation of graduate schools' curricula

Bulgarian universities are autonomous in building their curricula. Only for the regulated professions in the Areas of Higher Education - Law and Medicine, they have state regulation and obligatory basic disciplines. This determines in the other areas of study, the introduction of basic disciplines, which in their hours make up 25% of the total number of hours and credits. The other disciplines fall into the categories of compulsory (specialized) - 50% and the last 25% - compulsory-elective and optional. The role of the Ministry of Education and Science in Bulgaria is to carry out periodic national accreditation of universities (5 years) through its National Agency for Evaluation and Accreditation (HAEA) and to give a 10-point grading system to universities (respectively general and professional areas). For the received grades between 9 and 10 Universities, the right to study and prepare new specialties is 6 years.

¹⁹⁵ Developed by Prof. Donka Alexandrova, DcS

In **Spain**, the Ministry of Education regulates and formulates postgraduate school's curricula, specifying the number of credits and competences needed to access and obtain a master's degree or a PhD. This is regulated by the Royal Decree 43/2015, 2nd February that stipulates the ordinance for official university studies. Also, by the Royal Decree 99/2011, 28th January that regulates official PhD Studies.

In **Italy**, the school curricula and courses are accredited by the MIUR.

In **Poland**, the Minister responsible for higher education and science, based on legal provisions, authorises graduate schools to provide specific fields of study. Within this framework, curricula are established. By means of ordinances, educational standards for individual fields of study are defined¹⁹⁶. In accordance with the principle of autonomy of graduate schools, curricula are developed by a committee appointed for this purpose, then submitted to the Faculty Council for an opinion, after which the Academic Senate approves them. The law, however, regulates the general requirements for these programmes.

Slovakia does not have any comprehensive national strategy or plan to integrate a gender dimension in graduate schools and post-doc programmes encouraged in Slovakia. However, the RPO and HEIs are independent legal entities with relatively high competencies in developing their study programmes and graduate schools' curricula. Based on the Act on High Schools, the creation and implementation of study programs, and determining the focus and organising research, development or artistic and other creative activities belong to the scope of the self-governing competencies of public high education institutions.¹⁹⁷

In **Slovenia**, Course Sociology of Gender and Sexuality (with 10 ECTS) deals with the study of different theoretical approaches to the study of gender and sexuality. It will include the following thematic blocks: emotions, love, contemporary love and/or partner relationships, gender, sexuality and reproduction; attitude towards sexuality (sexuality and pleasure, sexuality and pornography, sexuality and prostitution); different sexual orientation, attitude towards homosexuality throughout history and nowadays, youngsters and sexuality

- Responsibility for quality-control of graduate school curricula

Higher education institutions in **Bulgaria**, which have received after a successful accreditation procedure performed by NAEA, the right to study doctoral students and postdoctoral students draw up their plans and curricula, which are adopted by the relevant faculty councils and the Academic Council of the University. They are subject to annual internal control and certification by the Directorate "Quality of Higher Education and Continuing Education."

¹⁹⁶ Ministry of Science and Higher Education, Rozporządzenie Ministra Nauki i Szkolnictwa Wyższego dnia 12 lipca 2007 w sprawie standardów kształcenia dla poszczególnych kierunków oraz poziomów kształcenia, a także trybu worzona warunków jakie musi spełnić uczelnia, by prowadzić studia międzykierunkowe oraz makrokierunki, Dz.U.2007.64.1166. Retrieved from: <https://sip.lex.pl/akty-prawne/dzu-dziennik-ustaw/standardy-ksztalcenia-dla-poszczegolnych-kierunkow-oraz-poziomow-17378070>

¹⁹⁷ Act no. 131/2002 Cal.

In **Spain**, the National Agency of Quality Evaluation and Accreditation (ANECA) is in charge of evaluating and accrediting the quality of the curricula of postgraduate studies. It is an autonomous institution, but it is assigned to the Ministry of Science and Innovation, and the Ministry of Universities. It was created in 2014, in the art. 8 of the Law 15/2014, 16th September. Its Mission Statement was approved in the Royal Decree 1112/2015, 11th December, and the agency is regulated by the following:

- Royal Decree 1614/2009, 26th October, that stipulates the ordinance for official artistic studies regulated by the Constitutional Law 2/2006, 3rd May of education.
- Royal Decree 43/2015, 2nd February, that stipulates the ordinance for official university studies.
- Royal Decree 99/2011, 28th January, that regulates official PhD Studies.

The **Italian** National Agency for the evaluation of universities and research institutes (ANVUR), periodically assesses the curricula and courses quality, accrediting them periodically.

In **Poland**, the quality of education at universities should be taken into account in two ways. Firstly, the authorities at each university establish their own quality assurance systems based on internal regulations. Secondly, the quality of education is assessed by an independent institution, the Polish Accreditation Committee.

In **Portugal**, the mechanisms for the national evaluation of Higher Education quality and accreditation are established by the Agency for Assessment and Accreditation of High Education (A3ES). This agency is a private law foundation whose goal is to assure the quality of High Education in Portugal, through the evaluation and accreditation of HEI and their study cycles. The evaluation process consists in the analysis of a self-assessment report of the study cycle produced by the institution and submitted to the agency, plus a visit of the evaluation panel. After these two phases, an evaluation report is produced. Only the study cycles that are accredited can run. Nowadays, none of these mechanisms of the A3ES considers gender and diversity as criteria of evaluation and/or accreditation of the HEI and their study cycles.

The **Slovenian** Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education is responsible for quality-control of graduate school curricula. The Slovenian Quality Assurance Agency (SQAA) provides for development and operation of the quality assurance system in the Slovenian higher education area. Since 2015, SQAA has been a full member of the European Quality Assurance Association for Higher Education ENQA. The tasks are associated with the accreditation of study programmes and higher education institutions. It is an independent professional body composed of experts in the field of higher education. Besides assuring quality in the study process, the granting of accreditations promoted the development of the culture of quality and the creation of regulatory frameworks subject to European development guidelines.

The newly re-established **Slovak Accreditation Agency** for Higher Education is responsible for the quality control of the graduate school curricula. The Slovak Accreditation Agency for Higher Education is a public institution whose task is to perform external quality assurance activities in higher education in the Slovak Republic. It was established by Act no. 269/2018 Coll. (the Quality Act) as a legal entity.¹⁹⁸ The Agency's mission is to improve higher education quality through modern tools following the European Standards for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ESG 2015). The evaluation is based on Standards for the Higher Education Internal Quality Assurance System. The standards for the Internal system, for Study programs or Habilitation and Inauguration Proceedings, do not refer to any gender equality aspect.¹⁹⁹ However, in the methodology of evaluation, several criteria for the Internal System evaluation refer to anti-discrimination aspects:

- The policies, structures, and processes of the internal system ensure protection against any forms of intolerance and discrimination against students, staff and applicants;
- The policies, structures, and processes of the internal system ensure consistency and compliance with generally binding regulations and with internal rules of the institution
- The policies, structures, and processes of the internal system ensure that the conditions of the admission procedure are inclusive and that equal opportunities are guaranteed to all applicants who demonstrate eligibility for the study.²⁰⁰

In **Romania**, according to the national education law (Law 1/2011), "based on CNCS reports on the quality of research and CNATDCU reports on the quality of human resources, doctoral schools are under the recurrent evaluation of ARACIS. The criteria and the evaluation methodology are established by order of the Minister of Education and Research²⁰¹, starting from the joint proposals of ARACIS, CNCS and CNATDCU. Each doctoral school is evaluated periodically, every five years." However, the principle of gender equality is not included within the criteria, reference standards and performing indicators that are being used as a reference within the accreditation process and periodic evaluation of doctoral schools.

3.6. Recruitment and career development

- Gender-aware recruitment policies in institutions of the public research

In **Bulgaria**, recruitment policies in public research institutions do not take gender into account as a criterion for recruitment. The competition starts with professional characteristics follows.

¹⁹⁸ <https://saavs.sk/agency/mission-of-the-agency/>

¹⁹⁹ <https://saavs.sk/standards/>

²⁰⁰ <https://saavs.sk/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Methodology-for-the-Evaluation-of-Standards.pdf>

²⁰¹ Ministry of Education (2016), "Metodologia pentru autorizarea, acreditarea si evaluarea periodica a scolilor doctorale" (Methodology for authorization, accreditation and periodic evaluation of doctoral schools). Retrieved from: https://www.edu.ro/sites/default/files/OMENCS%206.153_2016%20evaluare%20scoli%20doctorale.pdf.

In **Spain**, the recruitment policies in institutions of the public research sector are gender-aware. These are established in the Preface III of the Law 9/2017, 8th November, regarding the Work Contracts in the Public Sector, that integrates the Directives of the European Parliament and the Ministry 2014/23/UE and 2014/24/UE, 26th February 2014, in the Spanish legal ordinance. Also, in Chapter I art. 4.1 section i) of the Legislative Royal Decree 5/2015, 30th October, that approves the amendments of the Civil Servants Legal Status Act, establishing the non-discrimination in the hiring process of civil servants and their rights.

In addition, the Law 14/2011, 1st June, of Science, Technology and Innovation of the Ministry of Science and Innovation established in art. 14.1 section d) that gender equality is a right of the workers when carrying out their duties. The same right is specified in art 28.1 section c) that regulates the duty for technical workers in public administrations and public research institutions. Moreover, in Chapter I art 33.1 section j), it is established the necessity of a gender perspective in science, technology, and innovation to obtain the balance of women and men in all the Spanish System of Science, Technology, and Technology Areas Innovation.

In **Italy**, recruitment policies in the public research sector institutions are general, and there are not specific issues related to gender. The only rule followed is related to the composition of the selection board that has to have at least one-third of its members of women or men.

In **Poland**, there is no specific gender-sensitive recruitment policy applied in institutions of the public research sector apart from isolated solutions adopted by some universities, for example, the University of Warsaw²⁰² and the University of Gdansk²⁰³.

As there is no such policy in Poland, it is impossible to determine who would be responsible for its implementation and supervision. It seems, however, that the Rector of the University, jointly with the Minister responsible for higher education and science would be the appropriate bodies. The rules for the promotion of academic staff are enshrined in the law²⁰⁴, in specific ordinances and in the statutes of universities. In turn, the rules prohibiting discrimination are enshrined in the Labour Code and the Anti-discrimination Act. According to the law, the Rector of the University or the director of the institution (in the case of scientific institutions) is responsible for compliance with the law at the institution s/he is leading.

In **Portugal**, FCT created the "Scientific Employment Stimulus" competition. The competition aims to be "an incentive to hire new researchers and develop scientific employment plans and scientific careers by public or private

²⁰² University of Warsaw, Zarządzenie nr 194 Rektora Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego z dnia 27 sierpnia 2020 r. w sprawie „Planu równości płci dla Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego oraz planu działań równościowych na lata 2020-2023” (Decree No. 194 of the Rector of the University of Warsaw of 27 August 2020 on the "Gender equality plan for the University of Warsaw and the equality action plan for 2020-2023). 2020, Available at:

<https://monitor.uw.edu.pl/Lists/Uchway/Attachments/5574/M.2020.371.Zarz.194.pdf> [30.04.2021]

²⁰³ University of Gdansk, "Strategia Uniwersytetu Gdańskiego na lata 2020 – 2023" (Strategy of the University of Gdańsk for the years 2020 – 2023), 2019. Available at: https://bip.ug.edu.pl/sites/default/files/nodes/akty_normatywne/92705/files/zalu155u19_strategia_ug_20-25.pdf

²⁰⁴ Ustawa z dnia 20 lipca 2018 r. Prawo szkolnictwie wyższym i nauce, Dz. U. 2018. Poz. 1668, <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20180001668/U/D20181668Lj.pdf>

institutions". In 2021, the 4th edition of the competition was held, and 305 employment contracts were approved for doctoral researchers.

According to EURAXESS, a researcher support platform set up by the European Commission, Portugal is part of the group of countries that signed the agreement provided for in the Charter and the Investigator's Code. On the EURAXESS website, we find registered several Portuguese institutions and associations, among which we point out the following: Association of Scientific Research Fellows (ABIC); National Association of Researchers in Science and Technology (ANICT); Faculty of Science of University of Lisbon (FCUL); National Institute of Health Dr. Ricardo Jorge; NOVA University of Lisbon; University of Aveiro; University of Beira Interior (UBI); University of Coimbra; University of Minho; and, University of Porto.

In Portugal, many recruitment policies applied to the gender issue were not implemented.²⁰⁵

Recruitment and career development **in Romanian universities** and other academic & research organisations are per the legislation and policies in force at the national level (related to work and employment, equal opportunities and non-discrimination, etc.). Yet, they are not gender-equality oriented (there are no affirmative incentives for promoting women in higher education or in research and innovation)²⁰⁶.

Recruitment and career development for any academic position have to respect the national standards validated by the CNATDCU commission of the Ministry of National Education (these standards are first and foremost oriented towards impact and visibility in research through publications, international research projects, etc.). More importantly, they are being organised at the level of each HERI institution, depending on specific needs, availabilities and organizational charts.

At the same time, it is important to mention that any academic position has to be included in a certain field of specialisation (in exact sciences, social sciences, humanities, etc.), and gender studies are not being mentioned within the list of classically consecrated disciplines in humanities and social sciences, such as sociology or political sciences, etc. Therefore, the expertise in gender studies is considered to be an extra/ or a complementary specialisation without allowing the configuration of specific academic positions.

In **Slovenia**, the recruitment policies in institutions of the public research sector are no gender-aware. The Public Agency for Research of the Republic of Slovenia would be responsible for it. There is no legal entity having the right and responsibility to define promotion requirements and procedures that are gender-aware in institutions of the research sector and academia. Gender equality is not integrated into the national legal/ policy framework on research careers because there are no differences regarding sex.

²⁰⁵ On the lack of compliance with recruitment policies that include gender equality, check the article published by the Público newspaper on 02/25/2021: "Foundation for Science and Technology tramples on the rights of women scientists".

<https://www.publico.pt/2021/02/25/ciencia/noticia/fundacao-ciencia-tecnologia-atropela-direitos-mulheres-cientistas-1951893>

²⁰⁶ Consiliului Național de Atestare a Titlurilor, Diplomelor și Certificatelor Universitare (2012), "Criterii Abilitare" (Abilitation Criteria). Retrieved from: <http://www.cnatdcu.ro/criterii/abilitare/>

In **Slovakia**, although the issue of GE in research careers is partially reflected in the national GE strategy, there is no policy specifically focused on GE in recruitment and career development in R&D. Universities usually have directives on recruitment and career development, which declares that the process guarantees equal opportunities and no discrimination based on sex, marital status, age, religion, race or ethnic group, or national or social status.²⁰⁷ The recruitment process must be public, and a committee makes the decision. Other RPOs are independent institutions often in the private sector and may have, but probably do not have, any particular recommendations or policies in this area. The language of the public research and academic institutions is sexist, making women invisible. For example, in a new position announcement or documents and websites, gender sensitive language is rarely used. Mainly only male forms of words are used despite that the Slovak language also allows female forms. Thus, the area of science and academy appears thus as a “men’s world” without inclusively inviting women to do science or teaching at university.²⁰⁸

- Ministries and institutions responsible and involved in the gender-aware recruitment

In **Bulgaria**, no such institution due to non-consideration of this criterion exists. However, in terms of responsibility, the Commission for Protection against Discrimination (CPD) controls and monitors violations against gender equality in research. It is a Bulgarian national independent specialized state quasi-judicial body for prevention of discrimination, protection against discrimination and implementation of the state policy in the field of equal opportunities and equal treatment of all citizens on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria.

In **Spain**, the Ministry of Science and Innovation and the Presidential Ministry would be involved in this process of ensuring gender-aware recruitment policies. Also, the Gender Equality Units have the right and responsibility of raising awareness about gender inequalities in research institutions and universities. In the 13th additional provision of Law 14/2011, 1st June, of Science, Technology and Innovation of the Ministry of Science and Innovation is established a non-discrimination policy during the hiring process of workers in public research institutions when giving scholarships and grants. In addition, it specifies the implementation of mechanisms to eliminate gender inequalities, promotes Gender Studies and encourages women to take up a career in research.

In **Italy**, the Ministry for public administration, Ministry for university and scientific research, Department for equal opportunities of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers of Italy are responsible bodies in gender-aware recruitment.

In **Portugal**, MCTES is the entity responsible for recruitment and career progression policy relating to research and higher education, but gender-aware

²⁰⁷ See e.g. https://www.truni.sk/sites/default/files/rektor/zasady_vyberoveho_konania_2008_2.pdf
https://www.ucm.sk/docs/legislativa/zasady_vyberoveho_konania_na_obsadzovanie_pracovnych_miest_vysokoskolskych_ucitelov.pdf
https://www.uniza.sk/images/pdf/uradna-tabula/smernice-predpisy/S-158_2017-Zsady-vberovho-konania_10102017.pdf

²⁰⁸ E.g. https://www.cvtsir.sk/o-cvti-sr/volne-pracovne-miesta.html?page_id=9142 , <https://uniba.sk/o-univerzite/uradna-vyveska/vyberove-konania-na-miesta-akademickych-pracovnikov/>

policies are not applied. There is also no integration of gender equality into the political and legal structure of scientific careers.

- The right and responsibility to define promotion requirements and gender-aware procedures

The Academic Council proposes to the General Assembly of the University/Institute of the **Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (BAS)**, as the main legislative body to adopt Rules of Procedure of the respective institution, in which to define rights and responsibilities, as well as requirements and procedures for promotion, which are in line with gender equality in research institutions and academia.

In **Italy**, MIUR, RPOs, RFOs, and universities with their decisional bodies and CUGs have the right and the responsibilities to define gender-aware promotion requirements and procedures.

In **Portugal**, in Council of Ministers Resolution no. 61/2018, we find the National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination 2018-2030 promulgated.

To make the strategic plan viable, Portugal participates as a collaborating country in the main international mechanisms, such as the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women and the Council of Europe Convention on Prevention and Combat to Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (Istanbul Convention).

With regard to the field of Research and Innovation, the National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination establishes as one of its four central axes the “equal, inclusive and future-oriented scientific and technological development”.

Regarding the implementation of the national strategy for equality, the Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality (CIG) is the national body responsible for promoting and defending this principle.

- Gender equality integrated into the national legal/ policy framework on research careers

In **Italy**, there is the crucial request of having gender budgeting in the Universities and Research institutions, which enables a picture about the evolution of the situation of the different positions of professors and researchers per gender. An effort is necessary for improving the national legal and policy framework.

Bulgarian project partners are aware of the gender prejudice about career development and provided the following information. At the beginning of the third decade of the 21st century in Bulgaria, women and men have equal political and legal rights, but gender inequality, incl. in research, it is still a very topical issue because society continues to operate with persistent social stereotypes about the role of men and women in the family and works with prejudices about women's career development. Despite the centuries-old struggle of women for gender

equality, horizontal and vertical gender segregation (the so-called "glass ceiling") still exists²⁰⁹.

- National policy supporting the re-entry of the academic workforce into research careers

An example of how the national policy supports the re-entry of the academic workforce into research careers in **Spain** is as follows. The Ministry of Finance and Public Services has passed on 29th December 2020 the 3rd Gender Equality Action Plan for the National Administration Organisations and all dependant institutions, in which university and public research organisations are included.

There is no specific programme to support the re-entry of the academic workforce into research careers in **Poland**. One can only point to the facilitations for parents after maternity and paternity leave contained in the law on higher education and science. According to it, it is possible in such a situation to suspend studying in doctoral school, i.e. the doctoral student does not suffer the consequences of delays caused by such leave. It is also a period that does not count towards the periodic evaluation of an academic staff member.

In **Slovenia**, the re-entry of the academic workforce into research careers is not gender biased.

In **Slovakia**, the re-entry of the academic workforce, e.g. after maternity leave, is partially supported by a national policy. According to the Labour Act, the employee is responsible for keeping the working position for women and men after the maternal/parental leave. However, this may not always be so straightforward as a permanent working contract conditions this duty. Young adults usually receive a fixed-term working contract, often related to the project funding at the beginning of their research career. By the time they leave to take care of a child, they may not have a right to the permanent working contract, which guarantees the position after the maternal/paternal leave. We did not find any particular policy or measure at the level of RFO, RPO or HEIs to go beyond the national legislation mentioned above.

In **Portugal**, the National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination 2018-2030 «Portugal + Igual», was approved by the XXI Constitutional Government on March 8, 2018 and is published in Diário da República (Council of Ministers Resolution no. 61/2018, of May 21).

- Application of the European Charter for Researchers and a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers²¹⁰

In **Spain**, the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers is implemented in all research institutions assigned

²⁰⁹ PDF, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339712525_Ravenstvoto_na_polovete_-_evolucia_i_aktualni_problemi_Gender_equality_-_evolution_and_current_issues [accessed Jun 14 2021].

²¹⁰ <http://ec.europa.eu/euraxess/index.cfm/rights/whatIsAResearcher>

to the Ministry of Science and Innovation and the Ministry of Universities and are regulated by the Resolution of the Ministry of Universities of 16th September 2008, which includes the recommendations of the European Commission, 11th March 2005, regarding the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers.

In **Italy**, this code has been formally adopted by the public RPOs and RFOs and the Italian universities. The different institutions defined internal procedures for its application in recruitment processes.

In **Poland**, the European Charter for Researchers and a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers is popular in the public research sector in Poland. By May 2021, 91 centres, research institutes, higher education institutions have received the HR Excellence in Research award in Poland and decided to meet requirements set by the e "Charter & Code"²¹¹. The analysis of their documents describing the activities undertaken in the framework of the "Charter & Code" shows that most of them focus only on the introduction of general anti-discrimination measures, such as conducting training, publishing guides or leaflets. Less popular are hard measures around promotion of gender equality, among which the following are proposed: the establishment of a gender equality body, the introduction of gender equality in recruitment, gender equality training, the creation of facilities for breastfeeding and rest for pregnant women. Only a few institutions declared the willingness to create and implement a Gender Equality Plan.

In **Portugal**, according to the Association of Scientific Research Fellows - ABIC, such measures do not exist, since the guidelines of the European Charter of researchers have not yet been implemented. In May 2019, ABIC's board filed a complaint with the Ombudsman claiming: "compliance with the European Charter & Code and Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) award in Portuguese institutions".²¹²

In terms of applying the European Charter for Research and a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Research in **Slovakia**, we found the following information.

- In 2005, the Slovak Rectors' Conference members declared the commitment of Slovak universities to accept the principles of the Statements on the commitment of the rectors of Slovak universities to accept the principles European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers.²¹³
- The Slovak University of Technology in Slovakia is committed to applying to both documents and undertaking and analyses their compliance and anchoring in the Slovak national legislation and University regulations. They propose tools for implementing all the principle of the Charter and Code of Conduct; e.g. to fully implement the principle of non-discrimination a research study on the topic of comparison and evaluation of the

²¹¹ Euraxess, <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/hrs4r/awarded>

²¹² ABIC's claims and the Ombudsman's responses can be found at: <https://abic-online.org/noticia/resposta-da-provedoria-de-justica-a-queixa-abic-sobre-o-regime-de-dedicacao-exclusiva-do-ebi/>

²¹³ <https://www.upjs.sk/aktuality/2006/europska-charta-a-kodex-spravania/>

remuneration of women and men in the position researchers at the university, resp. at universities in the Slovak Republic in generality is needed.²¹⁴

- The Comenius University adopted the Charter and the Code of Conduct in April 2021 and is committed to implementing the principles in its Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R).²¹⁵

The rules on obtaining scientific or academic degrees are given in specific Decrees of the Ministry of Education of the Slovak Republic on the procedure for obtaining scientific-pedagogical titles or artistic-pedagogical titles. The rules and criteria are the same for both genders and do not reflect any specific circumstances for vulnerable groups. The universities can adopt further internal criteria for obtaining the academic title.²¹⁶

The European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers is applied in **Bulgaria**, in those universities and institutes of BAS, which apply for public funding for national and international research projects and programs, in which such a condition is mandatory. For the programming period 2020-27, 13 research institutions in Bulgaria are included in the National Roadmap for Research, which is an integral part of the European Research Map.

In **Romania**, as regards the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers, these documents have been endorsed so far by 15 Romanian universities and research organisations (out of at least 53 public universities at national level; the University of Bucharest is not among them)²¹⁷.

3.7. Working conditions and environment

- Measures in place that trace gender pay gaps

In **Spain**, gender pay gaps in research and universities are still present, as reports like SHE Figures and research such as that of Jabbaz, Samper-Gras and Díaz (2019)²¹⁸ show. The fact that salaries are equal *a priori* and published in the Official State Gazette (BOE) perpetuates the notion that there is no gender gap in the public research sector, especially since other factors like career advancement or family and work-life balance are often not taken into account. This is the reason why the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA), the Conference of Spanish University Rectors (CRUE) and the Ministry of Universities have started a study²¹⁹ to determine and assess the reality of salaries of the research and teaching staff from a gender perspective

²¹⁴ https://www.stuba.sk/buxus/docs/stu/informacie_o/stu/organy_akademicke_samospravne/zasadnutia_vedenie/15_priloha1_GAP_analyza_2019-12-16.pdf

²¹⁵ <https://uniba.sk/veda/hrs4r/>

²¹⁶ https://uniba.sk/fileadmin/ruk/veda/Legislativa/vp_2014_3.pdf

²¹⁷ European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. Retrieved from:

https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter/declaration-endorsement#show_Romania

²¹⁸ Jabbaz, Marcela, Samper-Gras, Teresa y Díaz, Capitolina, (2019). "La brecha salarial de género en las instituciones científicas. Estudio de caso".

Convergencia, 26 (80), 2019, pp. 1-27. DOI: 10.29101/crcs.v26i80.11248.

²¹⁹ ANECA press release. Accessed in 29/04/2021 and retrieved from <http://www.aneca.es/Sala-de-prensa/Noticias/2021/ANECA-lidera-la-puesta-en-marcha-con-perspectiva-de-genero-sobre-las-retribuciones-del-personal-docente-e-investigador>

in Spanish universities. The study's initial conclusions will be published after the first semester of 2021.

In **Italy**, UGs in the RPOs, RFOs and universities are the bodies that can receive any information if there are not appropriate behaviours that produce gender pay gaps. Gender balance, Gender Equality Plans can facilitate the data collection in each organisation.

In **Romania** there are no publicly available surveys or reports on the general issue of equal pay and equal treatment at work for women and men, or the specific problem of gender pay gap in the field of HERI. Despite the fact that the current National strategy on equal opportunities for women and men, for which ANES is responsible, has several objectives in equal pay between women and men, de facto it is challenging to assess this concern at the national level. On the one hand, the national legislation is in accordance with the principle of equal pay for work of equal value. On the other hand, the Labour Code in force imposes confidentiality (art. 163, al 1) and it also stipulates that the individual salary results from individual direct negotiations between the employer and the employee (art. 162). This can explain why "The measures set out by the European Commission's Recommendation of 7 March 2014 on strengthening the principle of equal pay between men and women through transparency have not been implemented in Romania." (p. 28). Moreover, although the current legislation in force provides special measures for the protection of maternity, birth, postnatal care, breastfeeding, and child-rearing, no positive actions measures aim to ensure full equality in practice between men and women in Romania life. The field of HERI makes no exception from this general context.

In **Poland and Slovenia**, no measures are in place that trace existing gender pay gaps in institutions of the public research sector. **Slovakia** does not have any specific measures targeting existing gender pay gaps in public RPOs or HEIs. The absence of any effort also stems from the fact that the data and awareness on gender gaps in public research and academic institutions are lacking. The gender pay gap for all university and higher education teachers was 6,5%, and research and development managers in public and private RPOs was 18% to the detriment of women.²²⁰ Slovakia did not adopt any pay transparency policies recommended by the European Commission in any economic sector, so the visibility of the gender pay gaps in research and higher education institutions is very low. Even the annual reports on the respective institutions rarely contain information on the gross wages for all employees or researchers. The women/men disaggregation is not available.

In **Bulgaria**, investing in formal care and appropriate family leave for both women and men contributes to reducing the pay gap between women and men, as it leads to fewer career breaks and employment for women. Flexible work schemes (including flexible working hours, reduced working hours and teleworking) are well used by both women and men and should not be seen as a cost for

²²⁰ Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic, Gender Equality in Slovakia 2020

employers, who often tend to penalize their employees in the form of a reduction in pay. Moreover, a number of initiatives have successfully promoted the inclusion of women in male-dominated sectors, such as science and technology. In almost all sectors, men are promoted much more often to supervisory or management positions, while women who have reached the highest position of CEO are less than 5%. "Vertical" segregation accounts for a significant share of the gender pay gap.²²¹

In **Portugal** there are no measures in place to track the existing gender pay gap in public sector research institutions. According to ABIC - Association of Scientific Research Fellows, such measures do not exist, since the guidelines of the European Charter for Researchers have not yet been implemented by the Portuguese government.

- Actors in negotiating researchers' remuneration

There are two main actors involved in the negotiation of researchers' remuneration in **Spain**: the administration, represented by the Ministry of Science and Innovation and the Ministry of Universities, and the trade unions. The researchers' salaries are published publicly in the BOE, but they are regulated by different laws depending on their rank. At the university level, categories like Assistant Professor (AD) or Associate Professor (CD) are bound by the Worker's Statute, whereas ranks such as Civil Servant Associate Professor (TU) or Full Professor (CU) are bound by the Civil Service Law.

Researchers' remuneration in **Italian** Public RPOs, RFOs and universities are regulated by a national agreement. Any position can be reached with a public competition.

In **Slovenia**, there is no negotiating practice regarding remuneration in research institutions in Slovenia. The public sector salary system applies to the entire public sector, which is made up of budget users (state bodies and self-governing local authorities, public agencies, public funds, public institutes, public commercial institutes and other entities under public law that are indirect users of the state budget or local authority budgets). The public sector salary system is regulated by the Public Sector Salary System Act (ZSPJS), which defines the fundamental and uniform rules on the functioning of the salary system and a unified methodology of calculating and paying salaries for all public sector activities. The fundamental principles of the salary system include equal pay for work in comparable positions, titles and functions, as well as transparency and salary incentives. The public sector salary system is based on the Public Sector Salary System Act and the regulations and collective agreements adopted in accordance with this act. In addition to a basic salary, employees are entitled to allowances and performance-related bonuses under the conditions defined by the normative framework.

²²¹ Eurobarometer 465.

In **Slovakia**, the remuneration of the researchers in public RPOs and teachers in HEIS is regulated by Act no. 552/2003 Col. on the compensation of certain employees in the performance of work in the public interest. The basic salaries are set by special regulations and valorised annually. The basis salaries scales, i.e. amount of gross monthly wage, depends on the salary degree, the number of years worked, and classification to “classes” based on the complexity of work and responsibilities. For example, the lowest possible degree up to 2 years of praxes presents the gross monthly wage of 807 euros (2020).²²² The basic salaries might be complemented by various allowances, performance surcharges and bonuses, usually granted upon internal criteria. Often the institution does not have any transparent rules, providing thus space for unfair and biased remuneration between women and men. Suppose a trade union organisation is established at the level of the organisation. In that case, collective bargaining can theoretically influence the remuneration system and the rules of extra pay. A written collective agreement then follows these. So far, we did not find any signs of collective bargaining addressing gender wage gaps or gender unbalanced working conditions.

In **Poland**, detailed remuneration criteria are regulated through the law on higher education and science and ordinances. Universities determine the conditions of remuneration for work in a company collective agreement or remuneration regulations. The starting point is the professor's salary, which is determined by detailed ordinances. Other academic positions are paid as an appropriate percentage of the salary of the professorial position.

In **Bulgaria**, the negotiation of the remuneration of the researchers in the higher schools and institutes of BAS is agreed according to the following normative documents:

- Law on Higher Education - Art. 20; Art. 21 (1) - item 8; Art. 70 (1) - item 4; Art. 91 (1) - item 2;
- Ordinance on the terms and conditions for the evaluation, planning, distribution and spending of funds from the state budget for financing the inherent scientific or artistic activity of the MES (adopted by CMD C 233 of 10.09.2016, Promulgated SG no. 73/16.09.2016)
- Regulations on the terms and conditions for obtaining scientific degrees and holding academic positions at the University.
- Regulations for the structure and activity of the University.
- The collective labour agreement with the Trade Unions of the Higher School.

In **Portugal**, ABIC - Association of Scientific Research Fellows and the National Federation of Teachers - FENPROF, participate in the remuneration negotiations.

- Specific funding programmes/initiatives addressing the underrepresentation of women in STEM

²²² <https://www.minedu.sk/data/att/16800.pdf>

In **Spain**, the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training leads actions to support gender in science and female underrepresentation in STEAM. On its website *Mujeres STEAM*²²³, they have information concerning strategies, resources, initiatives and projects dedicated for that purpose. At the autonomic level, there are initiatives such as *STEM Madrid* from the Community of Madrid²²⁴ that offer different measures and objectives to promote STEM careers among Madrid's students, emphasising girls.

In addition, companies launch their initiatives and programmes to develop STEM careers for women, as is the case of *Iberdrola*²²⁵. Italian universities, RPOs and RFOs are working and propose training and masters for this purpose.

In **Poland**, there is no publicly funded programme to support women in STEM. Nevertheless, female researchers can benefit from different measures such as programs and competitions, which offer professional support, financial assistance and internships. These programs include 'Lead IT, Lady', 'New Technologies for Girls', 'Women and Science', 'Girls go start-up!'; 'Girls on technical universities', 'Microsoft Women'. Most of them are implemented by non-governmental organizations and private sector aimed to promote technical and engineering studies among women as well as to support them in the technology industry.

- Anti-sexual harassment policies in research and HEI

Growing attention must be paid to the **existence of sexual harassment within RPOs**. In Poland, about 40.7% of students reported an experience with sexual harassment (31.10% were men, and 47% - women) (Commissioner for Human Rights, 2021). In Slovakia, about $\frac{2}{3}$ of students had experienced sexual violence.²²⁶ Due to the limits in national legislation or its implementation, this negative phenomenon could be covered and resolved by the institutions.

The **Italian Code** of Equal Opportunities with the Legislative Decree No 198 of 11 April 2006, Article 26 paragraph 2) defines sexual harassment as a form of discrimination. The Italian Presidency of the Council of Ministers defined the framework of the National Strategic Plan on Male Violence against Women for 2017-2020.²²⁷ The National Strategic Plan defines the overall strategy for adopting the "Convention of the Council of Europe on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence (Istanbul Convention)". The Plan is performed with a dedicated budget (€ 38,5 million for 2019), to deal with multi-level targets and overseen by a national mechanism with the mandate to monitor and review its implementation. For this purpose, even if it is not an operative plan, it underlines the need to produce statistics and then gender budgeting for Public administration.

The role of CUGs in the RPOs, RFOs and universities is particularly relevant as currently is the operative point that can officially collect data about harassment

²²³ *Mujeres STEAM* webpage. Accessed in 31/04/2021 and retrieved from <https://www.educacionyfp.gob.es/mc/intercambia/mujeres-steam/iniciativas-y-proyectos/comunidades-autonomas.html>

²²⁴ *STEM Madrid* webpage. Accessed in 31/04/2021 and retrieved from http://educacionstem.educa.madrid.org/?page_id=74014

²²⁵ *Iberdrola* initiative: women in STEM careers. Accessed in 31/04/2021 and retrieved from <https://www.iberdrola.com/compromiso-social/mujeres-stem-iniciativas>

²²⁶ Kuruc, A., & Valkovičová, V. (2020). Čo so sexuálnym obťažovaním? Príručka pre vysoké školy. Bratislava: Inštitút pre výskum práce a rodiny. https://www.totojerovnost.eu/downloads/Co_so_sexualnym_obtazovanimPrirucka_pre_vysoke_skoly.pdf

²²⁷ (<https://www.provinceditalia.it/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Piano-operativo-2017-2020.pdf>).

and any form of discrimination. Many institutions (and also CNR) formalised a body for a counselling service. However, this kind of service needs to be profoundly improved in its operativeness.

On June 21, 2019 the ILO's International Labour Conference adopted the Violence and Harassment Convention (No. 190), Recommendation (No. 206), and the accompanying Resolution contained in the document titled "Eliminating Violence and Harassment in the World of Work"²²⁸ Italy ratified the Convention in 2021; it provides a framework to prevent and address violence and harassment, based on an inclusive, integrated and gender-responsive approach. Article 13 of the Convention establishes that "The provisions of this Convention shall be applied by means of national laws and regulations, as well as through collective agreements or other measures consistent with national practice, including by extending or adapting existing occupational safety and health measures to cover violence and harassment and developing specific measures where necessary." This Convention is mainly a tool addressed to policy and decision-makers.

The definition of sexual harassment is introduced in the bargaining with the Italian letter, for the first time, in the National Contract of Metalworkers in 1990²²⁹ The national collective bargaining employment contract for School in Italy in 2017 has introduced the template of the Code of Conduct to be adopted to prevent sexual harassment²³⁰ Based on this template many schools defined their own Code of conduct.

'The 2018 Annual Conference of the Italian Association Donne&Scienza (Women&Science), co-organised with EPWS - European Platform of Women Scientists as a "#wetooinscience" initiative, focused on "Sexual Harassment in Higher Education Institutions and Research Performing Organisations.'

The universities and the different research organisations defined and approved a Code of conduct to prevent and combat harassment. Without claim for completeness, we cite some examples of codes of conduct in some public research performing organisations.

- The Italian National Institute of Statistics (Italian: Istituto Nazionale di Statistica; Istat approved the Code of conduct for the prevention and combating of harassment already in 2009²³¹
- The INFN (Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics) defined and adopted its Code of conduct for the protection of the dignity of people who work and operate within the Entity.
- The Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) adopted its Code of conduct related to sexual harassment since 2011²³²
- The National Research Council of Italy approved its Code of conduct for preventing harassment during 2020²³³

Moreover, the Department of Equal Opportunities of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers has established a working group (where CNR is invited) for defining national guidelines on the training of workers who for different reasons

²²⁸ (https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_721160.pdf).

²²⁹ (CCNL Metalmeccanici – Industria, 14 dicembre 1990, in www.olympus.uniurb.it).

²³⁰ (https://icsanmarcoargentano.edu.it/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/Allegato_1_CCNL_Comparto_Scuola_molestie_sessuali.pdf

²³¹ (https://www.istat.it/it/files/2011/07/codice_mobbing.pdf).

²³² (https://agenziaentrate.gov.it/portale/documents/20143/210665/Codice+molestie+sessuali_Codice+di+condotta_agg22luglio2014.pdf/84e433ff-7957-4f0a-fdce-c59859043f3f)

²³³ (<https://www.cnr.it/it/news/allegato/1955#:~:text=Art.,-13%20%E2%80%93%20Diritto%20alla&text=segnalazione%20che%20successivamente,-,2.,siano%20testimoni%20di%20tali%20episodi.>).

come into contact with victims of violence, violence and harassment in the workplace, and the integration and reintegration of victims into employment. The Italian Universities adopted a Code of conduct on sexual harassment, or some guidelines are included in the Ethical Code of the Institution.

In **Spain**, there are no state policies specifically tailored to combat sexual harassment or gender violence in academia, RPO or RFO, so the general national and/or autonomic legislation is applied. Articles 9.2 and 14 of the Spanish Constitution compel public powers to work effectively and not just formal equality. The Organic Law 1/2004 on Measures of Complete Protection against Gender Violence was the first to establish a system to protect victims. The Organic Law 3/2007 for the Effective Equality between Women and Men binds the public administration to promote working conditions that avoid sexual harassment and the creation of procedures for its prevention. This law includes HEIs and RPOs in article 2.2.

The Organic Law 4/2007 of Universities demands higher commitment for gender equality in universities, especially in its twelfth additional provision that obliges all universities to create Equality Units.

The Organic Law 14/2011 of Science, Technology and Innovation includes the same obligation in its thirteenth additional provision for RPOs. They must include the gender perspective in their work and create Equality Units.

Furthermore, each autonomous community creates their own equality laws, such as the 1/2020 Law for the Equality between women and men by the Government of the Canaries.

It is the Equality Units that are ultimately responsible for creating protocols to prevent, detect and intervene against sexual harassment and gender violence in the public research sector. The State Pact against gender violence of 2017²³⁴ includes several measures to fight it, such as reinforcing the work of the Equality Units in measure nº 8.

In **Poland**, the issue of sexual harassment is regulated in the Labour Code in Article 18(3). It imposes an obligation on employers to prevent such behaviour and to protect their employees. As for the public research sector institutions, university rectors and directors of research institutions are responsible for compliance with these regulations. It is also worth mentioning that the University of Warsaw has published a guide on Counteracting Sexual Harassment.²³⁵ The publication contains rules and procedures in force at the University of Warsaw and recommendations and advice on how to prevent and respond in situations of sexual harassment.

In addition, in 2018, the Autonomy Foundation developed the Anti-Discrimination Standard for Universities in Poland²³⁶. This is a model document that every university can use to develop internal solutions, procedures and policies to counter discrimination and violence. It is the result of work carried out under the

²³⁴ Secretaría de Estado de Igualdad y Delegación del Gobierno para la Violencia de Género, "Documento refundido de medidas del Pacto de Estado en materia de violencia de género. Congreso + Senado", 2019. Available at: https://violenciagenero.igualdad.gob.es/pactoEstado/docs/Documento_Refundido_PEVG_2.pdf [31/04/2021].

²³⁵ University of Warsaw, Przeciwdziałanie molestowaniu seksualnemu a uczelni. Informator Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego (Counteracting sexual harassment and universities. University of Warsaw Directory), 2021. Available at: <https://www.uw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/informator-uw-o-przeciwdzialaniu-molestowaniu-seksualnemu-okladka.jpg> [18.04.2021]

²³⁶ Autonomia Foundation, "Standard antydyskryminacyjny dla Uczelni" (Anti-discrimination standard for the University), 2018. Available at: <https://autonomia.org.pl/publikacje/standard-antydyskryminacyjny-dla-uczelni/> [18.04.2021]

project *University Standards for Counteracting Violence and Discrimination* (2014-2015), The Standard was used by, among others, the Silesian Medical University in Katowice, Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Pedagogical University in Krakow, University of Opole.

In **Romania**, as regards policies aiming at preventing sexual harassment/gender-based violence in the field of HERI, there is an important set of norms at the national level that regulate the problem of all forms of violence (mainly Law 202/2002 and OUG 137/2000, updated and republished). At the same time, it is up to HE and research institutions if they decide to adopt (or not) a special Protocol for preventing and tackling (sexual) harassment and gender-based violence – otherwise, these issues can be referred to in the Code of Ethics adopted by each organisation.

In **Slovenia**, the policy adopted to address sexual harassment/GBV in academia/RPO/RFO is described in the Employment Relationship Act, Articles 6 and 7:

(1) Sexual and other harassment are prohibited. Sexual harassment is any form of unwanted verbal, non-verbal or physical conduct or conduct of a sexual nature with the effect or intent to affect a person's dignity, especially when creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, shameful or offensive environment. Harassment is any unwanted behaviour related to any personal circumstance, with the effect or intent to affect a person's dignity or create an intimidating, hostile, degrading, shameful or offensive environment.

(2) Sexual and other harassment referred to in the preceding paragraph shall be considered discrimination following the provisions of this Act.

In terms of complex policies addressing sexual harassment and gender-based violence in academia and RPOs and RFPs, **Slovakia** does not have any specific national guidelines on these issues. The latest available data on sexual harassment in academia from 2020 revealed that 2/3 of students had experienced gender-based harassment, mainly in the form of sexual undertone and derogatory remarks on women or men, unwanted sexual attention or sexual coercion.²³⁷ Most of the perpetrators were male students (37%) and male teachers (23%). Despite the relatively high prevalence of sexual harassment in HEITs, we did not find any comprehensive anti-harassment policies at Slovak Universities. Usually, the university has its Ethical Codes. For example, the Comenius University' Ethical Codex states that the university teacher and researcher "do not commit personal humiliation, immoral conduct and coercion"²³⁸. The Student Code of Ethics of the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava states that "students and teachers do not commit personal humiliation, immoral behaviour and coercion."²³⁹ The codes of Ethics usually also provide the rules on filing a complaint and procedure to address the complaint. However, we did not find any monitoring or evaluation report on how the codes of ethics are applied or effective. Based on the survey of sexual harassment in

²³⁷ https://www.totojerovnost.eu/downloads/Co_so_sexualnym_obtazovanimPrirucka_pre_vysoke_skoly.pdf

²³⁸ https://fevth.uniba.sk/fileadmin/ebf/Veda/Kvalita_humanitnych_vied/Vp_2017_16.pdf

²³⁹ https://www.stuba.sk/buxus/docs/stu/pracoviska/rektorat/odd_vzdelavania/legislativa/VSK/2021_03_smernica_eticky_kodex_studenti_podpisany.pdf

academia, most affected women did not use any complaint mechanism or report the adverse experience to any dedicated department.²⁴⁰

In **Bulgaria**, no information about adopted policies for dealing with sexual harassment / GN in academia / RPO / RFO was found.

In **Portugal**, only the University of Porto and the University of Coimbra have enacted a code of good conduct for preventing and combating harassment at work at university.

3.8. Gender equality in decisions-making

Promoting gender balance in decision-making positions and professorships is limited at the national level of the countries.

In **Poland**, there are no formal regulations promoting gender balance in decision-making bodies. There are also no sanctions that apply when there are no women in decision-making bodies. However, the representation of women in scientific leadership positions has increased in recent years. In the 2020-2024 term, 11 women have been elected as rectors of public academic universities (a nearly threefold increase compared to the previous term)²⁴¹. Still, their percentage share in the total number of rectors can hardly be considered satisfactory. However, it is worth mentioning that in the Equality Plan of the University of Warsaw, one of the objectives is to increase balanced gender representation. This applies to chairmanships in faculty and university committees, management staff, expert and review teams, and chairmanships of scientific and popularisation events. It is planned that by 2023 women will represent 40%²⁴².

In **Romania**, regarding gender equality in decision-making within the fields of HERI, two aspects have to be mentioned. On the one hand, the national legislation in force on gender equality is following this principle. For instance, Law 202/2002 stipulates that all institutions and public bodies have to promote and support women and men's balanced participation in leadership and decision-making, including the balanced participation in expertise boards, groups, or other managerial or consulting structures (Articles 21 and 22). On the other hand, given the principle of university autonomy and the rest of the regulations in HERI, there are no incentives or plans at the national level aiming at leading institutions to adopt pro-active measures to increase women in decision-making and professorships.

In **Spain**, in regards to gender parity in decision-making bodies or committees, the main objective of all public organizations in Spain is the balanced presence of women and men as dictated by the Organic Law 3/2007 of Equality: no group must represent more than the 60% or less than the 40%.

²⁴⁰ https://www.totojrovnost.eu/downloads/Co_so_sexualnym_obtazovanimPrirucka_pre_vysoke_skoly.pdf

²⁴¹ Educational Foundation Perspektywy, "Women in Tech. 2020", 2020. Available at: <http://www.dziewczynynapolitechniki.pl/pdfy/raport-kobiety-na-politechnikach-2020.pdf> [17.04.2021]

²⁴² University of Warsaw, "Gender Equality Plan", 2021. Available at: http://rownowazni.uw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/XII_GEP-PL_plan-na-rownowscielektro.pdf [30.04.2021]

In **Bulgarian** research organisations, there is no problem with the balance between the gender of decision-making positions and professors. The staff growth is carried out through quotas by positions: 50% habilitated lecturers - associate professors and professors and 50% non-habilitated - assistants and chief assistants. In the governing bodies - Faculty Council, Academic Council, General Assembly - the ratio is: 25% non-habilitated and 75% habilitated lecturers.

On the other hand, in **Portugal**, the most recent data confirm an under-representation of women in the highest positions of Portuguese universities, as well as in the reach of the top of the academic career.

The gender balance in decision-making positions and professorships with adequate awareness-raising and training is not promoted in **Slovenia**. The gender-equality plans as an assessment tool in the accreditation of universities are currently in construction as an answer to Horizon Europe demands to make them mandatory for universities and research organisations. There is no institutionalization of the proportion of women in Grade A/professor positions as an assessment criterion in institutional evaluations (higher education accreditation, performance contracts with universities). Guiding targets and/or quotas for women in decision-making and professorships are neither set nor implemented through any measures, initiatives, or legislation. The ratio of women participating in decision-making is not evaluated regularly.

In **Slovakia**, despite the continual unfavourable situation in women's representation in a decision-making position in public RPO/FRFO and HEIs, Slovakia does not have any specific measures, training or awareness-raising initiatives in this term. Basic rules of creating the management and self-governing bodies of the public research and academic institutions are regulated by the respective acts on high schools and public research institutions. Moreover, further rules on the election procedures and election bodies are anchored in specific regulations and statutes of the particular institutions approved by the self-governing bodies.²⁴³ Usually, the rules are "gender-neutral" and the same for all candidates irrespective of gender.

- The institutionalised gender-equality plans are an assessment tool in the accreditation of universities and made mandatory for universities and research organisations

In **Spain**, the gender dimension is usually not taken into account in the accreditation of universities and their academic programmes. The main actor dedicated to such purpose is ANECA, but it does not contemplate the gender dimension in its evaluation, accreditation and certification schemes, even though gender and diversity are one of its guiding principles.

²⁴³ See for example: SAV - Výberové konania SAV, https://www.upjs.sk/public/media/0799/zasady_volieb_kandidata_na_dekana_PF_UPJS_2019.pdf

The **Italian** MIUR defined guidelines for the evaluation of universities, RPOs and RFOs, contained in the document titled “INDICATIONS FOR POSITIVE ACTIONS OF THE MIUR ON GENDER ISSUES IN UNIVERSITY AND IN RESEARCH” (in Italian it is “INDICAZIONI PER AZIONI POSITIVE DEL MIUR SUI TEMI DI GENERE NELL’UNIVERSITÀ E NELLA RICERCA”)²⁴⁴ This document explains the good practices identified at the European level, indications for the integration of the gender dimension in research funded by MIUR, indications for address documents addressed to the CRUI, universities and research bodies concerning the mechanisms for selecting teaching and research staff, and indications for the evaluation of universities and research institutes. CRUI, in its document titled „Guidelines for Gender Balance in Italian Universities,“ (in Italian, „Linee guida per il Bilancio di Genere negli Atenei italiani“)²⁴⁵ Defines elements related to Gender balance that should be considered in the process of assessment of the different RPOs, RFOs and universities.

In **Slovenia**, the gender balance in decision-making and the enhancement of women’s participation in research are formally regulated by the document Strategy of work and development of the Research Agency of Republic Slovenia (ARRS) 2016-2020viii. The Agency lists different indicators to evaluate its activity and impact on research. One of the fields to monitor is also human resources and gender balance, in Rules on the Procedures of the (co)financing and Assessment of Research Activities and on Monitoring the Implementation of Research Activities: Article 35 (in the case of absence of the researcher due to parental leave in at least six months, this should be taken into account at project applications and also prolongs the period until PhD defence). The Agency follows the proportion of women among researchers working on projects and programs financed by the Agency (42% in 2015) and proportion of women among heads of research programs and projects financed by ARRS (31 % in 2015), but there is no publically available data for the recent period.

In **Slovakia**, the evaluation of research and development competence, i.e. if an organisation is eligible to perform research and apply for financial support from the public funds, is anchored in the §26a of Act 172/2005 Call. on the organisation of the state support in R&D. The evaluation criteria encompass, e.g. publishing activity, patent applications and patents granted, the amount of funds obtained, participation in national and international projects consortium, providing conditions for education and training of employees in the field of research and development, and management quality certificate in the relevant area of research and development, etc. An explicit criterion on gender-balanced research teams or working conditions is not included. The certificate of research competency is valid for six years from its issue, and the process of evaluation has to be renewed by a new application.

²⁴⁴(https://www.miur.gov.it/documents/20182/615845/Documento_+Indicazioni_azioni_positive_MIUR_su_temi_generere.pdf/23e81cb6-f15a-4249-9bd6-cf4fdcd113a8?version=1.0&t=1526057127577).

²⁴⁵ Available at: https://www2.cruil.it/cruil/Linee_Guida_Bilancio_di_Genere_negli_Atenei_italiani.pdf

There are no known forms of institutionalisation of gender equality plans in **Bulgaria** as a tool for evaluation in the accreditation of universities and such plans are not mandatory for universities and research organizations.

- The institutionalised proportion of women in Grade A/professor positions as an assessment criterion in institutional evaluations (higher education accreditation, performance contracts with universities) was explored.

In **Spain**, the proportion of women Grade A staff is not used as a criterion for institutional evaluation or university accreditation. In general, there are no specific incentives or sanctions for not meeting these kinds of target, apart from possible awards such as the aforementioned CSIC distinctive.

In **Italy**, the quota system for universities, RPOs and RFOs is not present for defining the positions of professors or researchers. The quota system for the decision making bodies is sometimes established at the level of a single research institution or university

In **Bulgaria**, there is no institutionalisation of the share of women in A / professor positions as an evaluation criterion in institutional evaluations (accreditation for higher education, performance contracts with universities). Exceptions are higher military schools and academies, where there are gender quotas in professional fields, due to the specifics of the military professions and their civilian counterparts. These universities have a mandatory minimum quota of women. Bulgaria declared that the parity is the default.

Only several countries **have guiding targets and/or quotas for women in decision-making** and professorships set and implemented through any measures, initiatives, or legislation.

In **Spain**, in regards to gender parity in decision-making bodies or committees, the main objective of all public organizations in Spain is the balanced presence of women and men as dictated by the Organic Law 3/2007 of Equality: no group must represent more than the 60% or less than the 40%. This target has not been reached yet in several research sectors such as professorships, as the proportion of women is still low, although with a steady increase in time: 24% in 2019 compared to a 21% in 2016. On the other hand, women are directors of 50% of the public RPOs.

In **Bulgaria**, the evaluation of the implementation of the targets and/or quotas for women in the decision-making process and professorships in Bulgaria is monitored by the NAEA.

There are no incentives for institutions adopting pro-active measures and/or sanctions for non-compliance with the set targets to increase women in decision-making and professorships in **Slovenia**. We do not have any targets or quotas set in the university or RPO/RFO boards.

Slovakia does not use any tools to improve women's representation in decision-making positions. Nor the proportion of women in Grade A/professor positions as an assessment criterion in institutional evaluations (higher education accreditation, performance contracts with universities) is not institutionalised. No guiding targets and/or quotas for women in decision-making and professorships set and implemented through any measure, initiatives or even legislation are set. So far, no incentives for institutions adopting pro-active measures and/or sanctions for non-compliance with the set targets to increase women's decision-making and professorships are set in any RPO/RFO or HEIs. No targets or quotas set in the university or RPO/RFO boards are placed.

In terms of gender parity on boards, targets & quotas, **Italy** does not define them at the national level. However, some institutions or universities defined this quota system at the local level.

In **Portugal**, there are no institutionalized gender equality plans that serve as parameters for the assessment and accreditation of HEIs and research agencies.

3.9. Gender equality in the content of national research programmes

We searched if the gender aspects, such as **gender balance and gender in the research content, are taken into account** or encouraged in national research programmes, from programme design through implementation and evaluation only sporadically in the countries.

In **Romania**, some national research programs target women in research or take into account gender aspects within HERI. However, one cannot argue that these programs are genuinely significant for a genuine interest in the principle of gender equality or its implementation at national level. Instead, these projects have rather been a window of opportunity for funding and/or transnational institutional collaboration.

The UEFISCDI²⁴⁶ is the leading public Romanian agency that manages competition-based programs for higher education and research related programs in Romania. The agency is directly subordinated to the Ministry of Education. It comprises four areas of activities - i.e. related to research financing programs, higher education, institutional projects, and international institutional cooperation. Therefore, UEFISCDI²⁴⁷ official activity reports distinctively refer to higher education on the one hand and research, development, and innovation. First, from the point of view of HE, UEFISCDI has contributed to the in-house

²⁴⁶ UEFISCDI, Raport 2018-2019 directia invatamant superior (Report 2018-2019 of higher education directives). Retrieved from: https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/resource-821015-uefiscdi_raport-2018-2019_invatamant_superior.pdf

²⁴⁷ UEFISCDI, Rapoarte de activitate (Activity Reports). Retrieved from: <https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/rapoarte-de-activitate?&wtok=&wtkps=fY5LDolwFEX30jIP2D73IMxcQXIK1gECryQisa9W5g5cXY/5ya3BAVvAgmMHLITQS6AtXqoJkFVOXrzQEddjlc98rO2rNsJ0XbvOymOigqMgEt5kN9Jy2/ICGOI4XK4HYQoIM30sttwA+/Fc7dz5PxWPBLuLiPcel86mfm7SxdaOKnTp3fex/3wB&wchc=54b5a3302920ed1b00fcc8017a4531d06110de8b>

development of a series of IT platforms used to collect, manage, and analyse statistical data relevant to the national higher education system. Access to these databases is not (yet) publicly available but we will access it during the next stages of the project. For example, the national platform for higher education statistical data (ANS) contains, among others, sex disaggregated data concerning universities' staff at national level. Second, from the perspective of research, development and innovation, almost all calls for competition mention the aim of encouraging and supporting the development of female researchers' careers. Nevertheless, yearly reports uploaded on UEFISCDI's website do not contain sex-disaggregated information concerning women's research activities.

The **Spanish** State Research Agency (AEI) of the Ministry of Science and Innovation considers the gender dimension in its I Gender Equality Plan for R + D + I activities by explaining the various measures that the AEI has taken to fund research with a gender perspective such as the creation, promotion and funding of a specific sub-area of Feminist studies (FEM); funding studies about women and gender or any topic that includes that perspective; or taking into account the gender perspective in the socio-economic impact of proposals as an evaluation criteria for state-funded research project calls. In addition, the plan takes into account seven specific objectives with their respective measures for the period between 2021 and 2023 in order to reinforce its work in gender equality.

In **Poland**, gender aspects are not included either at the stage of programme design or its implementation or evaluation. The National Research Programme adopted in 2011 does not include in any way gender equality aspect. The Steering Committee designing strategic national research programmes of applied research within the National Centre for Research and Development is entirely composed of men. There are no indications of gender mainstreaming neither in documents designing nor processes of implementing national research programmes. The National Science Centre, responsible for basic research, takes into account gender dimension only at the level of promoting female scientists and encouraging them to apply for grants, but not at the substantial level of research content and procedures.

In **Portugal**, with regard to the content of research focused on gender issues, the most extensive national research program is integrated into CIEG, belonging to the Higher Institute of Social and Political Sciences of the University of Lisbon (ISCSP-ULisboa). CIEG was established in February 2012 and is part of FCT's network of research centres. It should be noted that CIEG is the only centre in Portugal explicitly dedicated to gender studies and obtained the classification of "Excellent" in the latest assessment prepared by the FCT. CIEG includes researchers/es from several national and foreign universities working with gender issues in a multidisciplinary manner, being the main scientific partner of the project promoted by DGES, GE-HEI ²⁴⁸. Higher education institutions have been asked annually to indicate projects or activities implemented on gender equality. At the University of the Azores, the theme is deepened, for example, in the

²⁴⁸ On CIEG's lines of research, publications and activities, check the website at the e-mail address: <http://cieg.iscsp.ulisboa.pt/investigacao/linhas-de-investigacao-do-cieg>

discipline of Human Rights of the Degree in Euro-Atlantic Studies, in the area of Political Science / International Relations.

In **Slovenia**, gender aspects are not considered or accounted for in national research programs, program design, implementation, and evaluation. Slovenia does not implement processes to promote the integration of a gender dimension in research and innovation content of projects and studies.

Slovakia does not have any comprehensive processes to promote the integration of the gender dimension in projects and studies' research and innovation content. A formal criterion on the gender-balanced research team or a short description of how the project will contribute to gender equality might be present in some calls for research funding. This condition, however, is/was only a formality and did not have any real impact on the de-facto gender equality in the research.

We searched for **processes to promote the integration of a gender dimension in research** and innovation content of projects and studies, for example, information and qualification tools or concrete rewards and incentives implemented at the national level.

The existing practice in **Bulgaria**, both in terms of legislation, and in the actions of institutions, and the behaviour of providers of vocational education services (VET), and social partnership is within a system that does not promote the implementation and quality of VET for the integrated dimension of gender in the form of information and qualification tools or specific rewards and incentives.

In **Italy**, the incentives are mainly related to the European regulations and the European projects.

In **Slovakia**, several attempts to create training modules or study programmes focused on gender, women's rights and gender equality in diverse areas of society occurred within specific national financial schemes in the past, more than 10 – 15 years ago. For example, within the project EQUAL, pilot Testing and implementation of pilot educational modules at university level on Introduction to Gender Studies (including a short chapter on Women in Science)²⁴⁹.

In 2006 – 2008 a project “Knowledge, Institutions and Gender: A European Perspective” funded under the 6th Framework Program of the European Commission in the program Creating the European Research Area. From Slovakia, Comenius University in Bratislava, Faculty of Arts, Center for Gender Studies has been involved. The area of interest was to conduct comparative empirical research of scientific institutions and everyday practice of “doing science”, running in parallel in five European countries.²⁵⁰

In **Poland**, no specific tools or mechanisms promote the integration of gender dimension in research and innovation content of projects and studies funded by

²⁴⁹ <https://phil.uniba.sk/katedry-a-odborne-pracoviska/odborne-centra/centrum-rodovych-studii/projekty/projekt-equal/>

²⁵⁰ <https://phil.uniba.sk/katedry-a-odborne-pracoviska/odborne-centra/centrum-rodovych-studii/projekty/projekt-knowing/>

the Polish government. These aspects are taken into account only by a non-profit and apolitical Foundation for Polish Science, a member of the international consortium implementing “RRI Tools” - European project aimed at supporting responsible research and innovation for society and society. It provides tools to include among other gender equality into research projects - at the level of individual researchers as well as research institutions as a whole.

3.10. Gender disaggregated statistics on women in research and innovation

National partners provided information on the **national mechanisms compiling statistical data on gender equality** or women in research organisations and HEIs.

There are no nationwide mechanisms for compiling regular reports on gender or women's equality in academic research in **Bulgaria**. However, every year in December, the Higher Education Institutions fill in annual reports to the National Statistical Institute with disaggregated data on their research staff by research, professional fields, qualification structure, age and gender.

In **Spain**, the yearly report “Data and Figures of the Spanish University System” of the Ministry of Universities²⁵¹ presents data disaggregated by gender of the teaching and researching staff (PDI), the administrative and supporting staff, and students from Spanish universities. It covers matters such as the representation of students with bachelor and master's degrees or the proportion of PDI by field of study and academic rank. Additionally, the bi-annual report “Female Scientists in Figures” of the Women and Science Unit of the Ministry of Science and Innovation²⁵² is more specific, providing statistic data disaggregated by gender on women in research as well as recommendations and solutions in those areas that have not achieved the aims in the matter of gender equality. In this document, several statistical analyses can be found that shed light into different issues, such as the scissor effect in the percentage of women and men in professorships, in which there is an overrepresentation of men. Both reports are of public access on the web.

In **Poland**, gender-disaggregated data are still a challenge - gender dimension is not taken into account in all areas of statistical composition and systematic monitoring of women's and men's activities in certain economic and social life areas is not implemented. It is the case of research and science as well, where no statistical compilation, including gender perspective is provided on a regular basis. The last statistical presentation of women's participation in science with

²⁵¹ Ministerio de Universidades, “Datos y cifras del Sistema Universitario Español”, 2020. Available at: https://www.ciencia.gob.es/stfls/MICINN/Universidades/Ficheros/Estadisticas/Informe_Datos_Cifras_Sistema_Universitario_Espanol_2019-2020.pdf [14/05/2021].

²⁵² Unidad de Mujeres y Ciencia del Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, “Científicas en Cifras 2021”, 2021. Available at: https://www.ciencia.gob.es/stfls/MICINN/Ministerio/FICHEROS/Cientificas_en_Cifras_2021.pdf [05/05/2021].

disaggregation on a discipline and level of research career (graduate, PhD candidate, PhD) was provided by the Central Statistical Office in 2007²⁵³.

In **Portugal**, The CIG has implemented the monitoring of the situation of women and men, from which the necessary decisions and public policies at the national and local level will be taken to combat the identified asymmetries. The result of this monitoring was published in the Statistical Bulletin 2017: Gender Equality in Portugal²⁵⁴. Also, within ENIND, one of the measures is to review and improve the Gender Dossier of the National Institute of Statistics (INE), including the mapping of equality between women and men, in order to meet the specific objective of "ensuring information, including statistical data, of quality, disaggregated by sex".

In **Slovenia**, the Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science assists the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport in collecting and analysing data to formulate equal opportunities policies in science effectively. In collaboration with the Research Agency of Republic Slovenia, the Commission collected the data on statistics by gender in science for 2001-2010 for the last time. These old data are publicly available.

Slovakia does not compile any comprehensive statistical report on gender equality or women in research and academia regularly. Partial information is spread within several statistical publications providing only a very narrow and skewed picture of the reality of women in research and academia.

- The national bodies responsible for the collection and processing the gender-disaggregated data on personnel in research and higher education vary in the surveyed countries.

In **Spain**, there are several bodies and organisations that collect and process data disaggregated by gender on personnel in research and higher education: the National Institute of Statistics (INE) in its R + D + I Activities section, the Integrated System of University Information (SIU) of the Ministry of Universities, the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT), the General Secretariat of Research of the Ministry of Science and Innovation, universities and public RPOs themselves, as well as various administrations and bodies at the national and regional level in general.

In **Romania**, the National Platform for the Collection of Statistical Data for Higher Education (ANS) under the coordination of UEFISCDI is an integrated information system, developed in a modular way, compatible with data collection systems at the European level, dedicated to higher education in Romania, which brings together the main statistical data on education superior accessible to all interested actors. Some relevant sex segregated statistics are gathered but there is no special effort for the time being to collect more complex indicators relevant

²⁵³ Statistics Poland, "Kobiety w Polsce" (Women in Poland), 2007. Available at: https://stat.gov.pl/cps/rde/xbcr/gus/Kobiety_w_Polsce.pdf [28.04.2021]

²⁵⁴ The Bulletin is available at: <https://www.cig.gov.pt/2018/02/igualdade-genero-portugal-boletim-estatistico-2017/>

for gender issues within HEIs.²⁵⁵ The National Platform for the Collection of Statistical Data for Higher Education (ANS) under the coordination of UEFISCDI is an integrated information system, developed in a modular way, compatible with data collection systems at the European level, dedicated to higher education in Romania, which brings together the main statistical data on education superior accessible to all interested actors.

In Slovenia, there is no responsible unit or organization for the collection and processing the gender-disaggregated data on personnel in research and higher education. On demand of the Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science, the data are extracted from statistics by personnel of Research Agency of Republic Slovenia (ARRS).

In Slovakia, in terms of responsibility to collect and process gender-disaggregated data on research and higher education personnel, the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic would be the most appropriate body. The Ministry collects the data and publishes Annual reports on the stay-of-art of high education institutions in Slovakia.²⁵⁶ However, in the latest report, women have been mentioned only four times in the 50-pages long document.²⁵⁷ The Ministry provides the national data also for She Figures.

In Poland, no institution responsible for collection and processing the gender-disaggregated data on personnel in research and higher education was identified.

In terms of any **partial statistical analysis on women in research**, several partners' countries compiled considerable publications related at least partially to gender equality in research and HEIs.

The **Italian** MIUR provided in 2020 the report titled: Focus "Le carriere femminili in ambito accademico"²⁵⁸ The Gender Budgeting for each institution and university collects data providing the statistical analysis. Some more statistics at the Italian level (and coming from different sources) are provided by the "Report on research and innovation in Italy 2019"²⁵⁹ a report produced by CNR-IRPPS.

In Poland, there are independent initiatives regularly analysing women's participation in certain research areas such as STEM - "Girls as Engineers!" Report providing data on the number of female students on the Technological Universities regularly since 2012²⁶⁰. The National Science Centre provided information on the participation of women and men in research projects financed

²⁵⁵ The platform can be accessed at <http://www.date.invatamant-superior.ro>

²⁵⁶ Výročné správy o stave vysokého školstva | Ministerstvo školstva, vedy, výskumu a športu Slovenskej republiky (minedu.sk)

²⁵⁷ <https://www.minedu.sk/data/att/17747.zip>

²⁵⁸ available at: http://ustat.miur.it/media/1166/focus_carrierefemminili_universit%C3%A0.pdf

²⁵⁹ (http://www.dsu.cnr.it/relazione-ricerca-innovazione-2019/volume/Relazione_sulla_ricerca_e_innovazione_in_Italia_2019_webformat.pdf),

²⁶⁰ Educational Foundation Perspektywy, "Kobiety na politechnikach. Raport 2021": kobiety w technologiach to przyszłość" (Women at Universities of Technology 2020: women in technology are the future), 2021 Available at: <http://www.dziewczynynapolitechniki.pl/pdfy/raport-kobiety-na-politechnikach-2021.pdf> [28.04.2021]

by NSC between 2011 and 2018²⁶¹. The National Centre for Research and Development does not provide such summaries at all.

In **Slovenia**, in the book *Gendering Science: Slovenian Surveys and Studies in the EU Paradigms* by Mirjana Ule, Renata Šribar, and Andreja Umek Venturini, the share of women PhDs in scientific disciplines in Slovenia in comparison with the EU in 2010 and typical academic careers in the EU in 2002 and 2010 are reported. The data originated from a survey performed by The Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science, Ministry of Education, Science and Sport. Otherwise, different groups for needs of EU projects collect the gender statistics occasionally and temporary (for the time of projects duration).

There is a partial statistical analysis of women in research in **Bulgaria**. As part of a scientific study of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, a survey was prepared in order to study and summarize public opinion on some of the most important issues related to the topic "Cultural and historical heritage, national identities and social environment." ²⁶²

In **Slovakia**, a complex overview of the gender statistics is compiled in the annual publication of the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic, "Gender Equality in Slovakia" since 2016. It gathers all the available statistics with gender disaggregations from EU and national harmonised survey and administrative data. A specific sup-chapter is devoted to statistics on women and men in sciences and technology. Hence, only a few indicators are provided.²⁶³

The Yearbook of Science and Technology compiled by the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic contains only basic indicators on women in science (employed persons, students, by technological sectors, etc.) It includes the results of the Research and Development survey for the last five years. The statistics on Human Resources in Science and Technology (HRST) was introduced in the Slovak Republic according to the Canberra manual methodology in 2002. It is compiled from the results of the Labour force survey. Statistics on HRST is also included in the publication.²⁶⁴

Some information has been provided in Global annual reports on Gender Equality in Slovakia.²⁶⁵ These reports, however, only very seldom focus on women in science and the academy. Usually, only gender segregation in higher education is mentioned, but without any decent analyses.

Partial statistical analysis on women in research was prepared within several but sporadic projects centred on women in science. However, the study is focused either on women in the Slovak Academy of Sciences or HEIs, never encompassing gender equality in all types of public research institutions. The list of publications resulting from the respective projects is provided in the annexe.

²⁶¹ National Science Centre, „Informacja na temat udziału kobiet i mężczyzn w projektach badawczych finansowanych przez Narodowe Centrum Nauki w latach 2011 – 2018” (Information on the participation of women and men in research projects financed by the National Science Centre in 2011-2018), 2019. Available at: https://ncn.gov.pl/sites/default/files/pliki/informacja_na_temat_udzialu_kobiet_i_mezczyzn_w_projektach_NCN_2011-2018.pdf [18.04.2021]

²⁶² <https://www.bfu.bg/upload/izdania-BSU/proekt-monografia/Glava4-1-anketa.pdf>

²⁶³ https://slovak.statistics.sk/wps/wcm/connect/c24e0a9a-c833-45ea-bd49-ff1c6f701ca3/Rodova_rovnost_2020.zip?MOD=AJPERES&CACHEID=ROOTWORKSPACE-c24e0a9a-c833-45ea-bd49-ff1c6f701ca3-nnr81HF

²⁶⁴ <https://slovak.statistics.sk/PortalTraffic/fileServlet?Dokument=4e932adc-7aa6-47a1-8742-30b98123a9ca>

²⁶⁵ Výskum – TOTO JE ROVNOST' (totojerovnost.eu)

Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the valuable information provided by the project partners in their national reports and compiled in this comprehensive report, we can present the following overview findings of the national policies and measures to promote gender equality in research and HEI in the countries.

From the tables below, national policies to promote gender equality in research and HEI are more likely incorporated in general strategies for gender equality than in a specific strategy. Despite that, in almost all the countries, the responsible monitoring or other governmental body responsible for promoting gender equality in research and HEI was identified, implementation and monitoring bodies are rarely established, or the competencies are not assigned to any agency.

Table 7 Strategies and plans for the promotion of gender equality research, innovation and higher education in place

COUNTRY	Separate national strategy or action plan for GE in research and HEI	GE in research and HEI as part of overall GE strategy	GE reflected in strategies and plans in research, innovation or higher education sector
Bulgaria		✓	✓
Spain	✓	✓	
Italy		✓	
Poland			
Portugal		✓	
Romania		✓	✓
Slovenia			✓
Slovakia		✓	

Table 8 National bodies responsible for promoting GE in research and HEI in place

COUNTRY	Bodies in charge to promote GE policies	Bodies involved in implementation of GE policies	Monitoring and impact assessment of Ge policies in place
Bulgaria			
Spain	✓	✓	✓
Italy	✓	✓	✓
Poland	✓		
Portugal	✓		
Romania	✓	✓	
Slovenia	✓		✓
Slovakia			

While some gender studies as part of graduate or post-doc curricula in most of the countries, the gender balance or gender in research as an essential part of the research programs or projects evaluations were identified only in Spain and Portugal.

Table 9 Gender equality in study curriculum and research programs

COUNTRY	Specific courses on gender and gender equality in research in place	Gender balance and gender in the research content taken into account in research programmes
Bulgaria	✓	
Spain	✓	✓
Italy	✓	
Poland		
Portugal	✓	✓
Romania	✓	
Slovenia	✓	
Slovakia		

Gender-specific and sensitive measures in recruitment and re-entry of the academic workforce to continue in research are not in place at the partners' national level, except for Spain. However, almost all the countries implement or refer to the European Charter for Researchers and a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. The ways of application, though, might differ or be only formal without any real effect on the gender-balance at the organisational level in RPO, RFO and HEI.

Table 10 Gender sensitive recruitment and career development

COUNTRY	Gender-aware recruitment policies in place	National policy supporting the re-entry of the academic workforce into research careers	Application of the European Charter for Researchers and a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers
Bulgaria			✓
Spain	✓	✓	✓
Italy			✓
Poland			✓
Portugal			
Romania			✓
Slovenia			
Slovakia			✓

We did not find any comprehensive mechanisms in place for tracking gender pay gaps at the national level. Either the gaps are not calculated due to pre-set wage levels in the public sector or considered for not relevant. Despite considerable gender segregation in research and study fields, programs to promote women in STEM have not been identified. Anti-sexual harassment policies are in place in most countries, referring to general regulations of prohibition of sexual harassment in the workplace or via Ethical Codes. However, we did not have space to assess the effectiveness of such policies.

Table 11 Working conditions and environment

COUNTRY	Measures that trace gender pay gaps in place	Programs addressing the underrepresentation of women in STEM	Anti-sexual harassment policies in research and HEI
Bulgaria			
Spain		✓	✓
Italy	✓		✓
Poland			✓
Portugal			✓
Romania			✓
Slovenia			✓
Slovakia			

Despite the considerable gender imbalances in decision making of RPO, RFO or HEI, particular measures or targets are in place only in Bulgaria, Spain and Italy. Other countries support the balance in gender representation and participation in decision only rhetorically or do not acknowledge this as a problem.

Table 12 Gender equality in decisions-making

COUNTRY	Policies to promote GE in decision – making in place	Guiding targets and/or quotas for women in decision-making in place
Bulgaria	✓	✓
Spain	✓	✓
Italy		✓
Poland		
Portugal		
Romania		
Slovenia		
Slovakia		

To collect appropriate, detailed and country-specific data on gender equality in research and HEI is the base for designing and proposing effective policies in this area. While national mechanisms to collect and process administrative data are usually in place in the countries, regular and comprehensive statistical reports on women and men in science and academy have been identified only in few countries. More countries compile, however, partial reports on this topic.

Table 13 Gender disaggregated statistics on women in research and innovation

COUNTRY	National mechanisms compiling regularly statistical data on gender equality in place	Responsible body to collect and publish report on GE in research in place	Partial statistical analysis on women in research in place
Bulgaria	✓	✓	
Spain	✓	✓	
Italy			✓
Poland			✓
Portugal	✓		
Romania		✓	
Slovenia	✓		✓
Slovakia			✓

Project partners also provided conclusions and recommendations in their national reports. Respecting their views, we present them here in a full range.

Conclusions from Romania

In Romania, the principle of gender equality and all gender-related aspects are approached mainly from the perspective of the need for non-discrimination policies and much less from the perspective of the need for gender mainstreaming policies. Legislation dealing with gender discrimination has been adopted in 2000 and it has improved significantly ever since (as the report shows). Moreover, Romania is a signatory state for all major European and international treaties in the field (including Istanbul Convention). However, **awareness, understanding and investment in gender mainstreaming policies are not (yet) being prioritised at mainstream political or societal levels.** Quite often gender equality is conceived in terms of gender parity (formal equality). As a conclusion we consider that Romania does not miss more laws or dedicated institutions/bodies as much as it misses the culture of making them efficiently being implementing. There is a say in Romania “laws are made to be violated”. This is most challenging in any effort to gender mainstream its future national strategies.

In the recent context of **visible gender backlash** that attacks first and foremost the scientific legitimacy of the concept, the use of the concept “gender” has become more difficult than ever. Gender related confusions and inconsistencies are very common within the current political discourse. For example, on the one hand, the current Government Program in force (2020-2024)²⁶⁶ stipulates that the Ministry of Work and Social Protection is the main public institution in Romania responsible with the implementation of the “equal opportunities principle”, without however referring to the principle of “gender equality” or to the concept of ‘gender’ at all. On the other hand, the current national strategy on equal opportunities (2021-27) clearly states that the national specific terms/concepts in the field of equal opportunities and treatment between women and men are used in accordance with the definitions of the European Institute for Equal Opportunities between Women and Men (EIGE) – i.e. “gender equality”, that is being referred to as a “general category” that also includes “equal opportunities and treatment” (see Annex 1, p. 6).

One can also observe that in Romania there is a general **lack of culture of evidence** that makes difficult the design and implementation of national policies in any area. In education, the national mechanism for gathering gender sensitive data is underdeveloped. There are discrepancies between national bodies with respect to their ability to collect such data and there is also a lack of integrative approach between all responsible institutions, which makes it very hard to assess

²⁶⁶ The Government of Romania, “Program de Guvernare 2020 – 2014” (“Government Program 2020 – 2024”), 23 December 2020. Available at https://gov.ro/fisiere/pagini_fisiere/Program_de_guvernare_2020_2024.pdf

the current *de facto* situation of gender equality in the fields of higher education and research, development and innovation.

After 1990, the education reforms took place within a **permanent unstable political environment**. Each political regime in power changed the priorities and the high-level management within their bodies. Within the last 30 years Romania had more than 23 ministries of education. The numerous denominations of the Ministry of Education also prove the lack of coherence. In 2010 it was called *Ministry of Education, Research, Youth and Sports*, in 2019 it became *Ministry of Education and Research* and in 2020 it included 2 separate components: *Ministry of Education & Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization*, that have recently been reunited.

At this moment in Romania there is **no integrative operational gender sensitive approach to educational policies at a whole**. In this regard one has to remind us that in Romania too, in accordance with EU gender equality related priorities, higher education has been subordinated to “education” as a larger “critical area of concern”. As a result, at national level greater attention has been paid to gender equality in terms of formal access to education and/or in undergraduate than in tertiary education. Hence, primary and secondary education are better represented (in comparison with higher education sector) in terms of evidence-based resources and efforts undertaken (studies, implementation of gender specific projects by different GOVs and NGOs) in view of designing gender relevant reforms. The higher education sector has been from this point of view neglected.

Since the principle of gender equality is being addressed within part of the legislation in force, there are norms and actors/public bodies that can be involved in the implementation of the principle of gender equality in HERI at national level. Nevertheless, higher education on the one hand, and research and innovation on the other, represent two distinct areas with specific difficulties and obstacles that need to be overpassed within the gender mainstreaming process.

First, as regards higher education, in spite of the national legal framework that has been designed in accordance with EU norms and regulations, gender mainstreaming can take place only through universities’ Rectors and management internal bodies’ decisions (given the university autonomy as main principle underpinning the functioning of HE in Romania). Second, from the point of view of research and innovation, the principle of gender equality is not being prioritized in any way. In this regard it is important to underline that the main problems that the field of RI has to face are: the low level of public funding, the absence of a clearly articulated political interest for RI as well as the insufficient human resources.

Within the University of Bucharest, the culture of evidence in general is currently developing, with a slow start in the recent years. In particular, for gender-based policy, the current status is also at the beginning. The current project for

developing Gender Equality Plans fits very well in the current agenda of the university, with several measures already included in the Strategic Plan for the following years. So far, the level of measures related to gender equality is scarce if non-existent in many aspects. Sex-disaggregated general data on students or staff is not enough to account for the many subtle issues regarding gender, and, unfortunately, this kind of statistics was not of primary interest until recently. The great advantage for the university is provided by the new ideas and strategies that this project is developing, providing ideas and support for a well-constructed Gender Equality Plan at the level of the University of Bucharest. The context is favourable and much can be achieved.

In terms of recommendations concerning the establishment of the GEPI at UB it is too soon to come with an evidence-based set of recommendations. Solid internal dialogue, finalizing of the planned research component (focus groups, interviews, etc.), establishment and involvement of the UB-GEPI implementation team in the reflective thinking is needed in order to come out with a coherent and feasible set of recommendations. At this stage of documentation and research (first 3 months out of the 4 years' project) we mention nevertheless:

At the national level:

- The need for a solid, reliable national mechanism for collecting gender sensitive data from all sectors of activities-with modern gender sensitive indicators that capture not only basic women vs. men statistics but are able to seize more profound useful information for today Romania about various types of existing gender discriminations such implicit, subtle, modern sexism, neo-sexism, and of course intersectional discriminations. This effort will make possible better understanding of the persisting gender inequalities in all areas of activities-including higher education and research. It is an effort in which higher education and research institutes should play a crucial role, not the case for the moment.
- Improve the existing National Platform for the Collection of Statistical Data on HEIs (ANS) by enriching it with more sex and gender relevant indicators.
- Introducing within specialized bodies working with the Ministry of Education (e.g. ARACIS, UEFISCDI, CNACTDU, bodies in charge with the evaluation of Doctoral Schools, etc.) gender relevant evaluation criteria, standards, benchmarks. This will (i) improve the gender knowledge base and will identify the real existing problems and also (ii) consolidate the process of institutionalization of Gender Studies and gendered research within the national higher education sector.

At the organisation level (University of Bucharest, Romania):

The general remark that needs to be highlighted from the beginning is that certain national aspects (e.g. gaps in gender equality legislation in force at national level) cannot be approached within GEPI-UB. The university, as a public institution, has

the obligation to function within the existing national legal framework. As the first set of recommendations, we mention for the time being:

- Continuing the already established mechanism of collecting integrated statistics, with more focus not only on sex segregated ones but also on gender sensitive ones.
- Introducing explicitly the principle of gender equality within the University Charter (e.g. within the Mission and Objective part) and other internal documents.
- Location of a “unit” to deal with the GEPI within the existing Direction of Strategic Orientation, Evaluation, Monitoring and Public Policies. As the Rector already suggested, this is the place where the Statistic Bureau is functioning and could be the best strategic location.
- Adequate budgeting and human resources attributed for the functioning of the GEPI-UB.
- Wide carefully conducted process of bottom-up consultation within UB (through the GEPI Implementation team). It is the best approach in view of getting widespread support from professors, administrative staff, researchers, students for the real functioning of the GEPI-UB in the future.
- Involving also men (professors, researchers, administrative staff, high management) in the process of implementation of GEPI, and paying attention also to reverse gender gap within the UB.

Conclusions from Bulgaria

No Member State has achieved full gender equality and progress has been slow. Progress on gender equality is evolving curvilinearly. A new impetus is needed. Although gender inequalities in education have been almost eliminated, there are still differences in employment, pay, care, participation in government and pensions. Too many people in the Member States still violate the principle of gender equality through sexist hate speech and by blocking action to combat gender-based violence and gender stereotypes. Some citizens of Bulgaria are no exception in this context. Gender-based violence and harassment persist, and this is a cause for concern.

Bulgaria officially supports the implementation of the Gender Equality Strategy adopted by the EC and synchronizes its legislation with the policy objectives and key actions for the period 2020-25. The country presents clear evidence of the encouraging behavior of its institutions towards the goal of achieving gender equality. Europe's goal is for women and men, girls and boys, in all their diversity, to be equal. The principles of equality in the Old Continent postulate that individuals are free to follow their chosen path of life, to have equal opportunities to succeed and where they can participate and lead European society on an equal footing.

We need to ensure resilience and flexibility of what has been achieved in terms of equality between genders.

The progress and success of equality efforts gender, as well as the implementation of the GEP, are vulnerable for changes within which they can be undone or suspended decisions and achieved results.

This often happens when key supporters or activists in senior management positions at the University and non-functional units change their functions / roles or leave. Budget changes, cuts, restructuring and apathy are also factors, which reduce or limit the resilience of the GEP.

In order to overcome these obstacles, it is especially important to engage different organisational structures both with the topic of gender equality and with work on the plan.

This means that they must be sought support and engagement with the plan from various stakeholders, not just in a particular URAK faculty or department. Allocating a multiannual budget for activities related to gender equality, which is not provided by only one faculty or department, also contributes significantly to sustainability. The inclusion of regular reporting and measures and / or monitoring and evaluation tools in the RDP helps to alarms when resilience decreases, and take an action before the situation to become a crisis. Before being approved and initiated, each plan must undergo a SWOT analysis (strengths and weaknesses) and on stress test to determine how resilient and flexible is to ensure that it is stable enough and can to overcome the challenges of the future.

Conclusions from Spain

As a member of the European Union and the United Nations, Spain has a legal framework that incorporates the rights of equality between women and men. The Spanish Constitution of 1978 establishes that equality is one of the highest values of the legal system and that all Spaniards are equal before the law, prohibiting any discrimination based on sex. But this formal equality does not have a correlate in real life. Spain has been progressively extending a set of legal regulations relating to the application of the principle of equality, such as Organic Law 3/2007 for the Effective Equality of Women and Men (LOIEMH), the inclusion of the Government Delegation for Gender Violence, the Institute for Women and Equal Opportunities, Directive 2002/73/EC and Directive 2004/113/EC, relating to the application of the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to goods and services.

In turn, the Canary Islands passed Organic Law 1/2018, which introduces for the first time the rights of equality between women and men and guarantees non-discrimination. Gradually, articles are being incorporated that reinforce the coverage that guarantees equality, such as Article 11. Right to equality and cooperation, and Article 17. Right to gender equality. It is also important to point out that since 2010 the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands has had the Canary Islands Institute for Equality, created by Law 1/1994, whose

predecessor was the Canary Islands Institute for Women and, as a consultative and advisory body, it must be taken into account and has the capacity to make proposals in the procedures for drafting general provisions promoted by the Government of the Canary Islands.

As regards protection against gender violence, two laws have been passed: Canary Law 1/2010 for equality between women and men, and Law 16/2003 on the Prevention and Comprehensive Protection of Women against Gender Violence, amended by Law 1/2017 to incorporate into the autonomous regulations the provisions contained in the Istanbul Convention and the resolutions of international bodies. In the university field, Canarian Law 1/2010 imposes a series of mandates on the Canarian university system, such as promoting equal opportunities in relation to professional careers; developing family and work reconciliation measures for all staff, both teaching and non-teaching, or including in the curricula teachings on equality among other measures. Different strategies, programs and action plans have been implemented by the State Research Agency, such as the creation of the Strategic Group for Gender Equality with the aim of implementing measures for the implementation of the gender perspective, which prioritizes work in three areas of action or areas of work, which respond to seven objectives and include a total of thirteen measures.

Likewise, the Law on Science, Technology and Innovation and the National Strategy for Science and Technology and Innovation 2013-2020, focused on research and innovation, has created several bodies to carry out the equality objective. Although educational competencies are devolved, national laws stimulate public research sector institutions to adopt equality measures for gender, and the Ministry of Science and Innovation has a program that encourages women to pursue a career in science and research.

Specifically, the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria has a Gender Equality Unit that implements the First Equality Plan 2016-2019 of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria and the Protocol for the non-sexist use of language.

In general, the data collected indicate that the legislative framework is not guaranteeing the incorporation of equality rights in society. Some of the indicators show that the unemployment rate, job insecurity and caregiving are higher for women than for men. Likewise, the time women spend on housework is almost double that of men. The percentage of representation and participation of women in the different constitutional bodies, Senate, Government, General Council of the Judiciary, Court of Auditors or Royal Academies, is still considerably lower than that of men.

The gender pay gap between men and women in research and academia is still present in Spain, as research reports show. ANECA, the main actor dedicated to the accreditation of universities and their academic programs, does not contemplate the gender dimension in its evaluation schemes. Likewise, no state

policies are specifically adapted to combat sexual harassment or gender violence in the academic environment, so general national and/or autonomous legislation is applied. The University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria does not include a professional orientation specifically aimed at women scientists and does not take into account specific data on the number of men and women in the workforce when hiring new academic/research personnel. Similarly, it does not offer mentoring programs specifically aimed at female employees, offers some training on gender equality, but not on a regular basis, does not establish gender differences in terms of access to internal training, nor does it allow for a specific sabbatical year for female scientists. In turn, no specific leadership programs with gender integration are proposed, nor specific gender training for managers. Nor is there a specific funding program for gender research, and data on research funds disaggregated by sex are collected but not publicly available.

It is important to note that there are no established women's networks in the institution. Although there have been improvements, equality between women and men is still a pending task.

Conclusions from Slovenia

Slovenia emphasises freedom of work as one of the fundamental freedoms defined by the Constitution of the Republic of Slovenia. Employment of citizens is the most common way to ensure social security and the right to a retirement pension. Citizens of both gender can freely choose employment and jobs must be accessible under the same conditions. The primary legislation of gender equality is disclosed in the Equal Opportunities for Women and Men Act, which defines general and special measures for the creation of equal opportunities, determines the holders of tasks, their competencies and obligations, introduces special informal treatment of cases of alleged unequal treatment of the sexes and the advocate of equal opportunities as an authorized person and the obligations of the entities involved in these cases. An unbalanced representation of the sexes in the sense of the previous paragraph is defined with the representation of one sex in an individual area of social life or its part lower than 40%.

Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2015–2020 sets out general priority areas for improving the situation of women and men and ensuring the sustainable development of gender equality in the Republic of Slovenia, and identifies key challenges and problems for the period 2015–2020. Periodical Plans for Implementation of the Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men for years 2016-2017 and 2018-2019 thoroughly address areas of work and measures to be taken accordingly to accomplish gender equality in different public and private spheres. According to this document, the relationship between gender equality and science/education is currently not balanced and different types of gender inequalities have been recognised.

The Protection against discrimination Act, active since 23. 5. 2016, provides for the protection of every individual against discrimination regardless of gender, nationality, race or ethnic origin, language, religion or belief, disability, age, sexual orientation, sexual identity and sexual expression, social status, financial status, education or any other personal circumstance. Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities of Republic Slovenia is responsible for the GE policies and their implementation, monitoring and evaluation.

In 2016, the Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities of the Republic of Slovenia implemented a pre-defined project entitled "Towards Equalising Power Relations between Women and Men ". The project's overall aim was to better understand equal and unequal power relations between women and men to identify adequate responses to persistent imbalances in gender-based power structures in Slovenian society.

Gender equality in research is regulated in the document Strategy of work and development of Research Agency of Republic Slovenia (ARRS) 2016-2020. The Agency, as one of the fields to monitor, includes the number of women working on research projects and number of women among project leaders. Gender balance in decision-making and the enhancement of women's participation in research are regulated by the Rules on the Procedures of the (co)financing and Assessment of Research Activities and on Monitoring the Implementation of Research Activities.

The area of Research and Innovation is regulated by the Resolution on Research and Innovation strategy 2011-2020. Measure no. 34 foresees an Action Plan for Improving Career Opportunities for Researchers in all Career Periods and for Ensuring the Gender Equality Principle.

In order to increase the participation of women in science, for improving scientific excellence, connections with European Research Area (ERA) and its goals, the Slovenian Strategy for Strengthening the European Research Area 2016-2020 (Slovenian ERA Roadmap 2016-2020) was put into force in 2016. One of the priorities was gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research (priority area 4).

The Ministry of Education, Science and Sport is responsible for implementing the Research and innovation strategy of Slovenia (RISS) 2011-2020 and the UNESCO L'Oreal Scholarship. Under the Ministry, there is also a Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science, which is very active in the area (research and data collection; suggestion of legal changes, including changes in order to create action plan to improve career possibilities of women; awareness-raising; dissemination of research findings; promotion of gender equality...).

In spite of many loose or too general regulations and strategies, the only monitoring in field of gender equality policy is performed occasionally on demand of The Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science, which assists the Ministry

of Education, Science and Sport in collecting and analysing data for the effective formulation of equal opportunities policies in science. There are no actions, which would increase number of women in decision-making bodies neither in society at national level or in research organisations, like JSI. There are also no activities, which would force research organizations to disclose gender dependent data. Availability of these statistical data is dependent on good will of directors.

At JSI level, we are currently in the process of acceptance of gender equality action plan by Scientific Council. The action plan meets the requirements of the European Commission for the participation of organizations in Horizon Europe, which must integrate the gender dimension into research and development work and have adopted gender equality plans. The detailed plan of the Jožef Stefan Institute for the Establishment of Gender Equality will cover areas such as work-life balance and organizational culture, gender balance in leadership and decision-making, gender equality in employment and promotion, gender mainstreaming in research and development. Learning content, measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment. It will be made in accordance with the instructions of the European Institute for Equal Opportunities and taking into account the set of tools GEAR (Gender Equality and Academia and Research). The main activities will consist of regular monitoring of promotion and awarding of women at different levels, monitoring and improving conditions important for family-friendly environment, obtaining data on the number and share of proposed (by JSI) researchers in decision-making bodies at different levels of research hierarchy. A special attention will be put to gender sensitive use of Slovene. We will make statistics on recruitment of young researchers regarding sex of the candidates and supervisors. We will develop and adopt a detailed program of equal opportunities at JSI, which will include the necessary additional organizational changes and measures for sustainable care for equal opportunities by gender. We will establish an appropriate organizational structure, which will include counselling services on women's career opportunities, care for nominating candidates for awards, ensuring the nomination of candidates to decision-making bodies, analysis of working conditions separately by gender, promotion of equal opportunities at JSI and activities for coordination of family life and professional work, such as implementation of the family day at JSI, a contact point for reporting eventual sexual harassment and taking appropriate action.

Conclusions from Poland

Article 33 of Polish Constitution adopted in 1997 states that "the male and female have an equal right to education, employment and promotions, to equal remuneration for work of equal value, to social security and to occupy positions, perform functions and obtain public dignity and decorations".

In addition, Poland has ratified most of the international legal acts supporting equality, including the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), as well as the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action.

Ratified international agreements constitute a particularly important source of the legal framework of equality policy in Poland, as they are listed as sources of universally-binding legislation in the Polish constitution (Article 87).

Accession to the EU has contributed to a general improvement of the legal framework for equality, including significant changes in the labour code introduced in compliance with European principles. Both the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union are supreme over national law. In 2010 the Polish parliament adopted The Act on the Implementation of Certain Provisions of the European Union in the Field of Equal Treatment.

The Act implements several EU directives, including the Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation; and Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation. The Act sets general framework conditions for equal treatment policy in Poland and it specifies the competent bodies in equal-treatment issues, that is, the Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment and the Commissioner for Human Rights.

As a consequence, institutional mechanisms for gender equality and gender mainstreaming in Poland remain a key issue of relevance for policy and the role of the EU gained a lot of importance in this respect. The EU funds and support constitute a crucial source for promoting gender equality principle in Poland. The literature and documentation discussing activities developed with the support of the European Social Fund (ESF) through a range of Operational Programmes - overseen by Government Ministries in collaboration with social partners and civil society organisations - demonstrates the importance of the ESF for gender equality policy in Poland. In fact, the ESF has proven to be a crucial source of funding. Additionally, it has had a decisive impact on implementing gender equality plans in ways that are sensitive to gender issues. The external gender-mainstreaming requirements to implement gender perspectives throughout the programmes and activities and assessment and evaluation have been influential.

The same applies to gender equality in science and research, where recommendations pertaining to such activities and good practices are emerging in Poland. Surveys carried out by the Office of the Commissioner for Human Rights²⁶⁷ and the Helsinki Foundation²⁶⁸ have unequivocally confirmed the presence of sexual harassment at universities and the need for clear anti-discrimination procedures. Furthermore, the National Science Centre (NCN) has implemented activities to monitor the participation of men and women in research

²⁶⁷ Commissioner for Human Rights (2018), *Doświadczenie molestowania wśród studentek i studentów. Analiza i zalecenia*. Office of the Commissioner for Human Rights. Warsaw.

https://bip.brpo.gov.pl/sites/default/files/%2FDoświadczenie%20molestowania%20wśród%20studentek%20i%20studentów%2C%202018_0.pdf [3.07..2021.]

²⁶⁸ Gerlich Julia (2019), *Molestowanie na polskich uczelniach publicznych*. Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights. Warsaw. <https://www.hfhr.pl/molestowanie-na-polskich-uczelniach-publicznych-raport-hfpc/> [12.04.2021]

grants²⁶⁹) and have undertaken steps to ensure balanced representation of the sexes in expert and reviewer committees²⁷⁰.

Despite above mentioned activities and legislative regulations real equality between women and men in science has still not been achieved. One of the biggest challenges of gender (in)equality in science - as it was mentioned - is the elimination of sexual harassment. Besides, an important factor hindering women from having the same opportunities in science as men is difficulty reconciling professional and family life by female scientists.

Initiatives undertaken in that field are implemented individually by each research or HE institution rather than as a part of a national strategy. This leads to a great dispersion of good practices in that field. Activities implemented by selected Universities (such as the University of Warsaw, the Jagiellonian University or the University in Gdansk) or non-partisan NGOs like Perspektywy Education Foundation or Foundation for Polish Science²⁷⁰ are very valuable, but they will not substitute a holistic gender equality strategy for Polish Research and Innovation.

The Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce has clear pay and recruitment transparency policies to avoid discrimination based on sex/gender, age, family status, ethnicity, disability, and other possible grounds of discrimination. But there is no advanced organisational solutions to change gender equality (similar to most HEI's in Poland). The University has received the distinction of "HR Excellence in Research" from the European Commission. This obliges the University to continuously develop its Human Resources and recruitment policies, including the development of equality policies in the form of The General Equality Plan for the Jan Kochanowski University. The University has great potential to provide a Gender Equality Plan supported by the groups of researchers and teaching staff, and has institutional background in the Organisation's administrative entities.

It should be strongly underlined that awareness of gender equality in science is of great importance, but gender equality has been often associated only with the recruitment processes and possibly, remuneration. Other issues are ignored or unknown. Therefore, both at the University and in other Research Organisations in Poland, or in the society itself, there is little awareness of gender equal opportunities in science. When developing and implementing GEP at the Jan Kochanowski University, key of importance will be raising the awareness of the essence and importance of GEP, conducting educational processes for University community: authorities, employees or students according to the issues of equal opportunities and Gender Equality in research and innovation.

²⁶⁹ NCN (2019a) Informacja na temat udziału kobiet i mężczyzn w projektach badawczych finansowanych przez Narodowe Centrum Nauki w latach 2011-2018. https://www.ncn.gov.pl/sites/default/files/pliki/informacja_na_temat_udzialu_kobiet_i_mezczyzn_w_projektach_NCN_2011-2018.pdf [3.07.2021]

²⁷⁰ NCN (2019b), Stanowisko Narodowego Centrum Nauki w sprawie równego dostępu kobiet i mężczyzn do środków finansowych na badania naukowe https://www.ncn.gov.pl/sites/default/files/pliki/2019_02_stanowisko_ncn_ws_rownego_dostepu_kobiet_i_mezczyzn.pdf [3.07.2021].

Conclusions from Slovakia

In Research and Innovation area, Slovakia ranks among the modest performers among the EU28 regarding R&D expenditure and commercial and non-commercial R&D outputs.²⁷¹ Higher education institutes rank low in international scoreboards²⁷², and the country faces the persistent emigration of students and young, particularly educated and highly skilled people abroad. The relatively high share of women researchers in the total researchers' headcount (41% in 2019) is explained by the dominance of public sector in R&D employment.²⁷³ The percentage of women researchers in business enterprise sector is only 15.9%. The proportion of female researchers in the higher education sector working under precarious working contracts is 12% to 9,3% of male researchers. The share of women in the Slovak Academy of Sciences, its presidents and members of the highest decision-making body decreased from 18.2 in 2018 to 13.6 in 2019, and even 9.1 in 2021.²⁷⁴ In the research funding organisations, the proportion of women in decision-making positions is 15.5 % (2020).²⁷⁵

In promoting and enforcing gender equality and equal treatment policies and legislation, including women's rights, Slovakia underwent relatively dynamic development. Essential legislative amendments, specifically those adopted in the country's accession to the European Union, contributed to a greater awareness among the public and professionals regarding direct and indirect forms of discrimination and created the main framework for gender equality enforcement. The promotion of gender equality in most societal areas is backed by several national strategies and action equality plans. The institutional administrative machinery was established hence with modest personal resources.

The overall effectiveness of eliminating gender inequalities in society and establishing a fairer environment for women and fully employing their talents is low. Based on the basic gender equality indicators, the unequal and gender imbalanced situation has stalled or even worsened. Despite relatively elaborated legislation, its enforcement lacks behind and does not bring substantial improvement.

Moreover, the development of the gender equality policies and institutional background in recent five years deteriorated by emergence of the anti-gender movement. The conservative groups supported by church and ultra-conservative lobbying agencies succeeded in penetrating political parties and government administration and prevent adopting several policies documents, including the Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence.

²⁷¹ https://rio.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/riowatch_country_report/RIO_CR_SK_2017_PUBSY_IDF_0.pdf

²⁷² The best Slovak HEIs ranked no. 688 (the Comenius University in Bratislava), no. 1210 (the Slovak University of Technology), no. 1286 (the Technical University of Košice in the January 2021 edition of the Webometric Ranking of Universities

²⁷³ https://rio.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/riowatch_country_report/RIO_CR_SK_2017_PUBSY_IDF_0.pdf

²⁷⁴ Positions covered: President: chairperson of the highest decision-making body (code PRES_CHAIR) and members: members of the highest decision-making body (count includes the president, code MEMB_HDM) EIGE https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/wmidm_educ_wmid_acadsci/metadata

²⁷⁵ Browse Gender Statistics | Gender Statistics Database | European Institute for Gender Equality (europa.eu)

In research and higher education, the topics of gender equality, advancement of women and gender in research/science are not prominent at the national level. The topic of women in science is dealt intermittently, usually upon the EU initiatives or research funding devoted specifically to women in science or gender imbalance in research and innovation.

In Slovakia, the overall commitment for gender equality in research, innovation and HEI is limited. The low engagement of the national governmental institutions results in the lack of nationwide strategies, plans or programs that would promote and advance the situation of women in research and HEI.

No national law or policy encourages institutions of the public research sector, i.e. research performance organisations, universities and research funding agencies, to adopt gender equality measures, including gender action plans. The only pressure stems from the European Union framework in research and innovation, namely programmes such as Horizon Europe, to comply with the requirement to have GEP active to get funding from the programme. Usually, if the adoption of gender equality measures is not legally binding and no sanction stems from the non-compliance, no action will be taken.

Conclusions from Portugal

Due to the accession of each Member State to the European Union, under the fundamental principles of European law and its case-law, EU law has priority over national law, although it is also based on it, is superior in absolute scope: any binding European rules subject any internal normative acts of the Member States and, including, their Constitutions, and it is for national judges to respect this primacy and to refer the matter to the Court of Justice of the European Union for a preliminary ruling in case of doubt.

The primacy of EU law is complemented by the principle of direct effect, in which citizens and citizens can invoke European standards in their relations with their Member States and with other citizens. Accordingly, EU law, regardless of whether or not it is transcribed into national legal systems, creates obligations and rights for individuals in relations with and between public authorities.

Given the path taken, we can conclude that the European, national and regional legal-political framework promotes, on the one hand, the promotion of gender equality at organisational level, but the mechanisms for technical support and control of the implementation of equality policies are still incipient, which makes it difficult, on the other hand, to promote them.

We are also aware of the greatness of the goals and difficulties of those who walk the path for the first time. We believe it is appropriate to make the main guidelines on gender equality policy binding, in grading the European legal order, from the EU institutions to the local executive bodies, strengthening support and creating control and enforcement mechanisms. And here, it matters both how you build it and the result that is achieved. This too must be planned in view of gender equality and equality between women and men.

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Portugal project partners encounter major obstacles and corresponding challenges in Portugal, specifically in the Azores' Autonomous Region, for the implementation of gender equality and gender equality. One of the major challenges at both national and local levels is integrating the gender perspective in all areas of political action, both internally and within the territory, based on mechanisms for diagnosing, monitoring, and evaluating the various actions and municipal equality plans. In this way, more inclusive and egalitarian cities, towns and civil parishes can be designed.

Annexes

1. List of national legislation and policies in terms of gender equality in society

Bulgaria

- The Constitution of the Republic of Bulgaria (Promulgated, SG No. 56/1991)
- The Law on Protection against Discrimination (Promulgated, SG No. 86/2003)
- The Law on Equality of Women and Men (Promulgated SG No. 33 of April 26, 2016)
- The Labour Code (Promulgated, SG No. 26/1986)
- The Employment Promotion Act (Promulgated, SG No. 112/2001)
- The Social Assistance Act (Promulgated, SG No. 56/1998),
- The Employment Act. higher education (Promulgated, SG No. 112/1995),
- The Law on Defence and the Armed Forces of the Republic of Bulgaria (Promulgated, SG No. 112/1995)
- The Family Code (Promulgated, SG No. 41/1985)
- The Social Security Code (Promulgated, SG No. 110/1999)
- The Law on Protection against Discrimination (Promulgated, SG No. 86/2003)
- The Anti-Trafficking in Persons Act (Promulgated, SG No. 46/2003)
- The Law on Protection from Domestic Violence (Promulgated, SG No. 27/2005)
- Ombudsman Act (Promulgated, SG No. 48/2003)
- Health Act (SG No. 70 of 10 August 2004)
- The Law on Equality of Women and Men (Promulgated SG No. 33 of April 26, 2016)
- The General Strategy for Gender Equality in Bulgaria 2021-30
- Annual National Action Plans for the Promotion of Equality between Women and Men
- Summary of analysis of the implementation of the National Strategy for promoting equality between women and men for 2016-2020.²⁷⁶

Spain

- The Spanish Constitution of 1978
- Organic Law 3/2007, of 22 March, on Effective Equality between Women and Men (LOIEMH)
- Organic Law 1/2004 on Measures of Complete Protection against Gender Violence
- Royal Decree 6/2019 on urgent measures for ensuring equal treatment and opportunities for women and men in employment and occupation²⁷⁷
- Female Scientists in Figures” of the Women and Science Unit of the Ministry of Science and Innovation²⁷⁸

²⁷⁶ Available at: [resume-analiz-strategy.pdf](https://www.government.bg/resume-analiz-strategy.pdf) (government.bg)

²⁷⁷ Available online <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2019-3244>

²⁷⁸ Available at: https://www.ciencia.gob.es/stfls/MICINN/Ministerio/FICHEROS/Cientificas_en_Cifras_2021.pdf

Spain – Canary Island

- Law 8/2014, of 28 October 2014, on non-discrimination on the grounds of gender identity and for the recognition of transsexual persons (retrieved from <https://www.equalitylaw.eu/downloads/5262-spain-country-report-gender-equality-2020-pdf-1-22-mb>)
- Law 1/2010, of 26 February, of the Canary Islands on equality between women and men
- Law 16/2003, of 8 April, on the Prevention and Comprehensive Protection of Women against Gender Violence, amended by Law 1/2017, of 17 March, which incorporates into the regional regulations the provisions set out in the Istanbul Convention and the resolutions of international bodies

Italy

- Italian Constitution
- National Code of Equal Opportunities between Women and Men, established by Legislative Decree No. 198 in 2006
- Decree No. 198/2006, a consolidating act called the Code of Equal Opportunities between Men and Women (the Equal Opportunities Code)
- Law 53/2000 on sustaining motherhood and fatherhood, time for care and for vocational training, and coordination of hours in the town's public services (and its subsequent amendments)
- Decree No. 151/2001 on the protection of motherhood and fatherhood
- Italian law 120 of 12 of July 2011 (introducing introduced a quota system)
- Italian budget law of 2020
- the Italian budget law of 2020, i.e., Article 1, paragraphs 302-305 of the law n. 160 of 2019
- Law 215/2012 for municipal elections; Law 56/2014 for elections - of second degree - of metropolitan and provincial councils; the law 20/2016 for the elections of the regional councils; Law 165/2017 for the elections of Parliament; Law 65 of 2014 for the Italian representation in the European Parliament (approving regulatory measures aimed at promoting gender balance within elective, local, regional, national and European assemblies)
- The National Recovery and Resilience Plan, Italy
- Second gender budgeting report published in 2021, available online <https://comunicazione.cnr.it/sites/default/files/media/BDG%20CNR%20EDIZIONI2def.pdf>
- Law April 7, 2014, n. 56 (appointing an equality councillor following of Legislative Decree no. 198/2006)
- National Strategic Plan on Male Violence against Women for 2017-2020. Available at <https://www.provinceditalia.it/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Piano-operativo-2017-2020.pdf>

Poland

- The Act on the Implementation of Certain Provisions of the European Union in the Field of Equal Treatment
- National Action Program for Equal Treatment for 2013-2021, The Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment (2013), Krajowy Program działań na rzecz

równego traktowania na lata 2013-2021 Available at:
https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/wp-content/uploads/sites/15/2019/11/Poland_National-Action-Program-for-Equal-Treatment-2013-2016.pdf [01.05.2021]

- National Action Program for Equal Treatment for 2013-2021, The Government Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment (2013), Krajowy Program działań na rzecz równego traktowania na lata 2013-2021. Available at:
https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/wp-content/uploads/sites/15/2019/11/Poland_National-Action-Program-for-Equal-Treatment-2013-2016.pdf [01.05.2021]

Portugal

- National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination 2018-2030 – Portugal + Equal (ENINDI, approved by the XXI Constitutional Government on March 8, 2018, it is published in Diário da República (Resolution of the Council of Ministers No. 61/2018, of May 21). see: <https://dre.pt/application/conteudo/115360036>
- Action Plan for Equality between Women and Men
- Action Plan for the Prevention and Combating of Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence
- Action Plan to Combat Discrimination on grounds of Sexual Orientation, Gender Identity and Expression, and Sexual Characteristics
- NP 4552:2016, for the reconciliation of work, family and personal life

Portugal - Azores

- III Regional Plan for the Prevention and Combat of Domestic Violence 2019-2022 (previous: Regional Plan for The Prevention and combating Domestic Violence (2010-2012), II Regional Plan for the Prevention and Combat of Domestic and Gender Violence (2014-2018) available at <https://portal.azores.gov.pt/>

Romania

- **Law no. 202/2002 on equal opportunities and equal treatment for men and women** (“Legea nr. 202/2002 privind egalitatea de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați), amended by Government Ordinance No. 84/2004, Law No. 501/2004, Law No. 340/2006, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 56/2006, Law No. 340/2006, Law No. 507/2006, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 68/2010, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 83/2012, Law No. 115/2013, Law No. 229/2015, Law No. 178/2018, Law No. 232/2018 (implementing Article 157 TFEU and Recast Directive 2006/54/EC); 7 June 2002 (Amended 10 August 2020). Available at <https://lege5.ro/Gratuit/geytinjsqy/legea-nr-202-2002-privind-egalitatea-de-sanse-si-de-tratament-intre-femei-si-barbati>
- **Government Ordinance No. 137/2000 regarding the prevention and sanctioning of all forms of discrimination** (“Ordonanța nr. 137/2000 privind prevenirea și sancționarea tuturor formelor de discriminare”), amended by Law No. 48/2002, Government Ordinance No. 77/2003, Law No. 27/2004, Law No. 324/2006, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 75/2008, Law No. 61/2013,

Government Emergency Ordinance No. 19/2013, Law No. 189/2013, Law No. 153/2017 (general multi-ground antidiscrimination law, implementing the Racial Equality Directive (Directive 2000/43/EC) and the Equality Framework Directive (Directive 2000/78/EC); 31 August 2000, (137/2000). Available at <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/24129>

- **Government Emergency Ordinance No. 96/2003 regarding the protection of maternity at the workplace** ("Ordonanța de Urgență nr. 96/2003 privind protecția maternității la locurile de muncă"), amended by Law No. 25/2004, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 158/2005, Law No. 154/2015 (implementing Directive 92/85/EEC and relevant provisions of Directive 2006/54/EC regarding pregnancy); 27 October 2003, (96/2003). Available at <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/47216>
- **Government Emergency Ordinance No. 61/2008 regarding the implementation of the principle of equal treatment between women and men with respect to access to goods and the provision of services** ("Ordonanța de Urgență nr. 61/2008 privind implementarea principiului egalității de tratament între femei și bărbați în ceea ce privește accesul la bunuri și servicii și furnizarea de bunuri și servicii"), amended by Law No. 62 of 1.4.2009, Law No. 128 of 26.4.2013 (implementing Directive 2004/113/EC); 14 May 2008, (61/2008). Available at <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/93183>
- **Government Emergency Ordinance No. 111 of 8.12.2010 on the leave and monthly allowance for child rearing** ("Ordonanța de Urgență nr. 111 din 8 decembrie 2010 privind concediul și indemnizația lunară pentru creșterea copiilor"), amended by Law No. 132 of 27.6.2011, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 124 of 27.12.2011, Law No. 166 of 9.10.2012, Law No. 187 of 24.10.2012, Law No. 126 of 23.9.2014, Law No. 66 of 19.4.2016, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 82 of 16.11.2016, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 6 of 18.1.2017, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 82 of 8.11.2017, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 15 of 7.3.2018, Government Emergency Ordinance No. 81 of 13.9.2018, Law No. 89 of 2.5.2019 (implementing Directive 2010/18/EU, 8 December 2010, (111/2010). Available at <http://www.mmuncii.ro/j33/images/Documente/Legislatie/2016/OUgnr111din2010.pdf>
- **Government Program 2020 – 2024**; Romanian Government, "Program de Guvernare 2020 – 2014" 23 December 2020. Available at https://gov.ro/fisiere/pagini_fisiere/Program_de_guvernare_2020_2024.pdf
- **National Strategy for the Promotion of Equal Opportunities and Treatment for Women and Men and Fighting against Domestic Violence for 2021-2027, Ministry of Labour and Social Protection (Justice)**, "Strategia națională privind promovarea egalității de șanse și de tratament între femei și bărbați și prevenirea și combaterea violenței domestice pentru perioada 2021-2027", Published 19 April 2021. Available at http://www.mmuncii.ro/j33/images/Documente/MMPS/Transparenta_decizionala/09032021Anexa_1_SNESVD_cu_ANDPDCA_CNPP_29_01.pdf

Slovenia

- Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2015–2020 (Resolucija o nacionalnem programu za enake možnosti žensk in moških 2015–2020 (Uradni list RS, št. 84/15) Available at <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=RESO108>
- Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, “Zakon o enakih možnostih žensk in moških” (“Equal Opportunities for Women and Men Act”), (2002) (Uradni list RS, št. 59/02, 61/07 – ZUNEO-A, 33/16 – ZVarD in 59/19) (In Slovenian: <http://pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO3418>; (in English: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/cm?idStrani=prevodi>).
- Government of Republic Slovenia, “Resolucija o nacionalnem programu za enake možnosti žensk in moških 2015–2020”, (“Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2015–2020”), (2015), (ReNPEMŽM15–2) (Uradni list RS, št. 84/15), <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=RESO108>
- Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, “Zakon o varstvu pred diskriminacijo” (ZVarD), (“Protection against discrimination Act”)(Uradni list: 33/2016, 21/2018-ZNorg); Active since: 23. 5. 2016; (In Slovenian: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO7273>); (In English: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/cm?idStrani=prevodi>).
- Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, Periodical Plan for Implementation of the Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men for years 2016-2017, available at <https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MDDSZ/Dokumenti/Enakost-spolov/12abf7bed8/NPZEMZMPeriodicni20162017.pdf>.
- Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, Periodical Plan for Implementation of the Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men for years 2018-2019, available at <https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MDDSZ/Dokumenti/Enakost-spolov/489adce54f/NPZEMZMPeriodicniNacrt20182019.pdf>
- Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, Department The Equal Opportunities, “Towards Equalizing Power Relations between Women and Men (2013–2016)”, (2016), [Gender Equality in Slovenia.pdf \(globalwps.org\)](#).
- Ministry of Public Administration, “Zakon o sistemu plač v javnem sektorju (ZSPJS)”, (“Public Sector Salary System Act”), (2018), <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO3328>
- Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, “Zakon o delovnih razmerjih”, (“Employment Relationships Act”), (2017), <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/cm?idStrani=prevodi>

Slovakia

- Act No. 460/1992 Coll. Constitution of the Slovak Republic (Zákon č. 460/1992 Z.z. Ústava Slovenskej republiky);
- Act No. 365/2004 Coll. on Equal Treatment in Certain Areas and on Protection against Discrimination and on Amendment of Certain Acts (Anti-discrimination Act), (Zákon č. 365/2004 Z.z. o rovnakom zaobchádzaní v niektorých oblastiach a o ochrane pred diskrimináciou a o zmene a doplnení niektorých zákonov (antidiskriminačný zákon));

- Act No. 311/2001 Coll. on the Labour Code (Zákon č. 311/2001 Z.z. Zákonník práce);
- Act No. 552/2003 Coll. on Works Performed in the Public Interest (Zákon č. 552/2003 Z.z. o výkone práce vo verejnom záujme);
- Act No. 461/2003 Coll. on Social Insurance (Zákon č. 461/2003 Z.z. o sociálnom poistení)
- Act No. 124/2006 Coll. on Work Safety and Health (Zákon č. 124/2006 Z.z. o bezpečnosti a ochrane zdravia pri práci);
- Act No. 125/2006 Coll. on Labour Inspection (Zákon č. 125/2006 Z.z. o inšpekcii práce)

2. List of national legislation and policies in terms of gender equality in research, innovation and higher education

Bulgaria

- The Roadmap for Research and Innovation
- Law on Higher Education
- Strategy for Promotion of Equality between women and men for the period 2021-2025 at the University of Ruse "A. Kanchev"
- Rules of Procedure of the respective institution
- Ordinance on the terms and conditions for the evaluation, planning, distribution and spending of funds from the state budget for financing the inherent scientific or artistic activity of the MES (adopted by CMD C 233 of 10.09.2016, Promulgated SG no. 73/16.09.2016)
- Regulations on the terms and conditions for obtaining scientific degrees and holding academic positions at the University.
- Regulations for the structure and activity of the University.
- The collective labour agreement with the Trade Unions of the Higher School.

Spain

- Guidelines for the development of the European Space for Research (ERA) in Spain 2016-2020
- 1st Gender Equality Action Plan 2021-2023 of the National Agency of Research for I+D+I; Agencia Estatal de Investigación, "I Gender Equality Plan of the State Research Agency of Spain for R&D&I funding activities", 2021. Available at: https://www.ciencia.gob.es/stfls/MICINN/AEI/ficheros/I_GENDER_EQUALITY_PLAN.pdf [30/04/2021].
- Constitutional Law 3/2007, 22nd March, for the effective equality of women and men, the Science, Technology and Innovation Law and the National Strategy of Science and Technology, and Innovation 2013-2020
- Art. 14 y 9.2 of the Spanish Constitution 1978 (research performance organisations, universities, and research funding agencies)

- Royal Decree 259/2019, 12th April, that regulates Gender Equality Units in National Administrative Organisations (research performance organisations, universities, and research funding agencies)
- Royal Decree 431/2020, 3rd March, that established the basic structure of the Ministry of Universities (Universities)
- Law 14/2011, 1st June, for Science, Technology, and Innovation (research performance organisations, universities, and research funding agencies)
- National Strategy of Science, Technology, and Innovation 2013-2020 (research performance organisations, universities, and research funding agencies)
- the Order PRE/525/2005, of 7th March
- Royal Decree 1614/2009, 26th October, that stipulates the ordinance for official artistic studies regulated by the Constitutional Law 2/2006, 3rd May of education.
- Royal Decree 43/2015, 2nd February, that stipulates the ordinance for official university studies.
- Royal Decree 99/2011, 28th January, that regulates official PhD Studies.
- The Organic Law 4/2007 of Universities demands higher commitment for gender equality in universities
- the Preface III of the Law 9/2017, 8th November, regarding the Work Contracts in the Public Sector, that integrates the Directives of the European Parliament and the Ministry 2014/23/UE and 2014/24/UE, 26th February 2014, in the Spanish legal ordinance
- Chapter I art. 4.1 section i) of the Legislative Royal Decree 5/2015, 30th October, that approves the amendments of the Civil Servants Legal Status Act, establishing the non-discrimination in the hiring process of civil servants and its rights
- 3rd Gender Equality Action Plan for the National Administration Organisations and all dependant institutions from 29th December
- Resolution of the Ministry of Universities of 16th September 2008, which includes the recommendations of the European Commission, 11th March 2005, regarding the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers

Spain - the Canary Island

- Law 1/2010, of 26 February, of the Canary Islands on equality between women and men (Arts. 22 y 23)
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